

**Monitoring, Evaluating and Modelling Sea Ice
and Climate Changes in the Arctic
(MONARC/MODARC)**

Technical Report No. 223

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Introduction

Recent analysis of sea ice cover in the Arctic have revealed that significant have occurred in the latter decades of the last century. For example, from the analysis of a recently declassified dataset of upward-looking sonar observations from US nuclear submarines it have been shown that the average ice thickness has decreased by 1.3 m, from 3.1 m in the 1958-1976 period to 1.8 m in 1990s; i. e., an average 4 cm per year, or 40% of the total ice volume [Rothrock et al., 1999]. Furthermore, analysis of microwave satellite observations have established that the multi-year ice area has decreased by 6% over last two decades analyzed (1978-1998) [Johannessen et al., 1995; Bjørge et al., 1997; Cavalieri et al., 1997], while the perennial multi-year ice area has decreased 14% over this period [Johannessen et al., 1999]. An analysis of sea ice observations (in situ and satellite) since 1900 in comparison with trends shown in two coarse-resolution global climate models – forced by observed greenhouse gases and tropospheric sulfate aerosols – found a good correlation [Vinnicov et al., 1999]. The analysis “strongly suggests” that the observed decrease in sea ice since around 1950 is related to anthropogenic global warming, and predictions by these two models suggests a substantial further decrease of the ice extent in this century [Vinnicov et al., 1999].

These most recent sea ice findings [Johannessen et al., 1999; Rothrock et al., 1999; Vinnicov et al., 1999] have received much attention not only in sea ice and climate research community, but also the general scientific community, and even the general public, through reportings in the international mass media. The reason for this interest is the critical importance of the larger context, namely the global climate change.

The global climate system is recently undergoing uncontrolled experiment as a result of man’s increasing emissions of carbon dioxide (CO₂) and other greenhouse gases and aerosols into the atmosphere. The changes in global mean temperature are predicted to exceed their natural variability between the decades 1980 and 2010 [Cubasch et al., 1995]. The use of “fingerprint” detection method [Hasselmann et al., 1995] has concluded that there is a 95% probability that the observed temperature increases during the last century are to human activities. The consensus from the numerical modelling community is that greenhouse warming will be enhanced in the Polar Regions, especially the Arctic [Barron et al., 1995], with a predicted warming 3-4 °C during the next 50 years [Mitchell et al., 1995]. The enhanced polar warming predicted by coupled atmosphere-ocean general circulation models (GCMs) suggests that the Arctic could be the first region to undergo substantial changes associated with global warming.

The predominant feature of the physical environment of the Arctic is the presence of sea ice cover, which is perennial in the central Arctic and at least seasonal in the marginal seas. The variability of sea ice is important climatologically, oceanographically and biologically, through the variety of interactions. For example, sea ice’s relatively fast response time suggests that a prediction in the Arctic sea ice cover is one of the most probable early effects of greenhouse warming [Barron, 1995; Mitchell et al., 1995].

Satellite remote sensing observations play an important role in improving our knowledge of arctic environmental and climate variability [Kondratyev et al., 1996]. In particular, passive microwave satellite measurements have been used to provide repetitive, spatially continuous, large-scale information on various climate parameters, including sea ice [Ferraro et al., 1994]. Analysis of data from the Scanning Multi-channel Microwave Radiometer (SMMR) from 1978-87 revealed a 2% reduction of in the Arctic sea ice extent

[Gloersen and Campbell, 1991; Johannessen et al., 1995] found large decreases in the period 1987-94, using data from the subsequent Special Sensor Microwave Imager (SSM/I). Significant reductions in the Arctic sea ice cover have recently been more firmly established using merged SSMR-SSM/I time series data 1978-96 [Björge et al., 1997; Cavalieri et al., 1997].

The seasonality and forcing mechanisms behind the decreases in arctic ice extent in 1990s have been analyzed using SSMR-SSM/I data (1979-95) together with meteorological data fields [Maslanic et al., 1996]. The ice reductions were found to be most pronounced in the Siberian sector in the summer, with record low ice minima in 1900, 1993 and 1999, apparently linked to atmospheric circulation anomalies – in particular, an increase in low pressure systems and associated advection of warm air from the Eurasian landmass in the 1990s. The pronounced summer reduction suggests consequential changes in other aspects (e.g., perennial ice pack 0 of the ice cover. Perennial, multi-year ice (i.e., having survived the summer melt) ice is ~3 times thicker than the first year or seasonal ice (~1-2 m), such that changes in their distribution could also both reflect and effect climate change. Multi-year (MY) and first year (FY) ice have different radiative properties, permitting discrimination using multi-channel passive microwave T_B data, during the winter months when their signatures are relatively stable. The possibility of monitoring interannual variations of MY ice area was explored earlier using SSMR data [Camiso, 1992], but its potential has remained under-released, until Johannessen et al. [1995].

Johannessen et al. [1999] analyzed 20 years of SSMR and SSM/I data to reduce and analyze spatially-integrated time series of MY and FY ice areas decreased $0.031 \times 10^6 \text{ km}^2 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ averaged over the same 5 months. The observed decrease in MY ice area represents a proportionally large (~7% per decade) reduction in the MY ice area 1978-98, compared with ~2% per decade decrease in the total ice area in winter. The apparent 14% reduction in MY ice area over two decades is corroborated by other analyses, such as a SSMR-SSM/I data analysis that found an 8% increase (5.3 days) in the length of the sea ice melt season in the Arctic from 1978-96 [Smith, 1998]. It is also supported by an analysis of oceanographic data that has revealed changes in the Arctic water masses since the 1970s that are reasoned to stem from a substantial (~2 m) melting of perennial MY ice [McPhee et al., 1998].

In order to assess the significance of the observed reduction of MY ice area in terms of mass balance, spatially- and temporally- coincident data on ice thickness are needed. Spatially averaged ice thickness estimates from Russian drifting stations have been compared with MY ice area during the common observation period 1978-91, finding a close positive correlation between these parameters. The observed relationship with ice thickness suggests that observed decrease in MY ice area (1978-98) represents more than a peripheral effect [Johannessen et al., 1999]. However, the available data remain inadequate to produce a real climatology of arctic ice thickness, and there remain great uncertainties concerning ice thickness trends. For example, the above mentioned ice thickness estimates indicate a 5 cm decrease per decade, substantially less than results from analyses of nuclear submarine data [Rothrock et al., 1999].

It is critical to resolve the remaining discrepancies and to continue to monitor and analyze these “awakenings in the Arctic” [McDonald, 1996] as they occur. It remains uncertain whether or not recent reduction in the Arctic sea ice cover are indeed manifestations of greenhouse warming, whether quasi-periodic fluctuations may predominate [Gloersen, 1995], or whether inaccuracies in the satellite data analyses *per se* are responsible [Walsh,

1995]. Indeed, the general question of homogeneous data and analytical techniques is considered to be most critical issue for long-term climatic monitoring [Karl et al., 1995; Mahlam, 1995].

The reasons behind the recently-observed patterns also remain speculative, though synoptic-scale atmospheric circulation anomalies appear to play the key role [Serreze et al., 1995; Maslanic et al., 1996; Deser et al., 2000]. For example, the exact relationship between the patterns of Arctic sea ice fluctuations and atmospheric circulation features such as the North Atlantic/Arctic Oscillation (NOA/AO) remains speculative, though some relationships and feedback loops have recently been proposed [Mysak and Venegas, 1998; Kwok et al., 1999; Deser et al., 2000; Kwok, 2000], base on observational data. The connection of atmospheric circulation anomalies underscores the need to consistently produce and analyze longer-term sea ice datasets. Indeed, that is possible that should atmospheric circulation anomalies seen in, e.g. NAO and OA indices during recent decades return to “normal”, the Arctic sea ice cover would probably rebound accordingly. On the other hand, these atmospheric circulation anomalies themselves may be part of global warming.

The potential of combining observational and modelling approaches to better understanding sea ice variability and trends has scarcely been reached, though, as mentioned earlier, Vinnicov et al., [1999] contend that greenhouse gas emissions are most probably behind the reductions observed in recent decades. The proposed research will use observations and models to significantly address the gaps in our knowledge of sea ice and climate variability in the Arctic. Moreover, the projects observational data sets will serve to modelling tools for studying regional climate patterns. These studies will improve the quantification of climate parameters and their seasonal, interannual and interdecadal climate variability. It will also improve our understanding of regional sea ice-climate processes. It will do focused on the Arctic, a key region for the climate and environment of Norway and northwestern Russia and their adjacent seas.

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1. Processing and integration of satellite data

1.1. Up-dating merged SMMR-SSM/I time series for the period 1978-2001

The global sea ice cover is considered to be a potential early indicator of global warming, which numerical models expect to be enhanced in the polar regions, particularly in the Arctic. Satellite passive microwave remote sensing has become one of the most important tools for examining the general characteristics of the global sea ice cover because of capability of providing observations both day and night, in almost all weather conditions, and due to global coverage of observations. The large contrast between the emissivity of sea ice and that of the ocean has been successfully utilised to obtain characteristics of the ice cover. Among the most useful sea ice parameters that can be derived from passive microwave data is sea ice concentration, from which ice extent, ice area and the area of open water within the ice pack can be calculated.

1.1.1. Data description

The present study is based on the merged SMMR-SSM/I sea ice time series from 1978-2001. The SMMR sensor data were acquired at 2-day intervals, and consist of T_{BS} measured at about 7, 11, 18, 21 and 37 GHz, horizontally and vertically polarized. The SSM/I data are 1-day polarized T_{BS} measured at about 19, 22, 37 and 85 GHz. The main parameters of the sensors are summarised in Table 1.1. The SMMR and SSM/I data sets in SSM/I north polar stereographic projection were obtained on CD-ROMs produced and distributed by the National Snow and Ice Data Center (NSIDC), Boulder, Colorado, USA.

1.1.2. Algorithm for data processing

The NORSEX algorithm [Svendsen et al., 1983] is used here to calculate first-year (FY) ice, multi-year (MY) ice and open water (OW) fractions in the Northern Hemisphere. Fig. 1.1 illustrates how the total ice cover is formed. According to this algorithm the brightness temperature from three-component footprint is assumed to be the sum of individual emitted brightness temperatures, weighted by the corresponding fractions of area:

$$T_B = C_{MY}e_{MY}T_{MY} + C_{FY}e_{FY}T_{FY} + C_{OW}e_{OW}272, \quad (1.1)$$

where C_{MY}, C_{FY}, C_{OW} are concentrations of multi-year ice, first-year ice and fraction of open water area, which are supposed to cover the field of view of the instrument, e_{MY}, e_{FY}, e_{OW} are emissivities of the respective components and T_{MY} and T_{FY} are temperatures of two types of ice, which are related to monthly average atmospheric surface temperature. Fractions, corresponding to multiyear ice, firstyear ice and open water are satisfied to the following equation:

$$1 = C_{MY} + C_{FY} + C_{OW} \quad (1.2)$$

The algorithm is very sensitive to the emissivities of the three types of surfaces and emissivities of multi-year ice are known to vary considerably both in time and space [Comiso, 1986; Comiso, 1990; Svendsen et al., 1983], so it was very important to construct the emissivity model adequately representing the three-component surface. Trying to increase the quality of calculations of multi-year ice parameters, we concentrated on the winter period – from November to March. For the purpose of improvement the algorithm, we: 1) used published field data [Carsey, 1992; Comiso, 1986; Grenfell, 1992; Svendsen et al., 1983] on measured emissivities in the Arctic; 2) used additional developed filter for removing false multi-year ice signals; 3) controlled the discrepancies between summer ice pack and multi-year ice maps during winter, trying to provide a reasonable correspondence between them.

Weather filters suggested by [Cavalieri et al., 1991] and [Gloersen et al., 1986] are used. Calculations for summer were made with the use of the version of NORSEX algorithm adjusted for the purpose of integrating data sets from SMMR and SSM/I sensor [Bjørge et al., 1997].

Table 1.1.
Parameters of sensors and satellites, which observations have been used in the study

Satellite	altitude, km	incidence angle, deg	sensor	resolution	polarization	frequencies GHz	period of measurements
Nimbus 7	955	50.2	Scanning Multichannel Microwave Radiometer (SMMR)	25 km x 25 km	H & V	6.63 10.69 18.00 21.00 37.00	November 1978 – August 1987
Defence Meteorological Satellite Program (DMSP)	860/ 830	53.1	Special Sensor Microwave Imager (SSM/I)	25 km x 25 km, (12.5 x 12.5 km for 85.5 GHz)	H & V V H & V H & V	19.35 22.24 37.00 85.50	July 1987 – present

Fig. 1.1. Microwave-derived ice concentrations. The total ice concentration is calculated as a sum of concentrations of two fractions – multi-year ice and first-year ice.

1.1.3. Results

Changes in the total ice cover

In the present study we have processed SMMR (1978-87) and SSM/I (1987-2001) data into merged, continuous, time series of sea ice concentration, area and extent (see Fig. 1.2). No additional SSM/I adjustments were made in order to consider the possible effects of inconsistencies between F8/F11/F13 SSM/I brightness temperatures, following the conclusion of [Stroeve et al., 1998] that although local and regional effects can be significant, any biases are not significant in terms of hemispheric averages such as those produced here. Due to

differences in latitudinal coverage between SMMR and SSM/I, ice concentrations poleward of 84 degrees were not included in the merged time series. In Fig. 1.2 you see monthly averaged total ice area for Northern Hemisphere over the whole period of observations. Maximum corresponds to the winter months and minimum – to the summer month. Minimum ice cover in the Arctic is usually observed in September.

Fig. 1.2. Variability of total ice area in the Northern Hemisphere (do not include the area north of 84° latitude: 1410104 km²) over the period 1978-2001, as derived from SMMR and SSM/I data. Marks on the time axis correspond to the 1st January of each year.

Changes in the multi-year ice cover

In the analysis of multi-year ice dynamics we used monthly averages instead of daily averages to minimise weather effects, which can significantly change the results from one day to another. The use of monthly averages also reduces high frequency noise, facilitating the analysis of the interannual variability and trends of multi-year ice during the continuous period of satellite observations. The study has been done only for winter months (November – March) when the signatures are relatively stable because of absence of melt ponding effects in that time.

As was mentioned earlier, we have used the NORSEX algorithm to calculate multi-year ice concentrations on the base of passive microwave measurements. As in [Comiso, 1997], we assume that the emissivity of multi-year ice is single-valued and second-year ice has emissivities identical to that of the older ice types. Seasonal variations of emissivity are taken into account through an additional filter for removing false multi-year ice signals. Our results on variations of multi-year ice during winters are presented in Fig. 1.3. The plot represents multi-year ice area for each winter month of the period of observations for the Northern Hemisphere (do not include the area north of 84° latitude: 1410104 km²).

Fig. 1.3. Variability of multi-year ice area in the Northern Hemisphere (do not include the area north of 84° latitude: 1410104 km^2) over the period 1978-2001, as derived from SMMR and SSM/I data. Marks on the time axis correspond to the 1st January of each year.

1.1.4. Testing and modification of used program software

The program software for calculation of multi-year and first-year ice parameters is based on NORSEX algorithm. This computer program was developed by Kjell Kloster and Einar Bjørge (NERSC). In further the program was modified by Elena Shalina (NIERSC). The program is divided on three subprograms:

1. Estimating total ice concentration in grid pixels for each two days (SMMR data) or for each day (SSM/I data). This procedure performs calculation of multi-year and first-year ice concentrations and sum of these values.
2. Estimating only multi-year ice concentration in grid pixels for each two days (SMMR data) or for each day (SSM/I data). The procedure of calculation of multi-year ice concentration are different from the same procedure in the first subprogram. The discrepancy of procedures will be specified later.
3. Computing monthly means for ice concentration in grid pixels, ice area and ice extent for chosen ice kind (total or multi-year ice) for the whole northern SSM/I grid.

Possible steps of a program modification were carried out after its careful analysis.

1. The first and the second subprograms use a data file, contained latitude values of centers of grid pixels. The data file was written with an error. One latitude value was lost. For the analysis we used a new data file from CD DMSP F_13 SSMI TB Grid Volume 16: 1/1/99-3/31/99 (NSIDC). The corrected latitude values for the Northern Hemisphere were created on June 22, 1999. Possible corrections for estimating total (Table 1.2) and multi-year (Table 1.3) ice areas were calculated for the winter 1998-1999. The difference between the old and corrected values does not exceeds 0.3%. Nevertheless this correction is necessary for obtaining true ice concentration values in grid pixels.
2. The third subprogram uses a data file with area values of grid pixels. This file was created in June 1997. Thereafter the NSIDC corrected the northern SSM/I grid in June 1999. We used the corrected data file and obtained new ice area values (Tables 1.2-1.3). Values of correction to the multi-year ice area during the winter are relatively constant with the

mean value of 5.2%. On the contrary, values of correction for the total ice area are decreased from November (5.8%) to March (2.9%). This decreasing is connected with increasing (during the winter) total ice area in more south latitudes, where area correction values are smaller (Fig. 1.4).

3. The first and the second subprograms use a subroutine "buffer_zone()", created for the reasonable calculation of sea ice parameters in the coastal zone. A subroutine argument 'buffer' is calculated with an error. The results of error revisions are shown in Tables 1.2-1.3. The difference between old and corrected values of the ice area does not exceed 1.1%, but it can be appreciable in some pixels.
4. The first and the second subprograms have similar subroutines "norsex()" and "norsexm()" correspondingly. These procedures contain a basis of the NORSEX algorithm. We found an error in calculation of the argument 't_atm_surf' in the subroutine "norsexm()". Correction of this error essentially changes multi-year ice area values (Table 1.3). Maximum correction value (10.2%) was obtained for February. We can suppose that the monthly values of multi-year ice area correction will be roughly constant for different years. But this supposition needs a confirmation. A mitigating circumstance in the case is partly neutralization of all corrections each other (Table 1.3).

As we noted in Item 4, "norsex()" and "norsexm()" procedures contain a basis of the NORSEX algorithm. These subroutines use different equations for calculation of the multi-year ice thermodynamic temperature ('t_ice'):

$$\begin{array}{l|l} t_ice = 0.4*t_atm_mean + 0.6*OCEAN_TEMP; & | \text{ norsex()} \\ t_ice = t_atm_mean. & | \text{ norsexm()} \end{array}$$

Table 1.2.

Example of total ice area corrections for the whole northern SSM/I grid (the area to the north of 84° latitude: 1410104 km² is not included) in the winter 1998-1999

YEAR	MONTH	ICE AREA (sq. km)	DIFFERENCE (sq. km)	DIFFERENCE (%)	CODE VERSION
1998	11	7 997 463			CURRENT
		7 984 702	-12 762	-0.2	+ NEW LATITUDES
		8 460 575	463 112	5.8	+ NEW AREAS
		7 939 270	-58 193	-0.7	+ NEW 'buffer'
		8 396 770	399 307	5.0	+ ALL NEWS
1998	12	9 901 479			CURRENT
		9 888 668	-12 812	-0.1	+ NEW LATITUDES
		10 380 992	479 513	4.8	+ NEW AREAS
		9 896 897	-4 582	0.0	+ NEW 'buffer'
		10 369 842	468 363	4.7	+ ALL NEWS
1999	1	11 414 266			CURRENT
		11 401 505	-12 761	-0.1	+ NEW LATITUDES
		11 848 805	434 539	3.8	+ NEW AREAS
		11 421 765	7 499	0.1	+ NEW 'buffer'
		11 845 049	430 783	3.8	+ ALL NEWS
1999	2	12 331 863			CURRENT
		12 319 051	-12 812	-0.1	+ NEW LATITUDES
		12 698 008	366 146	3.0	+ NEW AREAS
		12 350 605	18 742	0.2	+ NEW 'buffer'
		12 703 665	371 802	3.0	+ ALL NEWS
1999	3	12 416 249			CURRENT
		12 403 437	-12 811	-0.1	+ NEW LATITUDES
		12 774 410	358 161	2.9	+ NEW AREAS
		12 432 576	16 327	0.1	+ NEW 'buffer'
		12 777 691	361 442	2.9	+ ALL NEWS

Table 1.3.

Example of multi-year ice area corrections for the whole northern SSM/I grid (the area to the north of 84° latitude: 1410104 km² is not included) in the winter 1998-1999

YEAR	MONTH	ICE AREA (sq. km)	DIFFERENCE (sq. km)	DIFFERENCE (%)	CODE VERSION
1998	11	3 083 493			CURRENT
		3 079 600	-3 893	-0.1	+ NEW LATITUDES
		3 235 263	151 771	4.9	+ NEW AREAS
		2 931 339	-152 153	-4.9	+ NEW 't_atm_surf'
		3 049 035	-34 458	-1.1	+ NEW 'buffer'
		3 043 491	-40 002	-1.3	+ ALL NEWS
1998	12	3 517 451			CURRENT
		3 508 440	-9 011	-0.3	+ NEW LATITUDES
		3 698 253	180 802	5.1	+ NEW AREAS
		3 229 431	-288 020	-8.2	+ NEW 't_atm_surf'
		3 502 948	-14 503	-0.4	+ NEW 'buffer'
		3 373 013	-144 438	-4.1	+ ALL NEWS
1999	1	4 090 569			CURRENT
		4 082 668	-7 901	-0.2	+ NEW LATITUDES
		4 304 551	213 982	5.2	+ NEW AREAS
		3 682 127	-408 442	-10.0	+ NEW 't_atm_surf'
		4 060 389	-30 180	-0.7	+ NEW 'buffer'
		3 848 371	-242 198	-5.9	+ ALL NEWS
1999	2	4 327 390			CURRENT
		4 318 768	-8 622	-0.2	+ NEW LATITUDES
		4 562 374	234 983	5.4	+ NEW AREAS
		3 887 014	-440 376	-10.2	+ NEW 't_atm_surf'
		4 284 200	-43 190	-1.0	+ NEW 'buffer'
		4 053 608	-273 782	-6.3	+ ALL NEWS
1999	3	4 574 495			CURRENT
		4 567 532	-6 963	-0.2	+ NEW LATITUDES
		4 820 157	245 662	5.4	+ NEW AREAS
		4 115 912	-458 583	-10.0	+ NEW 't_atm_surf'
		4 534 059	-40 436	-0.9	+ NEW 'buffer'
		4 294 469	-280 026	-6.1	+ ALL NEWS

Here 't_atm_mean' – is a monthly thermodynamic temperature of surface atmosphere; 'OCEAN_TEMP' - mean thermodynamic temperature of open water surface. Several questions occurred to us from analysis of these equations:

- A. Why different equations are used for the calculation of the multi-year ice surface temperature?
- B. Why 't_atm_mean' values for the Arctic were acquired from the ESMR Antarctic atlas ["Antarctic Sea Ice, 1973-1976: Satellite Passive-Microwave Observations"]?
- C. Why 't_atm_mean' values vary for different months and suppose to be constant for different Arctic regions? It is also necessary to note that the northern SSM/I grid includes areas from 31°N and the ice concentration is calculated for whole SSM/I grid, but not for the Arctic separately. Also an atmospheric correction procedure should be used for calculation of the brightness temperatures in the Arctic and subarctic regions.

Fig. 1.4. Pixel area difference (km²) between corrected and old data for the whole northern SSM/I grid. The picture contains two contour lines, where the difference is equal to zero.

1.2. Analysis of the estimates of sea ice parameters, retrieved with the NORSEX algorithm, using numerical experiments

One of the Project tasks included a detailed analysis of the accuracy of the multiyear sea ice concentration estimates, obtained with the use of the NORSEX algorithm. We estimated changes of the first-year and multiyear sea ice concentrations, caused by the natural variability of the input parameters, such as sea ice and open water emissivities, sea ice and atmospheric temperatures. The used approach consisted of simulating possible variations of $T_b(19)$ and $T_b(37)$, caused by the natural changes of afore-mentioned input parameters. The estimates have been conducted for the typical March conditions and the following surface types: compact multiyear ice, compact first-year ice, open water and mixture of multiyear (80%) and first-year (20%) ice.

1.2.1. Variations of retrieved C_{my} , C_{fy} , and C_{ow} due to natural variations of sea ice and open water emissivities

The following sea ice and open water emissivities are used in the NORSEX algorithm:

Surface type	19.35 GHz	37 GHz
water	0.65	0.75
FY-ice	0.97	0.97
MY-ice	0.82	0.74

According to Carsey [1992], which analyzed different series of in situ observations sea ice measurements, the average value and standard deviations for E_{my37} amounts to 0.764 and 0.079, and for E_{my19} – to 0.850 and 0.068, correspondingly. There is also an indication that E_{my37} and E_{my19} are correlated. By means of approximation of this dependence the following estimate was obtained:

$$E_{my19} = 0.657 * E_{my37} + 0.330$$

Fig. 1.5a shows variations of retrieved parameters due to variations of MY-ice emissivities for compact MY-ice. If E_{my37} is less than that in the NORSEX algorithm, than obtained estimate for C_{my} amounts to 100% or more. If E_{my} increase above this threshold, than C_{my} decrease and reach 60% for $E_{my37}=0.84$. Fig. 1.5d shows variations of retrieved parameters due to variations of MY-ice emissivities for the case of mixture of MY (80%) and FY (20%) ice. In this case, estimates for C_{my} decrease from almost 100% to 45% and true estimate is obtained only for $E_{my37}=0.74$ (NORSEX threshold value).

According to Carsey [1992], the average value and standard deviations for E_{fy37} amounts to 0.955 and 0.015, and for E_{fy19} – to 0.941 and 0.019, correspondingly. Fig. 1.5c and 1.5e show variations of retrieved parameters due to variations of FY-ice emissivities for compact FY-ice. If E_{fy37} is less than that in the NORSEX algorithm, than algorithm underestimates C_{fy} to 10% or less and false MY-ice can appear. If E_{fy19} is less than that in the NORSEX algorithm, than algorithm underestimates C_{fy} to 10% or less, and total sea ice concentration is less than 100%. Variations of OW emissivity cause sea ice concentration estimates of more than 100% (Fig 1f). These estimates are than reduced to 100% by means of filtration.

1.2.2. The variability due to changes in sea ice surface temperature and atmosphere temperature, used in the algorithm

The following parameterization for the thermodynamic temperature of the firstyear ice is used in NORSEX algorithm:

$$T_{ice} = 0.4 * T_{at} + 0.6 * T_{ocean} (=272)$$

where T_{at} – average monthly temperature for the Arctic.

Experimental studies revealed that surface temperature of firstyear sea ice varies with ice thickness and depth of snow on ice. Therefore this parameterization should be modified for more correct description in the algorithm.

NORSEX algorithm employs mean monthly atmospheric temperatures for the whole Arctic. It is known, that real thermodynamic temperatures significantly vary spatially and temporally. Fig. 1b shows estimates of variations of retrieved concentrations due to possible changes in atmospheric surface temperatures. The estimates were conducted for the case of compact firstyear ice. As it is evident from the figure, low temperatures can cause underestimation of C_{fy} and appearance of “false MY-ice”.

1.2.3. Conclusions

Conducted studies revealed that the estimates of the multiyear sea ice concentration are rather sensitive to the changes of the input parameters, such as multiyear, firstyear ice and open water emissivities, sea ice and atmosphere temperatures. As a result of natural changes of input parameters the estimates for C_{my} , C_{fy} , and C_{ow} could significantly exceed 100% or to be below 0%, and NORSEX algorithm copes with these cases by means of artificial updating of obtained estimates to 100% or to 0% correspondingly.

Based on the conducted studies the following modifications of the NORSEX algorithm could be recommended:

- 1) Retrieval of the estimates for C_{my} , C_{fy} , and C_{ow} for the delineated homogenous zones except of SSM/I pixels.
- 2) Parameterization of the temperature of sea ice surface taking into account ice thickness and depth of snow on ice.
- 3) Use of the gridded daily temperatures from NCEP reanalysis data instead of monthly temperatures for the whole Arctic.

Fig. 1.5. Variations of the retrieved fractions of open water (OW), firstyear (FYI) and multiyear (MYI) ice, caused by changes in sea ice and open water emissivities and atmospheric surface temperature.

1.3. Validation of the multi-year ice estimates using independent satellite data

Several studies were devoted to the assessment of the trends in sea ice extent and area in the Arctic from passive microwave radiometer data. Johannessen et al. (1996) had find continued decreases in Arctic ice extent and ice area, and established a decrease in the ice concentration. In the Arctic the estimated trends in ice extent and ice area are $-33\,000\text{ km}^2/\text{yr}$ and $-36\,000\text{ km}^2/\text{yr}$, correspondingly. These represent rates of decrease of 4.5% and 5.6%, respectively over the observation period from 1978-95. Previous studies of the ice cover from the 1978-87 Nimbus-7 SMMR record showed significant decreases of the Arctic ice extent with a trend of 2.4% per decade (Gloersen P., and W.J. Campbell, 1991). The decrease in overall ice concentration was 1.8%. Analysis of the SSM/I data for 1987-94 revealed greater trends in Arctic ice extent and ice area, again with no significant changes in water area or any of the Antarctic ice parameters. The $54\,000\text{ km}^2/\text{yr}$ decrease in Arctic ice extent during 1987-94 is considerably greater than the statistically significant $-32\,000\text{ km}^2/\text{yr}$ trend previously reported during the 1978-87 SMMR period (Bjorgo et al., 1997). A seasonal analysis of the Arctic trends revealed the greatest decreases to be in summer and spring. For example, the decreases in August ice area were $54\,000\text{ km}^2/\text{yr}$, as compared to the overall mean trend of $-36\,000\text{ km}^2/\text{yr}$. Taking into account relatively large summer decreases Johannessen et al. (1995) supposed larger reduction in the multiyear ice area comparatively to the total ice area. By analyzing satellite observations of the microwave emissions made from 1978 to 1998, Johannessen et al. (1999) found that the area of multiyear ice had declined by 7% per decade during the 20-year period. The winter-averaged MY ice area decreased $31\,000\text{ km}^2/\text{yr}$ as compared with a total ice area decrease of $24\,000\text{ km}^2/\text{yr}$, averaged over the same 5 months.

Taking into account the importance of obtained trends for the Climate studies careful analysis of data quality should be done. Therefore the purpose of this task of the Project consists of verification of SSM/I-derived estimates of multiyear sea ice concentration by using independent data. From the beginning several previous studies, devoted to verification of sea ice parameters, retrieved from passive microwave radiometers, have been analyzed.

1.3.1. Overview of the studies aimed on verification of the SSM/I-derived multiyear ice concentration estimates

Different algorithms were developed for calculating ice type and concentration from SMMR and SSM/I data: NASA Team, AES York and FNOC, NORSEX, U-Mass Decision, and Bootstrap Algorithms (Steffen K. et. al., 1992). Some results of conducted studies on validation of sea ice parameters, retrieved from passive microwave radiometers, are described in work by Cavalieri (1992). A validation tool for distinguishing between first-year and multiyear ice with sufficient accuracy and spatial resolution consisted of high-resolution active and passive imagers flown on aircraft. NASA and Navy SSM/I underflights across the Beaufort and Chukchi seas during the NASA validation Program (Cavalieri, 1991) provided data with which to validate multiyear ice concentrations obtained with NASA SSM/I algorithm. It was established, that algorithm correctly maps the large-scale distribution of multiyear ice: the zone of first-year ice off the Alaska coast, the large areas of mixed first-year and multiyear ice, and the region of predominantly multiyear ice north of the Canadian archipelago. Comparisons between the analyzed aircraft mosaics and the corresponding SSM/I multiyear ice concentration grids having at least 80% aircraft coverage reveal that the SSM/I algorithm overestimates multiyear ice concentration by 4+-5% on average in the Chukchi Sea and by the 12+-11% on average in the Beaufort Sea. The summary of the multiyear ice comparisons is presented in Table 1.4.

Table 1.4.
Summary of results for satellite-derived multiyear ice concentration (after Cavalieri, 1992)

Region	Month	Sensor	Mean difference +/- one standard deviation	Validation data set	Reference
Greenland sea	October	SMMR	-4 +-6a8 +- 6b	Aircraft radiometers	Svendsen et al., 1983
Beaufort sea	March	SSM/I	5.3 +-3.9c 14.2 +-11.3d	NADC/ERIM SAR	Cavalieri et al., 1991
Chukchi Sea	March	SSM/I	3.8+-4.7	NOARL/KRMS	Cavalieri et al., 1991
Beaufort Sea	March	AMMR	-6.0+-14	JPL C-band SAR	Cavalieri et al., 1991

- a- NORSEX algorithm using 10- and 37-GHz channels
- b- NORSEX algorithm using 18- and 37-GHz channels
- c- Excluding data from one of four flights that gave anomalously large biases
- d- Including data from all flights

In contrast to the total sea ice concentration comparisons, these results reveal a considerably greater variability. According to work by Grenfell (1992), this variability is attributed to a number of factors, including multiyear ice signature variability on individual floes, according to Gloersen (1992) – due to physical temperature differences at penetration depths corresponding to 19- and 37-GHz, and the influence of a variable snow cover (Cavalieri, 1991). Cavalieri (1992) concludes that there is still a great deal of uncertainty in the accuracy of Arctic multiyear sea ice concentrations. This is very likely the result of the inherent variability of the emissivity character of the ice itself, but there are too few studies from which to draw firm conclusions.

Belchansky et al. (2001) also studied accuracy of multiyear sea ice concentration retrieval from SSM/I data using NASA Team algorithm. Obtained estimates have been compared with that from Okean and RADARSAT radar images. Data covered the Greenland, Barents, Kara and Laptev seas and nearby parts of the Arctic Ocean. In all periods SSM/I gave lower MY-ice concentrations, as compared with OKEAN. Clearly evident annual variability of deviations could be mentioned between estimates from these sensors. RADARSAT ScanSAR and Standard Beam estimates of MY-ice concentrations were also more, than that from SSM/I.

Table 1.5.
Monthly average deviations between SSM/I- and Okean-01-derived MY-ice concentrations (after Belchansky et al.).

Month	1995			1996			1997		
	MYIC	SD%	N im	MYIC	SD%	N im	MYIC	SD%	N im
November	-6.1	12.3	10	-17.2	22.6	8	-13.0	18.9	8
December	-5.9	12.4	27	-8.0	16.4	17	-13.1	22.0	6
January	-4.6	14.3	26	-9.7	20.1	23	-6.6	17.5	18
February				-6.0	17.7	23	-8.2	18.2	17
March				-7.8	19.5	20	-6.0	19.3	21

In the publications by Svendsen et al. (1983), and Cavalieri (1992) the verification of MY-ice concentrations, retrieved with NORSEX algorithm, are analyzed. Svendsen et al. (1983) evaluated SMMR sea ice algorithm in the Greenland Sea by comparing with the data from aircraft radiometers along selected flight tracks during NORSEX. SMMR concentrations were obtained with the NORSEX algorithm using different combinations of SMMR channels. Using the 10- and 37-GHz combination he estimated the accuracy of the total ice concentration as $0.5 \pm 2.5\%$. As compared with a multichannel aircraft radiometer, SMMR estimates of MY-ice area, obtained with the NORSEX algorithm revealed differences of $-4 \pm 6\%$ with the 10- and 37-GHz channels and $-8 \pm 6\%$ with the 18- and 37-GHz channels, indicating that the SMMR underestimated the concentration relative to the aircraft-measured values (Cavalieri, 1992). According to Svendsen, the absolute accuracy of the aircraft-determined concentrations was $\pm 10\%$.

1.3.2. Validation data

The following validation data have been used in our analysis:

1. ERS Scatterometer data for the winter of 1995-1996 (06-12.11.95; 04-10.12.95; 01-07.01.96; 05-11.02.96; and 04-10.03.96).
2. ARGOS buoys N3311 and 3312, deployed in the Laptev Sea on September 1993 (November 1993-March 1994)
3. Ice maps, composed from Okean SLR images in the Laptev and East-Siberian seas in the winter of 1995/1995 (09.11.94; 19.11.94; 30.11.94; 07.12.94; 11.12.94; 04.01.95)
4. Okean images from ICEWATCH Project for the Barents, Kara and Laptev seas and ice charts, composed from them, for the winter of 1995/1996 (38 images, 07.01.96; 01.02.96; 02.02.96; 15.03.96; - direct comparison);
5. Okean images from ICE ROUTES Project for the Barents Sea and ice charts, composed from them for April 1998 (23.04.98 and 24.04.98)
6. MY-ice boundary, retrieved from RADARSAT image on 27.01.97 in Svalbard area
7. RADARSAT ScanSAR images for the Barents and Kara seas for March 1997 and 1998
8. ERS-2 SAR images for Severnaya Zemlya for November 4, 7 and 10, 1996

1.3.3. Comparison of SSM/I and ERS-Scatterometer data on multiyear sea ice extent and concentration

In order to compare MY-ice concentrations, retrieved from SSM/I-data and scatterometer the series of synchronous data were retrieved from both sensors for the winter of 1995/1996 (see Fig.1.6.). Patterns of the MY ice concentration could be obtained daily from SSM/I, whereas more or less complete coverage from scatterometer could be produced weekly. Therefore average weekly SSM/I-derived MY ice concentrations were compared with that from scatterometer for the following time intervals: 06-12.11.95, 04-10.12.95, 01-07.01.96, 05-11.02.96, 04-10.03.96. Sea ice classification from scatterometer data was conducted by simple thresholding (-13.98 dB) according to recommendation by Dr. Ezraty. These patterns are shown in Fig.1.6. Sea ice regime in the Arctic Ocean was studied during long time and based on this knowledge it is possible to analyze derived estimates of multiyear ice concentration. All these patterns revealed presence of MY sea ice in the central Arctic. Nevertheless, both SSM/I and scatterometer patterns show presence of MY-ice in areas, where it could not be: in the Sea of Okhotsk and Bering Sea, central and southern parts of the Barents and Kara seas, in the Pechora Sea, and in the mouths of Siberian rivers.

Fig. 1.6. SSM/I and ERS scattermeter derived patterns of multiyear ice in the Arctic during the period November 1995 – March 1996

From analysis of SSM/I data it was found, that amount of false multiyear ice increase from November to March. MY-ice concentration patterns for the periods November 06-12, 1995 and March 04-10, 1996 are shown in Fig.1.7. False multiyear ice is evident in the areas, marked by rectangular. Total area and extent of false multiyear ice in November amounted to 26,500 and 87,300 km² correspondingly, and in March – to 195,500 and 647,100 km². This partly explains the observed seasonal increase of MY-ice area, obtained with SSM/I data (see Fig.1.8.).

It was found that amount of “false multiyear ice” in the Barents, Kara and Laptev seas varies for different years. The maximum amounts were observed in the following years: 1980-1982, 1984-1985, 1988, 1991, 1996, and 1999. Insignificant amount was observed in 1987, 1990, 1993-1995, 1997-1998, and 2000-2001. The patterns of the SSM/I-retrieved multiyear sea ice concentrations are shown in Fig. 1.9. for the winters of 1980/81, 1989/90, 1990/91, 1993/94 and 1998/99. It is evident from this figure, that the amount of “false multiyear ice” in November is insignificant for all years. In March of 1990 and 1994 amount of “false multiyear ice” was also insignificant. In March of 1981, 1991, and 1999 it covered large areas in the southern and central parts of the Kara Sea, as well as some areas of the southern Barents Sea. According to regime data multiyear ice was not observed in this areas. In our opinion appearance of “false multiyear ice” can be caused by the significant natural variability of multiyear and firstyear ice emissivities on frequencies of 19 and 37 GHz, and differences between real and calculated sea ice and atmosphere temperatures. Possible influence of changing atmosphere surface temperatures on appearance of “false multiyear ice” is shown in Fig. 1.10, where a series of multiyear ice concentrations were calculated for March 1996. On March 4 the “multiyear ice” covered the whole northern part of the Barents Sea, whereas on March 12 it almost disappeared that is unreal. NCEP gridded surface temperatures significantly decreased from (-35°-50°C) on March 4 to (-2°-7°C) on March 12. After March 14 amount of “false multiyear ice” started to increase again, whereas atmospheric surface temperature started to decrease. Nevertheless increase of atmospheric surface temperature after March 27 did not cause disappearance of the multiyear ice from the northern part of the Barents Sea.

1.3.4. Comparison of the MY-ice boundary and MY sea-ice concentration, retrieved from SSM/I data with those, retrieved from satellite radar images: Okean, ERS-1/2, and RADARSAT

Multiyear ice boundary and MY sea ice concentration could be determined from satellite radar images. The resolution of these images is significantly better than that of SSM/I (25 m–for ERS SAR, 100 m–for RADARSAT ScanSAR, and 1-2 km – for Okean, as compared with 12.5 km for 85 GHz channel of SSM/I). ERS and RADARSAT operate at a wavelength of 5.6 cm and Okean–at 3.15 cm, and the difference between backscattering of MY and FY ice is larger for Okean. The work to be done includes retrieval of sea ice concentration and multiyear ice concentration from SAR images, retrieval of the same parameters from synchronous SSM/I data, comparison and analysis of these estimates. The following key areas of the Arctic Ocean ice cover were selected for comparison: ice edge, multiyear ice boundary, polynyas, and areas with predominantly multiyear ice.

Several Okean SLR images have been selected for comparison with SSM/I. These images were geolocated and interpreted. Several comparisons have been done in the Barents and Kara seas in winter of 1996 and for April of 1998. One example of these comparisons is presented in Fig. 1.11, which shows sea ice conditions in the western Arctic for the February 1, 1996.

Period	MY ice area	MY ice extent
November 06-12, 1995	26,500	87,300
March 04-10, 1996	195,500	647,100

Fig.1.7. False multiyear ice in the Western Arctic, as retrieved from SSM/I data

The boundaries for the areas with different concentrations of MY-ice (100%, 80%, 60%) near FJL and to the north of it correspond fairly well in both data sets. Nevertheless SSM/I reveal false multiyear ice in the central and northern parts of the Barents Sea and in the Pechora Sea. The summary of comparisons for series of Okean images for the north-eastern part of the Barents Sea is presented in Table 1.5.

Fig.1.8. Interannual variability of SSM/I-derived multiyear ice area for November (1), average for the period November-March (2), and for March (3)

Fig. 1.9. SSM/I-derived figures of multiyear sea ice concentration in the western Russian Arctic.

Fig.1.10. Appearance of “false multiyear ice” in the Barents Sea and its connection with the atmospheric surface temperatures.

Zone number	Zone area (km2)	C my ice (%), SSM/I	C my ice (%), "Okean"
1	120 677	99	100
2	62 731	81	80
3	36 899	60	40
4	516 562	14	0

Fig.1.11. MY-ice concentrations, as retrieved from "Okean" SLR image and SSM/I data for February 1, 1996

TABLE 1.5.

MY sea ice concentrations in the western Russian Arctic, retrieved from Okean images and synchronous SSM/I patterns.

Date	N area	Area, km2	MY ice area, km2	SSM/I-MY ice concentration	Okean MY – ice concentration
07.01.96	1	96 619	95 136	98.5	100
	2	57 852	47 240	82	80
	3	62 165	27 412	44	50
	4	58 168	0.991	2	30?
	5	429 628	18 678	4	0
01.02.96	1	120 677	119 283	99	100
	2	62 731	51 050	81	80
	3	36 899	22 292	60	40
	4	516 562	69 505	14	0
02.02.96	1	105 870	98 366	93	100
	2	52 921	31 587	60	80
	3	402 198	36 758	9	0
15.03.96	1	169 910	128 856	76	100
	2	85 690	12 868	15	70
	3	486 641	17 091	4	
23.04.98	1	128 319	60 034	47	90
	2	40 583	168	0	50?
	3	516 836	6 576	1	0
24.04.98	1	125 541	80 157	64	90
	2	29 881	8 070	27	70
	3	44 250	1 931	4	?
	4	18 959	0	0	50?

An example of comparison between MY-ice concentrations, retrieved from Okean, SSM/I and ERS scatterometer in the north-eastern part of the Kara sea is shown in Fig. 1.12. Okean image was obtained on December 31, 1995 and SSM/I and scatterometer data – on January

NUMBER OF ZONE	ZONE AREA, 1000 km ²	MY ICE AREA, 1000 km ²	C MY ICE (%) ("OKEAN")	C MY ICE (%) (SSM/I)	C MY ICE (%) (ERS-1 SCAT)
1	31.004	26.286	≥ 90	85	50
2	20.723	13.648	80	66	0
3	10.547	7.165	70	68	0
4	34.200	8.862	20	26	7

Fig.1.12. MY Ice concentrations, as retrieved from "Okean" SLR image for December 31, 1995, SSM/I and ERS-1 Scatterometer for January 01-07, 1996

01-07, 1996. SSM/I underestimated MY-ice concentration, as compared with Okean. It is worth to mention that MY-ice boundary, identified from ERS scatterometer by means of simple thresholding does not coincide exactly with that from Okean. In the Laptev and East-Siberian seas the analysis was done for the winter of 1994/1995, and comparisons were done for the following dates: November 9, 19, 30, December 7, 11 (1994), and January 4, 1995. The multiyear sea ice concentrations were revealed from synchronous SSM/I images; coverage of Okean images, and areas with different sea ice parameters, were overlaid on SSM/I patterns. The results of quantitative comparison are presented in Table 1.6.

Table 1.6.

MY sea ice concentrations, retrieved from Okean images and synchronous SSM/I data.

Date	N area	Area, km ²	MY ice area, km ²	SSM/I-MY ice concentration	Okean MY – ice concentration
09.11.94	1	96 383	3 101	3.2	40-50
	2	69 981	2 320	3.3	40-50
	3	12 305	0	0	100
	4	61 786	0	0	40-50
	5	316 220	190 875	60.4	90-100
19.11.94	1	190 650	28 895	15.2	20-30
	2	338 809	314 116	92.7	90-100
30.11.94	1	17 803	7 374	41.4	90-100
	2	15 057	1 673	11.1	40
	3	94 300	75 622	80.2	90-100
	4	367 764	4 469	1.2	0
07.12.94	1	146 203	523	0.4	0
	2	47 095	10 432	22.2	60-70
	3	329 654	269 640	81.8	90-100
11.12.94	1	66 651	40 425	60.7	90-100
	2	84 603	52 399	61.9	90-100
	3	447 058	4 609	1.0	0
04.01.95	1	408 536	4 535	1.1	0
	2	15 507	0	0	45
	3	121 460	46 258	38.1	100

The comparison between RADARSAT-derived multiyear ice boundary and SSM/I-derived MY-ice concentration is shown in Fig.1.13. As it is evident from the figure, the boundary retrieved from RADARSAT coincide with significant gradient in SSM/I. Several comparisons between SSM/I and ERS SAR revealed a qualitative correspondence of the estimates of MY-ice concentration.

A series of RADARSAT ScanSAR images were obtained for the Barents and Kara seas and used for comparison with SSM/I-derived multiyear sea ice concentrations. These images covered such areas as Franz-Joseph Land and Severnaya Zemlya in March of 1997 and 1998. The multiyear ice boundary can be retrieved from these images, because multiyear ice has a higher than first-year ice backscattering. Areas with predominant multiyear ice as well as inclusions of multiyear ice into first-year could also be detected. Its partial concentration was estimated visually. The results of these comparisons are shown in Fig. 1.14-1.15 and in the table 1.7.

Table 1.7.

Multiyear sea ice concentrations retrieved from SSM/I data and synchronous RADARSAT ScanSAR images

Date	Zone number	Zone area	Cmy-SSM/I	Cmy- RADARSAT
05.03.98	1	41 201	76.9	95
05.03.98	2	6 914	39.4	70
05.03.98	3	24 622	32.4	60
05.03.98	4	20 037	46.7	80
05.03.98	5	118 303	13.1	0-10
11.03.98	1	74 339	75	95
11.03.98	2	38 279	33	70
11.03.98	3	3 942	59	70
11.03.98	4	18 686	15	0-10
11.03.98	5	7 524	0	70
11.03.98	6	10 117	17	20
11.03.98	7	55 483	8	0-10
24.03.98	1	81 431	65	95
24.03.98	2	20 347	13	70
24.03.98	3	8 555	28	70
24.03.98	4	28 457	1	0-10
24.03.98	5	46 656	4	0-10
29.03.98	1	29 937	58.4	95
29.03.98	2	1 968	0	0
29.03.98	3	2 958	22.5	60
29.03.98	4	7 198	10.3	30-40
29.03.98	5	2 945	12.8	20
29.03.98	6	3 279	21.5	70
29.03.98	7	2 624	39.4	30
29.03.98	8	3 937	39.7	80
29.03.98	9	2 293	41.3	60
29.03.98	10	1 310	44.0	20
29.03.98	11	1 310	40.3	20

It is necessary to mention that multiyear ice boundaries, retrieved from RADARSAT images coincide with gradients in multiyear sea ice concentrations, retrieved from SSM/I. The absolute values of Cmy, retrieved from both sensors could significantly differ. In areas with compact multiyear ice, where RADARSAT estimates of Cmy are close to 100%, SSM/I give the following values: 77, 75, 65, and 58, which is significantly lower. In areas with predominant multiyear ice SSM/I also underestimates Cmy. In areas with first-year ice both estimates does not differ significantly except of the cases, where false multiyear ice appears.

1.3.5. Comparison with ARGOS-buoys

In September 1993 two ARGOS buoys were deployed on the ice in the Laptev Sea, which after that drifted in general northern direction. After the end of summer melting the ice, where these buoys were deployed, became second-year ice. During winter 1993/94 we obtained monthly MY-ice concentrations and overlaid buoy locations on these patterns. The results are presented in Table 1.8.

Table 1.8.

Multiyear sea ice concentrations, corresponding to ARGOS buoys locations.

Date	Coord. Buoy 1	Coord Buoy 2	MYIC 1	MYIC 2
01.11.93	77.803 N 122.626 E	79.661 N 123.957 E	100%	100%
01.12.93	78.151 N 131.081 E	79.956 N 130.425 E	91%	100%
01.01.94	79.039 N 128.512 E	80.842 N 126.313 E	100%	100%
01.02.94	79.976 N 125.121 E	81.810 N 120.327 E	100%	100%
01.03.94	80.615 N 128.554 E		100%	
01.04.94	80.775 N 133.100 E		100%	

SSM/I- derived MY-ice concentrations in this period did not significantly differed from 100% and varied between 91% and 100%, which correspond well with sea ice conditions, observed during deployment of these buoys.

Fig.1.13. SSM/I-derived pattern of MY sea ice concentration for January 27, 1997 with overlaid MY ice boundary, retrieved from RADARSAT ScanSAR image

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Fig. 1.14. Partial concentrations of multiyear ice, retrieved from SSM/I data for 05.03.1998 (a) и 11.03.98 (c); and synchronous RADARSAT ScanSAR images for 05.03.1998 (b) и 11.03.98 (d).

Fig. 1.15. Partial concentrations of multiyear ice, retrieved from SSM/I data for 24.03.1998 (a) and 29.03.98 (c); and synchronous RADARSAT ScanSAR images for 24.03.1998 (b) и 29.03.98 (d).

1.3.6. Conclusions

1. Visual analysis of SSM/I-derived patterns of the multiyear sea ice concentration revealed their qualitative correspondence with the other data: namely, multiyear ice clustering in the central Arctic Basin. Nevertheless, SSM/I patterns show presence of MY-ice in areas, where it could not be: in the Sea of Okhotsk and the Bering Sea, central and southern parts of the Barents and the Kara seas, and in the Pechora Sea. Therefore we believe that the algorithm for calculation of the multiyear sea ice concentration should include “filtration block”, which can use a priori geographical knowledge on sea ice distribution.

1. Comparisons between the multiyear sea ice boundaries and concentrations, revealed from synchronous SSM/I and Okean images; have been done for the winter of 1994/1995 in the Laptev and the East-Siberian seas. Several comparisons have been conducted for the winter of 1996 and for the April of 1998 in the Barents and Kara seas. These comparisons revealed that SSM/I mainly underestimated MY-ice concentration.
2. Multiyear sea ice concentrations were calculated for each month of the winter of 1993/94 for the points, corresponding to the locations of two ARGOS buoys, deployed on the multiyear ice in the Laptev Sea. The MY-ice concentrations for their locations did not significantly deviate from 100%.
3. MY-ice concentrations, retrieved from SSM/I-data and scatterometer, were compared for the winter of 1995/1996 for the following time intervals: 06-12.11.95, 04-10.12.95, 01-07.01.96, 05-11.02.96, 04-10.03.96. Only qualitative correspondence was found between these estimates.
4. In our opinion the seasonal increase of multiyear sea ice in the Arctic is controversial to WMO definition of multiyear sea ice (it is ice, which survived summer melting) and is caused by inaccuracy of the algorithm. Therefore multiyear ice area in October should correspond approximately to the total sea ice area in September. Changes in multiyear ice area during winter are caused by ice exchange between the Arctic and nearby areas, mainly through the Fram Strait.
5. We believe that the trends of multiyear ice extent could be more representative, than that of concentration, because of the better accuracy of its retrieval.

1) *Recommendations for future activities:*

Conducted studies revealed several open questions in algorithm and software of NORSEX algorithm. Therefore continuation of the studies aimed at improvement of the algorithm and software would be useful, taking into account the importance of SSM/I data for climatic studies. In our opinion the future work should concentrate on the following problems:

1. The repeated detailed analysis of the program software and correction of found errors; use of corrected parameters of SSM/I grid, such as land mask, geographic coordinates and area of grid pixels in the software;
2. Modification of the algorithm using a priori data about surface atmosphere temperature. Compilation and analysis of contemporary data on spatial and temporal variability of sea ice emissivity. Reduction of errors by means of calculating sea ice parameters in delineated zones instead of pixels.
3. Algorithm verification by means of comparison with a)Okean SLR mosaics for the whole Arctic or its parts(possible periods 1983-2000); b)RADARSAT ScanSAR image mosaics for the whole Arctic or its parts (possible periods 1996-2002); c)Ku- and C-band data of satellite scatterometers, using advanced sea ice classification technique.

4. Recalculation of obtained ice parameters in order to production more accurate information about characteristics and dynamics of arctic ice.
5. Determination of trends in sea ice parameters strictly for the Arctic within defined boundaries.

According to WMO definition, multiyear ice extent in the beginning of freeze-up should correspond to total ice extent in late summer. During winter the multiyear ice area decreases due to ice export from the Arctic mainly through the Fram Strait. Therefore SSM/I-derived estimates of sea ice concentration for late summer conditions should be verified. Inaccuracies in its retrieval could be caused by differences in melt pond distribution on sea ice. The following data could be useful in such work:

2) RADARSAT, ERS and AVHRR NOAA images – retrieval of ice edge position and ice concentration

High-resolution (1-2m) visible/infrared images – estimation of melt pond coverage on sea ice.

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2. Processing and integration of other sea ice data

Non-satellite sea ice observational data including the Arctic and Southern Ocean Sea Ice Concentration grids (the so-called “Walsh dataset”) and Russian historical data (the so-called “Zakharov dataset”) from Arctic and Antarctic Research Institute (AARI) in St. Petersburg were acquired and analysed statistically.

Systematic evidence on the geographic location of Arctic sea ice boundary in that area of the Arctic Ocean that adjoins the Atlantic is available from the very beginning of the 20th century. Due to the effort of the Danish Meteorological Institute, first monthly charts of spreading of this ice in the Greenland and Barents Seas were prepared. From that time, information on the location of ice boundary in spring-summer (from April to August) has attained a regular character. From the late 1950s, ice observations in this and other regions were undertaken on a year-round basis. The development of shipping along the coast of Siberia accompanied with observations resulted in ice monitoring extending to Siberian Arctic waters. The observations on the ice edge position in the area of the Arctic Ocean that have started in the mid-1920s were not interrupted in all subsequent years. Aviation from the late 1930s and satellites in the 1970s becomes the main observation means.

2.1. Monthly Arctic Sea Ice Concentration Grids by John Walsh and Bill Chapman (January 1901 - August 1995)

Monthly sea ice concentrations for the Arctic are digitized on a standard 1-degree grid (cylindrical projection) to provide a "relatively uniform set of sea ice extent for all longitudes, as a basis for hemispheric scale studies of observed sea ice fluctuations" (Chapman and Walsh, 1991, Walsh, 1978, Walsh and Johnson, 1978).

These data are a compilation of data from several sources integrated into a single gridded product by John Walsh and Bill Chapman, University of Illinois. The source of data for each grid cell is included within a separate file. These sources of data have changed over the years from observationally derived charts to satellite data. Gaps within observed data are filled with climatology or other numerically derived data.

Much of the pre-1953 data is either climatology or interpolated data and the user is cautioned to use this data with care.

Ice concentration values are representing the number of tenths of ice coverage in each grid area. The grid interval is 1 degree latitude.

The data sources for the ice concentrations vary spatially and temporally. There are seven basic data sources for the ice concentrations:

1. Danish Meteorological Institute
2. Japan Meteorological Agency
3. Naval Oceanographic Office (NAVOCEANO)
4. Kelly ice extent grids (based upon Danish Ice Charts)
5. Walsh and Johnson/Navy-NOAA Joint Ice Center
6. Navy-NOAA Joint Ice Center Climatology
7. Temporal extension of Kelly data (Kelly, 1979)
8. Nimbus-7 SMMR Arctic Sea Ice Concentrations or DMSP SSM/I Sea Ice Concentrations using the NASA Team Algorithm

Sea ice extent data is provided by Kelly, et. al. 1988. The ice extent data is compiled for the months April-August for the majority of the period 1901-1956. In this dataset, utilized the Kelly data were used to create an ice concentration data source for the early period of record. This data is given very low priority in the hierarchy of available data so that if there

are data from any sources (except climatology), the extended Kelly data were replaced with this new source data. The modification of the Kelly data is done in two parts: (1) conversion from ice extent to ice concentrations, and (2) temporal extension of the available data.

(1) A marginal sea ice zone was added to the Kelly ice extent data by computing average ice concentration drop-off rates for the period during which there are satellite observations. These drop-off rates indicate the rate at which ice concentrations decrease as a function of distance from open water and distance from 10/10 ice concentrations. The drop off rates vary with season; the summer melt season drop-off rate is about 0.5 that of the freeze-up season. We apply these drop-off rates to the Kelly ice extent data to create a marginal sea ice zone.

(2) Regional sea ice anomalies have been shown to persist for many months and even seasons (Chapman and Walsh, 1991). The authors attempted to capitalize on this persistence by extending the ice anomaly data from (1) forward and backward in time to fill in the months September-March for each year in the 1901-1956 period. lagged autocorrelations for the period of satellite observations was computed and the autocorrelations were used as weighting functions in the temporally extended data.

During October, 1996, updates were made to the Walsh sea ice database. The database previously contained data through December, 1990. Updates to this dataset are, and will continue to be made using ice concentrations obtained via the SSMI sources using the NASA Team algorithm. Fig.2.1 (a) shows ice extent from SMMR and Walsh datasets. In order to maintain a consistent data source for the last part of the period, all data from October, 1978 through August, 1995 are from the SMMR/ SSMI sources. This means that data from previous versions of this data set were replaced by SMMR and SSM/I data from Oct. 1978 - Dec. 1990. It appears that the SMMR and SSM/I data contains significant differences poleward of the ice edge for most months. Ice concentrations are generally lower in the central Arctic for these data than for other data sources. Ice extents appear to be consistent across datasets, ice areas derived from pre-1978 data may be significantly higher than those calculated from the satellite period. Ice extent, calculated from Walsh data is presented on Fig 2.1 (b).

Fig.2.1. (b) demonstrates that The data from winter contain heterogeneities due to observational deficiencies, especially before the 1950s; however, the summer data are relatively homogenous around the Arctic.

The analysis of the relationships within and among datasets involving large grid point (or station) arrays and time series can be done in many different ways. Simple methods of analysis like compositing and correlation based on selected "reference grid points" or indices are easy to perform, but they involve subjective decisions about the choice of reference time series. Matrix operations offer the possibility of a more objective definition of the structures in such datasets. One such technique applicable to measurements of a single field at many locations is called Principal Component Analysis (PCA) (Priesendorfer, 1988, Bretherton et al., 1992). PCA identifies linear transformations of the dataset that concentrate as much of the variance as possible into small number of variables.

a)

b)

Fig 2.1 Northern Hemisphere Ice extent (million square km) (a - annual from Walsh and SMMR data;. (b - monthly and annual from Walsh data)

Principal Component Analysis of Walsh data set for 1901-1995 revealed the general features of the ice cover's spatial and temporary variability.

The spatial EOFs were computed from anomalies of ice concentration relative to the average over the years 1901-1995. Then, anomaly data for averaged over summer (JAS) and winter (JFM) months ice concentration anomalies were projected onto EOF 1-2. Time series of PC1 for winter and summer seasons are represented on fig.2.2 (a) and 2.3 (a) correspondingly.

Further way of examining the evolution of ice concentration anomalies in both time and space is by considering the projections on pairs of EOFs. We considered the projection of ice concentration data onto the first two EOFs. If there were no temporal coherence in temperature evolution, it would be represented in EOF space by random distribution of points. Fig.2.2 (b) and fig.2.3 (b) demonstrate clearly, this is not the case.

Fig.2.2 (b) represents projection of winter concentration anomaly field onto EOFs 1 - for the period 1901-1995. Fig.2.3 (b) shows projection of the summer concentration anomaly field onto EOFs 1. Each symbol on the figures represents one year.

A statistical projection of ice concentration anomalies fields onto EOFs 1-2 shows three different locations in "EOF space", with shifts from one state to another in the early 1950s and late 1970s. The reason of this can be connected with different input-data sources, e.g. start of satellite observations in 1978/79. The data from winter in particular contain heterogeneities due to observational deficiencies, especially before the 1950s; however, the summer data are relatively homogenous around the Arctic. It became evident that the Walsh data may not be adequate to draw reliable conclusions about the earlier periods, especially in winter.

Fig 2.2 Time series of PC1 for winter (JFM) season (a) and projection of winter concentration anomaly field onto EOFs 1 -for the period 1901-1995 (b).

Fig 2.3 Time series of PC1 for summer (JAS) season (a) and projection of summer concentration anomaly field onto EOFs 1 -for the period 1901-1995 (b).

Annual and summer ice anomaly patterns were calculated. Fig 2.4 represents anomalies of annual ice concentrations, calculated relative to the whole period of observations for the periods a) 1920-1939, b) 1945- 1964, c) 1970-1989. Fig 2.5 shows summer (JAS) ice concentration anomalies for the same periods.

Fig.2.4 Anomalies of annual ice concentrations, calculated for the periods a) 1920-1939, b)1945- 1964, c) 1970-1989.

Fig 2.5 Anomalies of annual ice concentrations, calculated for the periods a) 1920-1939, b)1945- 1964, c) 1970-1989.

The patterns are different in the 1920s-1930s warm period and the subsequent cooler period, particularly in the Greenland and Barents Seas. However, the substantial reduction in Northern Hemisphere ice extent seen in the recent warm decades is absent in the earlier warm period.

2.2. Variations of Arctic sea ice extent in the 20th century from dataset based on available Russian observations

New dataset based on available Russian observations covering about 3/4 of the Arctic Ocean region, missing only the Canadian Arctic Archipelago and the Beaufort and Chukchi marginal seas of the western Arctic was analysed as well as time series of annual mean area, covered by the ice in the North-European basin and ice extent in Siberian Arctic basin in the second half of August (Zakharov, 1976,1978,1981,1987,1996).

To investigate the intrasecular oscillations in ice spreading throughout the 20th century, series of average monthly areas of ice extent were used regardless of ice concentration obtained by different observation instruments and hence having a different degree of reliability. Thus, the duration of these series and their coverage within a year vary from one Arctic Ocean region to another and this fact should be taken into account in the analysis of intrasecular variations. To obtain a generalized picture of sea ice development over as great area of the Arctic Ocean as possible with the maximum observation duration preserved, we have to be restricted to a region of this ocean of 11 347 million km² comprising 77% of its area. This region occupies the entire central part of the ocean that is ice covered the year round and the marginal Norwegian, Barents, Kara, Laptev and East-Siberian Seas and the western Chukchi Sea. It does not include the eastern Chukchi Sea, Beaufort Sea, straits of the Canadian Arctic Archipelago, Hudson Bay, Baffin Bay and Davis Strait.

Sea ice of the North-European Basin (Norwegian, Greenland, Barents and White Seas) includes the East-Greenland ice belt over its entire length from Fram Strait in the north to Cape Farvel at the extreme south of Greenland and Barents Sea ice. The external boundary of North-European ice adjoins open water and unlike other ocean areas, the shores do not prevent its growth in the horizontal direction. The geographic location of these boundaries from April to August of each year is known from the beginning of the 20th century. The only exception is a 6-year period belonging to the time of the World War II.

These data do not obviously give a complete picture of ice cover development as they cover only a 5-month spring-summer period of the year. In order to fill this gap, a reconstruction of the average annual sea ice area over the first six decades of the 20th century was attempted based on April-August data. Beginning from 1959, there is no need in such a reconstruction, as ice observations in the North-European Basin attain a year-round character.

With this aim based on actual year-round data for 1959-1988, an equation to calculate the average annual ice area in the North-European Basin (Y) based on its average in April-August (X) was derived: $Y = 0.89X + 100$ (1). The correlation coefficient between X and Y comprised 0.94 ± 0.01 . Using this equation, the calculation of missing data for the period 1900-1958 was made (Fig.2.6).

Fig.2.6 Annual mean area, covered by the ice in the North-European basin

The main problem of any reconstruction is a question of errors inevitable at the procedures of data series reconstruction. The answer to this question can be obtained by comparing the actual and the calculated values of average annual ice area in this case for the period from 1959 and by calculating the RMS error of reconstruction. This error turned out to be equal to $S = \pm 52$ thousand km^2 at the RMS deviation of the initial actual series $\sigma = \pm 154$ thousand km^2 respectively with the ratio of $S/\sigma=0.34$. Thus, the methodological error of reconstruction comprises one third of the RMS deviation of the actual series. This result indicates quite a high reliability of the reconstruction method used.

Consider the intrasecular changes in ice spreading in the Siberian Arctic waters that include the Kara, Laptev, East-Siberian and western Chukchi Seas (with a total area of 2508 million km^2). These waters are covered much of the year with solid ice from the Asian continent shores to their external boundaries. Regular data characterizing their state along the entire Northern Sea Route, i.e. from Novaya Zemlya to Bering Strait for the middle of the Arctic summer are presented on figure 2.7. This is the longest ice data series for this region. Until the late 1930s, its basis was mainly comprised of en-route shipborne observation data and later of airborne ice reconnaissance and satellite data. With time, the period of observations also extended first over the navigation season and then over the entire year.

Fig.2.7 Ice extent in Siberian Arctic basin in the second half of August, thousand km^2

It is important to note that the contribution of the Siberian portion of the ice cover turns out to be comparatively small. Ice of the East-Greenland and Barents Sea makes the greatest contribution. In the mean annual expression, its fraction comprises 80% of this dispersion. This result is important as it allows a judgement of the most important sea ice area changes over much of the Arctic Ocean (77% of its area) based only on the data for the North-European basin. The fact is that sea ice beyond the northern boundary of the marginal seas is preserved the year-round and does not influence the variability of its area. An assessment of the closeness of relationship between the average annual ice area in this part of the ocean (fig.2.8) and the average ice area for April-August in the North-European Basin obtained from actual data for 1960-1994 confirms the validity of this conclusion.

Fig.2.8 annual mean ice area over much of the Arctic Ocean (77% of its area), thousand km²

The correlation relationship between them expressed by the coefficient of 0.93 ± 0.02 allows us to sufficiently reliably reconstruct the changes of the mean annual sea ice area in the Arctic Ocean from data on the North-European Basin.

Two first decades of the 20th century in the Arctic were distinguished by the conditions that were non-existent during all subsequent years (table 2.1). This was expressed in lower water and air temperatures and a greater level of sea ice extent. The difference in its average values for 1900-1920 and 1921-1939 comprised 308 in May, 377 in June, 441 in July, 273 in August and 309 thousand km² during a year. It is important that the transfer from a higher level of ice extent at the beginning of the century to the next lower level occurred suddenly and was very sharp. It was accompanied with a similar sudden increase of surface air temperature in the Arctic that signified a change of one climatic epoch to another. From this time, the character of the ice cover behavior that entered a regressive phase of its development has also changed. Until 1918, the processes of its expansion with a mean annual rate of +159 thousand km²/decade predominated.

From 1918, the ice area in the North-European basin and in the other regions of the Arctic Ocean began to decrease (Viessé, 1932, 1937, 1940, 1941, 1944). The ice area in August in the Barents, Kara, Laptev, East-Siberian and Chukchi Seas taken together has decreased from 1924 to 1940 by about 1 million km². The East-Greenland ice belt has decreased in size from 1898-1920 to 1921-1938 by 157 thousand km² in April, 186 in July and 95 thousand km² in August. As a result, the average ice boundary was displaced westward up to 75 nautical miles in places and near the shores of Spain, ice ceased to appear. The ice cover of the Barents Sea in May-June that comprised 61% in 1896-1919 decreased to 47% in 1920-1940 with the ice edge in this sea retreating northward by about 120 km. In the

other Arctic Seas the ice area retreat also occurred in the summertime being even greater almost everywhere than in the Barents Sea.

The observation gap during the World War II does not allow us to accurately determine the time when a multiyear minimum in ice spreading was achieved and the new third stage in its development began. The features of this new climatic stage within the Russian Arctic were most pronounced in the Kara Sea. The average annual temperature at the stations of this sea decreased by 2-4° compared to the moment of culmination of warming at the border of the 1930s and 1940s. This decrease beyond the Kara Sea lost its intensity quite quickly especially eastwards being even replaced by small warming at some stations of Chukotka. A significant ice concentration increase from 1946-1995 towards the subsequent two decades occurred in the Kara Sea. This increase also extended to a lesser extent to the Laptev Sea. On the contrary, in the East-Siberian and the Chukchi Seas, the ice concentration decreased from the beginning to the end of this intrasecular stage.

The end of the third and the beginning of the fourth current stage in the development of the ice cover in the Arctic falls on the very end of the 1960s (to be more exact on 1968). It was followed by weak at first and then from the early 1990s quite intense ice area decrease that influenced although to a different extent the entire Arctic Ocean. A sufficiently weak sea ice area decrease throughout the 1970s-1980s has practically become more intense in the entire marginal area of the Arctic Ocean with the beginning of the new decade. Thus, the East Greenland ice belt in August reduced from 539 to 278 thousand km² from 1989 to 1990 and the Barents Sea ice from 222 to 97 thousand km². The ice area decreased from 456 to 79 in the East-Siberian Sea and from 393 to 109 thousand km² in the Laptev Sea. The exception is the Kara Sea where no similar changes were noted. The process of ice situation improvement was not restricted only to the marginal seas extending to the central Arctic and the other ice-infested areas of the Northern Hemisphere. An assessment of linear trends of sea ice area in the Northern Hemisphere (Vinnikov et al., 1999) is further evidence of the direction of changes. According to (Johannessen et al., 1999), the process of the decrease of ice cover dimensions was accompanied with the multiyear ice area decrease in the Arctic Basin. This area decreased by 610 thousand km² from the late 1970s to the end of the century. A comparison of the sea ice draft data in the deep-sea Arctic Ocean at the end of the period of melting indicates a strong ice thickness decrease (by 1.3 m) from 1958-1976 by 1993-1997 (Rothrock et al., 1999).

We refer the boundary between the second and the third stages to 1939, which is not in agreement with ice cover extent variations in Fig. 2.9. In doing this, we were guided first by the fact that the first intra-secular maximum of surface air temperature in the polar area was in 1939 and, second, by the doubts in the high quality of ice state data in the 1940s and in the first half of the 1950s. Each of these stages is characterized by the following linear trend parameters: 1900-1918 $\beta = +169$ thousand km²/decade, 1918-1939 $\beta = -200$ thousand km²/decade, 1939-1968 $\beta = +25$ thousand km²/decade and 1968-1996 $\beta = -121$ thousand km²/decade.

Table 2.2 contains evidence on the contribution of the individual seas to the variability of the ice extent of the Arctic Ocean. As can be seen, the contribution of the Siberian portion to the total dispersion of changes in the total arctic ice area turns out to be comparatively small, while the contribution of the East-Greenland and Barents Sea ice is overwhelming. In the mean annual expression, the fraction of the latter comprises 80 % of dispersion making it possible to judge about the sea ice area change in the Arctic Ocean (to be more exact over 77 % of its area), based on the North-European Basin data. An assessment of the closeness of relation between the mean annual ice areas in this part of the ocean and in the North-European Basin confirms the relevance of this conclusion. The correlation relation between them in the

Fig. 2.9. Mean annual sea ice area in the Arctic Ocean in deviations from an average

Table 2.1
Mean annual ice area in the Arctic Ocean (77 % of the ocean area in its formal boundaries), thousand km²

Years	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
190.	8595	8686	8799	8705	8372	8645	8732	8618	8542	8726
191.	8662	8728	8899	8830	8779	8684	8865	8952	8988	8609
192.	8536	8519	8377	8527	8450	8310	8557	8647	8619	8724
193.	8380	8369	8388	8329	8507	8395	8285	8240	8256	8128
194.	8415	8559	8495	8301	8300	8254	8274	8140	8325	8363
195.	8221	8244	8383	8166	8112	7958	8128	8032	8211*	8153
196.	7996	8094	8373	8582	8337	8374	8573	8530	8593	8745
197.	8374	8323	8336	8230	8164	8237	8184	8235	8363	8428
198.	8526	8419	8465	8227	8053	8158	8291	8394	8432	8364
199.	7925	8029	8066	8100	8100	7926	8395			

Note: * - from here and further, data are actual.

Table 2.2

Contribution of the individual seas to the dispersion of ice area changes in the Arctic Ocean in different months of the year, %

	X	XI	XII	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX
EG	24	43	55	56	52	51	42	35	29	26	11	11
B	43	57	45	44	48	49	58	65	58	39	15	12
K	24	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	18	22	17
L	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	10	24	21
ESC	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	11	26	34
WC	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-3	-4	2	5

Note: EG – East Greenland waters; B – Barents Sea;
 K – Kara Sea; L – Laptev Sea; ES – East-Siberian Sea;
 WC – western Chukchi Sea.

1958-1996 time interval is expressed by a coefficient of 0.95. The intra-secular stages in the development of sea ice in the North-European Basin as can be seen in Fig. 2.10, fully correspond to the stages in Fig. 2.9. This is also confirmed by surface air temperature variations in the latitudinal belt of 85-65° N.

Fig. 2.10. Mean annual sea ice area in the North-European Basin in deviations from an average

The contribution of the individual seas to the total dispersion of the mean annual ice area corresponds to: EG – 36%, B – 44%, K – 8%, L – 5%, ES – 7 % and WC – 0%.

We shall discuss now each of these stages in greater detail using for this different indicators of the intra-secular dynamics of the ice regime.

First intra-secular stage (1900 – 1918). The first two decades of the 20th century in the Arctic were distinguished by the conditions that were absent in all subsequent years. This was expressed in lower water and air temperatures and a higher ice cover extent. As can be clearly seen from Fig. 2.9, these differences in these levels before and after 1918 are quite pronounced. The difference in mean sea ice areas in the Arctic Ocean between the 20-year periods 1900-1919 and 1920-1939 comprised 262 in April, 343 in May, 239 in June, 397 in July, 433 in August and 294 thousand km² during a year. It is important that the transition from a high level of ice extent at the beginning of the century to the next lower level occurred suddenly in a jump. It was accompanied with a similar sudden increase of surface air temperature in the Arctic signifying one climatic epoch being replaced by another. The mean annual surface temperature in the latitudinal belt of 85-65° N from the first 20-year period to the second one has increased by 1°C. The character of behavior of the ice cover that entered the regressive phase of its development has also changed. Table 2.3 presents the linear trend parameters for each intra-secular stage of ice cover development in the 20th century.

Table 2.3

Linear trend parameters β of sea ice area in the Arctic Ocean by the stages of its development (thousand km²/decade)

Period	1900-1918	1918-1938	1946-1968	1968-1996
October				-77
November				-34
December				-76
January				-104
February				-118
March				-150
April	+121	-134	+6	-173
May	+187	-164	+44	-182
June	+182	-116	+124	-143
July	+195	-342	+198	-154
August	+239	-431	+188	-141
September				-107
Mean annual	+169	-200	+122	-122

Data on the ice boundaries of the East-Greenland and Barents Seas in April-August and changes in their location contained in Tables 2.4 and 2.5 shed some additional light on the ice conditions during the first two decades of the 20th century.

Table 2.4

Location of the external boundary of East-Greenland ice in
April-August 1898-1920 and its change by 1921-1938

Latitude	Longitude in 1898-1920					Change in the boundary location*				
	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII
60°	40°30	41° 30	41° 30	41° 20	43° 00	-1° 30	-0° 30	-0° 30	-0° 55	-1°00
61	40 00	40 00	40 45	41 00	43 00	-1 00	-0 30	-1 00	0 00	0 00
62	39 10	39 30	40 20	40 40	42 30	-0 55	0 00	-0 40	0 00	0 00
63	39 00	38 50	39 40	40 00	41 30	-0 45	-0 50	-0 20	0 00	0 00
64	38 00	38 00	38 30	39 00	41 00	-0 30	1 10	0 00	0 00	0 00
65	35 00	35 00	36 00	36 30	40 00	-1 00	-0 30	-1 00	0 00	0 00
66	28 00	27 00	29 30	30 00	34 00	-5 30	-5 00	-3 30	-4 30	-1 00
67	20 00	24 00	23 00	26 00	30 00	-8 00	-7 30	-4 00	-4 00	-0 30
68	14 30	17 00	19 00	20 00	25 00	-6 00	-4 00	-1 30	-3 00	0 00
69	12 00	13 50	16 30	18 00	22 00	-4 00	-2 40	-1 00	-2 00	1 00
70	10 00	11 00	13 30	16 00	20 00	-3 00	-3 00	-1 30	-2 00	1 00
71	8 00	8 20	10 30	14 00	18 00	-3 00	-3 10	-2 30	-2 30	0 00
72	5 00	7 00	8 30	12 30	16 00	-4 30	-2 30	-3 00	-2 30	-2 00
73	3 00	5 00	6 00	1 00	14 00	-5 00	-3 00	-3 30	-4 00	-2 00
74	1 30	3 00	4 00	7 00	12 00	-4 30	-3 50	-3 30	-5 30	-2 00
75	0 30 *	1 30	2 30	4 00	9 00	-4 30	-3 30	-3 30	-6 00	-3 00
76	2 00 *	1 00	1 00 *	2 00	8 00	-3 30	-3 00	-3 00	-6 00	-2 00
77	5 00 *	3 00 *	1 00 *	1 00 *	6 00	-5 00	-3 30	-3 00	-6 00	-2 00
78	7 00 *	5 00 *	2 30 *	3 00 *	3 00	-4 30	-3 30	-2 30	-6 00	-2 00
79	10 00	7 00 *	6 00 *	6 00 *	0 00	-5 00	-2 00	-4 00	-5 00	-3 00
80	Ice	11 00	10 00	11 00	6 00		-1 00	-3 00	-7 00	-4 00

Note: The change in the ice boundary location by 1921-1938 is given in degrees and minutes of longitude;

Sign “ - “ denotes the westward boundary displacement;

*- denotes eastern longitude, in all other cases, the longitude is western.

Table 2.5

Northern boundary of sea ice in the Barents Sea in 1898 – 1920
and change of its boundary by 1921 – 1938

Longi	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII
15° E	75° 55	76° 4 0	77° 00							
20	73 30	73 50	74 40	76° 30	76 °50	-2° 25	-1°	-1° 15		
25	73 25	73 55	74 50	76 20	76 50	-2 30	-2 05	-1 55	-1° 15	-2°
30	73 10	73 50	74 20	76 20	77 20	-2 40	-2 10	-2 40	-1 05	-1 00
35	72 15	73 30	74 00	75 50	77 00	- 3 15	-2 20	-2 50	-1 00	-1 40
40	71 00	72 05	74 00	75 50	77 20	-3 50	-3 00	-1 45	-2 10	-2 00
45			74 15	76 00	77 15			-0 40	-2 15	-2 25
50				76 00	77 50				-2 20	-1 50
55				76 15	77 45				-2 05	-2 05
60				76 25	77 20				-1 35	-2 00

Note: * - change of the ice boundary location is given in degrees and minutes of longitude;
sign “ – “ denoted the northward ice boundary displacement.

Second intra-secular stage (1918-1939). From 1918, a decrease of the sea ice area began in the North-European Basin and in the other regions of the Arctic Ocean, whose intensity in the time interval 1918 – 1938 is reflected in data of Table 2.3. The upper bound of this interval is of a slightly conventional character due to the absence of direct data. As noted above, the first climatic air temperature maximum in the 20th century occurred at the very end of the 1930s. In view of the relationship between the polar atmosphere temperature and sea ice development, this maximum can serve as an indirect indication of the end of the second stage of ice cover development.

V.Yu.Viese presented first evidence about the sea ice area decrease after 1918 in 1926. With time, it was supplemented and made more detailed both in the studies of Viese (Viese, 1932, 1937, 1940, 1941 and 1944) and of other scientists (Zubov, 1938, 1944, 1948; Karelin, 1941). The most important of the results obtained are very briefly described below.

The tendency towards the ice cover extent decrease in most areas of the sub-Atlantic Arctic was outlined at the very end of the second decade of the 20th century. However, it was most pronounced in the 1930s. The ice area in August in the Barents, Kara, Laptev, East-Siberian and Chukchi Seas together has decreased from 1924 to 1940 approximately by 1 million km². The size of the East-Greenland ice belt has decreased from 1898-1920 to 1921-1938 by 157 in April, 186 in July and 95 thousand km² in August. As a result, the average ice boundary moved westward up to 75 nautical miles in places, while near the shores of Iceland, ice that prevented normal shipping and fishery in waters of this island at the beginning of the century, does not anymore appear.

The ice cover extent of the Barents Sea in May-June that comprised 61 % in 1896-1919, decreased to 47 % by 1920-1940, whereas the ice edge retreated northward by about 120 km. In the other Arctic Seas, the ice area in the summertime also decreased, and according to Viese even on a greater scale almost everywhere compared to the Barents Sea.

For example, in the southwestern Kara Sea beginning from 1929, ice in September was not encountered at all although in 1869-1928, the probability of observing it here comprised 30 %. The dates of the freeze up and ice breakup in the coastal sea areas have sharply decreased at this. Thus, while until 1920, the final freeze up of Yugorsky Shar Strait occurred around November 24, on average, in 1920-1937, this freeze up occurred later, on January 25.

The decrease of the ice area was accompanied with the ice thickness decrease. Unfortunately, it is impossible to reliably assess this decrease due to the absence of accurate data. An estimate given in literature for the central Arctic cannot be considered correct. It was obtained by comparing the maximum ice thickness measured during the drift of the “Fram” in 1893-1896 (more than 3 m) and “Sedov” in 1937-1940 (2.2 m.). Not doubting the fact itself of ice thinning in the process of climate warming, one should not however, attribute the difference in thickness entirely to climate changes. This difference could occur due to the fact that the “Sedov” drifted surrounded by younger ice. Suffice it to remind that the “Sedov” began to drift in the Laptev Sea at latitude $75^{\circ} 21' N$, $132^{\circ} 15' E$, whereas the “Fram” – at a point of $78^{\circ} 50' N$, $133^{\circ} 30' E$.

A comparative analysis of the drift of the “Fram” and “Sedov” also served as a basis to make a conclusion about the increased drift velocity in the Arctic Basin during the epoch of climate warming. “The drift of “Sedov”, wrote Viese (Viese, 1940), started much more to the south than the “Fram” drift while it occurred much more northward and ended much more southward. The “Fram” drift lasted for 1055 days, and the “Sedov” drift – only for 812 days”. In addition, the drifts of the “Sedov”, “North Pole” stations and numerous buoys in the 1930s in the Polar basin were noticeably more rapid compared to the drift of the “Zhanetta” and “Fram” in the last quarter of the 19th century and of “Sv. Anna” at the beginning of the 20th century.

The improvement of ice conditions in the 1920-1930s created favorable conditions for shipping. Table 2.6 presents the dates of the start, end and duration of navigation to Spitsbergen according to (Hesselberg, 1940) that confirm the development of events towards the improved conditions of polar shipping to the shores of this archipelago. The improvement has also occurred at the extreme east of the North-European Basin in the Novaya Zemlya area. As early as the beginning of the 20th century, the navigation situation at the approaches to the straits of this archipelago (Yugorsky Shar, Kara Gate and Matochkin Shar), likewise near the northern tip of Novaya Zemlya – Cape Zhelaniya frequently excluded a passage to the Kara Sea due to ice conditions. In summer of 1901, the icebreaker “Yermak” was not able not only to approach this cape, but also to come up without hindrance to the northern island of this archipelago from the side of the Barents Sea. Moreover, this powerful icebreaker was beset in ice for a whole month. In 1938, the same icebreaker “Yermak” penetrated the Arctic Basin in the sector of the New Siberian Islands to $83^{\circ}05' N$, holding thus a world record of the northern latitude for a freely navigating vessel.

Table 2.6

Dates of the start, end and duration of navigation to Spitsbergen,
according to [Hesselberg, 1940]

Year	Day, month		Duration, days	Year	Day, month		Duration, days
	Start	End			Start	End	
1907	19.06	1.10	106	1924	22.04	15.10	176
1908	13.06	1.10	111	1925	21.05	27.10	159*
1909	30.06	1.10	94	1926	24.05	17.11	177
1910	19.06	1.10	105	1927	13.06	28.10	137
1911	29.06	5.10	99	1928	2.06	20.10	141
1912	1.07	6.10	98	1929	8.07 28.08	13.08 9.10	80
1913	1.07	6.10	93	1930	20.05	21.10	155
1914	1.07	7.10	99	1931	23.05	18.10	149
1915	13.08	1.10	50	1932	18.05	25.10	161
1916	1.07	13.10	105	1933	4.05	29.10	179
1917	21.07	2.10	74	1934	2.05	31.10	183
1918	1.06	1.10	123	1935	16.05	1.11	170*
1919	10.06	1.10	114	1936	17.05	29.10	166
1920	24.05	11.10	141	1937	3.05	6.11	188*
1921	1.05	11.10	164	1938	1.05	2.11	186
1922	27.05	7.10	134	1939	29.04	17.11	203
1923	9.05	9.10	154				

N.N. Zubov (Zubov, 1938) pointed out that in 1930, there was not a single occasion when it was impossible to round Novaya Zemlya from the north onboard a ship unsuitable for ice navigation. In summer of 1932 for the first time in the history of shipping, a small expedition ship “Nikolay Knipovich” rounded the Franz-Josef Land from the north whereas the icebreaking vessel “Sibiryakov” – Severnaya Zemlya. In general, the 1930s in the Arctic turned out to be extremely favorable for transit along the Northern Sea Route, which at that time has become a normally operating transport waterway. In summer of 1935, 1937, 1939, 1940, 1941, 1943 and 1945, one could sail without hindrance along the entire coast of Siberia from Novaya Zemlya to Bering Strait.

Third intra-secular stage (1939 – 1968). An assessment of the linear trend parameters at this stage of the Arctic ice development has become possible only from 1946 due to a gap in the observations (Table 2.3). By this time, a system of ice observations in the Russian Arctic has been already formed with observations themselves attaining a regular character. Due to this, there was an opportunity to investigate their temporal variations, which was used

in (Zakharov, 1976). It was shown that the new intra-secular stage of Arctic ice development was manifested in the decreased surface air temperature, earlier ice formation and landfast ice establishment in autumn, its later breakup in spring at the majority of Arctic coastal points and in the open sea, increased ice thickness and slower drift, decreased ice exchange between the marginal seas and the Arctic Basin and in the southward displacement of the old ice boundary including multiyear ice.

Within the Russian Arctic, the features of this new climatic stage were most pronounced in the Kara Sea. The mean annual temperature at the stations of this sea decreased by 2-4° C compared to the moment of warming culmination at the boundary of the 1930s and 1940s. This decrease beyond the Kara Sea limits attenuates quite rapidly, especially eastward being even replaced at some stations on Chukotka by an insignificant warming.

Cooling resulted in some important changes in the state of the ice cover in the Arctic Ocean and its seas. The dates of the onset of stable ice formation, for example, at Cape Cheluskin in 1959-1970 were by 25-30 days earlier than in 1941-1945. On Uyedineniya Island, this change comprised 25 days and on Preobrazheniya Island, it was 20 days. A detailed picture of changes in the ice formation in Siberian Arctic waters is presented in Fig. 2.11. The earlier onset of ice formation and the decreased air temperatures in autumn and winter have influenced the ice thickness (Table 2.7). The average ice thickness in the vicinity of polar stations in the Kara Sea increased by about 30 cm in the late 1960s compared to the moment of warming culmination. In the Laptev Sea, this increase was only 7 cm while in the East-Siberian Sea, the ice thickness has not practically changed. Thus, even in the area of the largest cooling, which is the Kara Sea, the ice thickness increase was comparatively small.

Fig. 2.11. Change in average dates of the onset of ice formation near the coast of Siberia from 1946 –1955 to 1956 – 1965 , days (negative values on the map denote earlier ice formation)

Table 2.7

Ice thickness change in the vicinity of polar stations at the coast and on the islands of the Arctic Seas during the third intra-secular stage, cm

Sea, station	Δh_1	Δh_2	Δh_3	Δh_4	Δh_5
Kara Sea, Zhelaniya	20	5	26	63	57
Yugorsky Shar	17	7	23	29	22
Bely Island	12	10	30	4	17
Marre-Salya	9	10	9	16	21
Dikson Island	5	16	26	30	24
Cheluskin	15	23	27	27	34
Andrey Island	18	6	2	18	24
Russky Island	15	5	22	7	21
Uyedineniya Island	6	7	27	28	41
Laptev Sea, Preobrazheniya	-24	1	10	3	-7
Tiksi	-8	1	-8	-2	-2
Kigilyakh	12	17	22	-6	1
Sannikov	6	10	10	-10	4
Kotel'ny Island	4	6	8	2	-8
Shalaurov	1	21	23	1	-6
East-Siberian Sea, Chetyrekhtolbovoy	-4	5	-15	-2	-1
Billings	-5	-5	-6	-10	-12
Vrangel Island	12	12	-2	10	4
Chukchi Sea, Vankarem	8	14	-12	14	13
Bering Sea, Provideniya	-12	-19	-14	-11	-27

Note: Δh_1 , Δh_2 , Δh_3 , Δh_4 , Δh_5 – deviation of the average ice thickness during the 5-year periods 1946-1950, 1951-1955, 1956-1960, 1961-1965 and 1966-1970 from the average in 1941-1945. The sign “-” means the ice thickness decrease.

The attenuated intensity of atmospheric circulation in the central Arctic resulted in the slower ice drift in the Arctic Basin. In the 1950s and 1960s, this drift occurred with the velocities that were typical of the period of cooling at the beginning of the century, i.e. of the first intra-secular stage. The average drift speed by the general direction in 1955-1970 was 1.7 km/day. Simultaneously, there was deterioration of ice conditions in the Greenland Sea and in Icelandic waters. Thus, in the 1940s, ice in waters of Iceland appeared in March in 5 cases, in the 1950s - in 7 and during the subsequent 12 years – annually.

The increased ice cover extent in most marginal seas is a phenomenon typical of the third intra-secular development stage. This is indicated in data of Tables 2.8 and 2.9 and in Fig. 2.12. This increase began in the Kara and Laptev Seas (early 1940s), then in the Barents

Sea (mid-1950s) and finally in the Greenland and Beaufort Seas and in Davis Strait (mid-1960s). The exception is the Chukchi Sea and the eastern East-Siberian Sea where the ice quantity decreased. A fuller understanding of the spatial non-uniformity features in the changes of ice conditions is given in Fig. 2.13. As can be seen, there was a noticeable ice concentration increase on the western segment of the Northern Sea Route, especially in the Kara Sea from 1946-1955 to the subsequent two decades. This increase, however, less intense also spread to the Laptev Sea. In the East-Siberian and Chukchi Seas, the ice conditions, on the contrary, improved leading to a decreased ice concentration from the beginning to the end of this intra-secular stage. This “mirror” reflection in the ice cover extent variations between the western and eastern segments of the Northern Sea Route has been known as an ice opposition from the time of V.Yu. Viese.

Table 2.8

Mean annual ice area in the North-European Basin, thousand km²

Year	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Averag
190.	1430	1510	1610	1528	1234	1474	1551	1450	1383	1545	1472
191.	1489	1547	1698	1637	1592	1508	1668	1744	1775	1442	1610
192.	1377	1363	1238	1370	1216	1114	1345	1447	1351	1511	1333
193.	1157	1169	1337	1115	1395	1318	1126	1181	1235	1064	1210
194.	1363	1487	1366	1297	1183	1300	1127	1068	1211	1186	1259
195.	1142	1194	1339	1159	1031	882	968	890	1028	1107	1074
196.	937	1037	1163	1350	1183	1266	1357	1358	1566	1527	1274
197.	1181	1229	1149	1118	1020	1112	1087	1162	1228	1262	1155
198.	1351	1238	1311	1071	877	993	1101	1222	1274	1248	1169
199.	963	959	957	1041	1037	974	1192				

Note: ■ - data are reconstructed by the mean annual surface air temperature.

In addition to the increased quantity of ice to the north of the coast of Siberia, there was a change in its age composition. Fig. 2.14 shows, in particular, the change in the content of multiyear ice that influenced the conditions of shipping.

Fourth intra-secular stage (1968-1999). The end of the third and the beginning of the fourth concluding stage in the ice cover development in the Arctic fell on the very end of the 1960s (to be completely exact, on 1968). It was first followed by a weak and then from the early 1990s, quite an intense decrease in the ice area influencing although to a different extent, the entire Arctic Ocean. The upper bound of the stage cannot be exactly defined to-date due to unclear future development of the ice cover. That is why, it was conventionally referred to the very end of the centennial.

Fig. 2.12 Deviation of ice extent in the Arctic Seas (a) and of air temperature at polar stations (b) in 1946-1970 from their levels in 1941-1945

Fig.2.13. Ice concentration change along the Siberian coast from the 1946-1955 decade to 1966-1974, tenths

Fig.2.14. Change of concentration of old (second-year and multiyear) ice from the 1946-1955 decade to 1956-1965, tenths (positive values denote the increase of concentration towards 1956-1965)

Table 2.9
Mean annual ice area in Siberian Arctic waters, thousand km²

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
192.					2298	2260	2276	2264	2332	2277
193.	2277	2264	2115	2277	2175	2141	2223	2123	2085	2128
194.	2117	2136	2194	2068	2181	2018	2210	2137	2178	2241
195.	2143	2114	2108	2069	2145	2139	2224	2206	2247	2110
196.	2123	2121	2274	2295	2218	2171	2280	2236	2091	2282
197.	2256	2158	2252	2177	2208	2189	2161	2138	2198	2229
198.	2240	2245	2218	2220	2240	2229	2253	2236	2222	2180
199.	2026	2134	2173	2123	2181	2016	2287	2091	2263	2146

Data of Table 2.3 indicate that the linear trends at this stage are characterized the year-round by the decreased level of ice cover extent by the end of the century. However, the intensity of this decrease experiences strong seasonal changes with a minimum in November (-34 thousand km²/decade) and a maximum in May (-182 thousand km²/decade). On average for a year, it is equal to - 122 thousand km²/ decade.

Quite a small decrease of sea ice area throughout the 1970-1980s has suddenly sharply intensified with transition to a new decade practically in the entire marginal part of the Arctic Ocean. Thus, the East-Greenland ice belt in August decreased during 1989 to 1990 from 539 to 278 thousand km², and the Barents Sea ice from 222 to 97 thousand km². In the East-Siberian Sea, the ice area decreased from 456 to 79 and in the Laptev Sea from 393 to 109 thousand km². The exception is the Kara Sea, where no changes were observed with the change of years. In the total expression, the ice area in August decreased during 1989 to 1990 by more than 1 million km². This was sufficient to achieve a secular minimum in spreading of Arctic ice in the 20th century.

The process of improving ice conditions was not restricted to only the marginal seas spreading also to the Central Arctic and the other ice-covered regions of the Northern Hemisphere. An assessment of the linear trends of sea ice area in the Northern Hemisphere made in (Vinnikov et al, 1999) does not leave any doubts relative to the direction of changes. According to (O.M. Johannessen et al, 1999), the process of the decrease in the ice cover size was accompanied with the decrease in the multiyear ice area in the Arctic Basin. This area was reduced by 610 thousand km² from the late 1970s to the end of the century. A comparison of the sea ice draft in deepwater area of the Arctic Ocean at the end of the period of melting indicates a strong decrease in the distributed ice thickness (by 1.3 m) from 1958-1976 to 1993-1997 (Rothrock et al, 1999).

It is natural that the aforementioned changes had a positive influence on the conditions of arctic navigation not only along the Northern Sea Route, but also in the Central Arctic. While prior to the early 1990s, the icebreakers reached the North Pole in free navigation only twice, during the last decade of the 20th century, they made 26 voyages that ended in reaching the Geographical Pole. According to data (Frolov, 1998), in the summertime in 1990-1998 in six cases (1991, 1992, 1993, 1994, 1996 and 1998) of nine, navigation of icebreakers from the Atlantic to the Pacific Ocean was possible across the North Pole. In the 1970s, there were 4 such cases and in the 1980s, only 3. The year 1996 can serve as an example when the

favorable ice conditions in the central Arctic allowed the icebreaker “Yamal” to pass as early as the second half of July in free navigation not only across the Geographical Pole, but also across the Relative Inaccessibility Pole. This success was to a great extent provided by a wide (hundreds of kilometers) belt of ice with a decreased concentration (8 tenths by an estimate of this author), formed by the time of sailing from Spitsbergen across the Pole and further to Vrangal Island.

A dramatic improvement of ice conditions in the Arctic at the end of the 20th century occurred along with a surface air temperature increase and the mass and temperature increase of Atlantic waters in the Arctic Basin (see for a review Alekseyev et al., 1997, 1998). Observations of numerous expeditions in the Arctic Basin throughout the 1990s have revealed that this increase was not of a short-term and of a random character. It was recorded over much of the Arctic Basin being especially pronounced at meridians of the Laptev Sea. Simultaneously with the temperature elevation, there was an increase of the Atlantic water mass and the heat content with the upper boundary rising more to the surface. The salinity of the upper layer north of Severnaya Zemlya islands increased resulting in a decrease of the vertical salinity gradient in the boundary layer between the surface and Atlantic waters, which contributes to the heat input from Atlantic waters to the surface. If further development of events in this direction continues over a significant area of the Arctic Basin, a real threat to the ice cover existence will appear.

2.3. Intercomparison of datasets

Spectral, wavelet and autocorrelation analysis were conducted for both above-mentioned data sets in order to determine patterns of oscillatory behaviour in the ice cover and to estimate the response time of the ice cover to anomalous conditions as well as to determine patterns of oscillatory behaviour in the ice cover.

Fig 2.15 represents autocorrelation functions for annual Northern Hemisphere ice extent from Walsh data and annual mean ice area over much of the Arctic Ocean from Russian data

Fig.2.15 Autocorrelation functions

Considering autocorrelation function on the period 15 years we can find only positive values with amplitude decrease with time. Results of calculations for all data sets with the lag of 30 are presented on fig.2.16. From this figure one can estimate internal structure of the processes. Correlation functions have smooth variation, indicating predominance of short frequencies, or, in other words, oscillations with long period. Existence of negative values in all correlation functions and its periodical character allow to make a conclusion concerning periodical character of the functions themselves with the period approximately 20 years. In spite of all above mention differences between data sets and discrepancies found in Walsh data at least in winter season, autocorrelation functions have similar structure and reflect the main features of the process.

Fig 2.16 Autocorrelation functions

Fig 2.17 shows histogram values for annual Northern Hemisphere ice extent from Walsh data and annual mean ice area over much of the Arctic Ocean from Russian data. From both histograms we can see good coincidence with normal distribution.

Fig.2.17. Histograms for annual Northern Hemisphere ice extent from Walsh data and annual mean ice area over much of the Arctic Ocean from Russian data

Fig.2.18 Periodogram values

From periodogram values (Fig. 2.18) it is seen, that there are 18-y and 64-y cycles in all time series. Spectral density has a maximum on point 18.

Additionally, for data from both sources wavelet analysis was implemented.

Fig 2.19 represents the wavelet power spectrum for annual mean area, covered by the ice in the North-European basin from Russian data (a) and for annual mean ice area over much of the Arctic Ocean (77% of its area). Fig. 2.20 shows time evolution (a) and the wavelet power spectrum (b) for ice extent in Siberian Arctic basin in the second half of August.

Fig.2.19 The wavelet power spectrum for annual mean area, covered by the ice in the North-European basin (a) and for annual mean ice area over much of the Arctic Ocean

Fig 2.20 Time evolution (a) and the wavelet power spectrum (b) for ice extent in Siberian Arctic basin in the second half of August.

Wavelet analysis has a number of advantages over Fourier analysis that are particularly attractive. Unlike the Fourier transform, which generates record-averages values

of amplitude and phase for each frequency component or harmonic, the wavelet transform yields a localised, “instantaneous” estimate for the amplitude and phase of each spectral component in the data set. (William J.Emery and Richard E.Thomson “Data analysis methods in physical oceanography”)

The wavelet analysis reveal oscillations of 30-y and 60-y cycle in Russian data for annual mean area, covered by the ice in the North-European basin and for annual mean ice area over much of the Arctic Ocean during the whole period of observations. Short-period oscillations (4-y) were found from 20s to the middle of 70s. Starting from the early century 10-20-y oscillations were found, but since the end of 70s their amplitude became less intensive. Predominance of long-period oscillations during last decades is also evident.

All above mention peculiarities are the most pronounced for the data for North European basin. As for Siberian Arctic data we also can find 30-y oscillations (but less intensive), 60-y variations are absent here, that can be caused by shorter period of observations. Strongest are 10-20-y oscillations up to the end of 70s.

Fig 2.21 represents the wavelet power spectrum for annual ice extent from Walsh data

Fig 2.21 Power spectrum for annual ice extent from Walsh data

However, the wavelet analysis in annual Walsh data does not reveal any oscillation at all before early 50s, that support the conclusion about observational deficiencies before 1953.

2.4. Arctic ice thickness variability, 1970-1991

Long elastic-gravity waves (200 to 500 m) in the sea ice cover arise from ocean swell waves and can propagate for hundreds to thousands of kilometres with weak dampening. The measured ice surface parameters (wavelength, wave period and direction) are then related to thickness through a wave energy dispersion relation. The ice thicknesses determined from different propagation directions are averaged to provide a basin-wide mean thickness. The seasonal cycle has a 40-cm range, while a linear trend of anomalies from 1971-90 indicates a decrease of only ~10 cm (less than 4%) during the period. This is much less than the 1950s/1970s to 1990s sonar data analyses (Serreze et al,2000, Wadhams,1997), though comparable with other observational and modelling analyses (Holloway,2001, Hilmer and Lemke, 2000). In any case, the large multi-decadal variability inherent in the sea ice–climate system renders interpretation of ice thickness trends from the available observational data an open question.

The results of investigating physical-mechanical processes in sea ice allowed identification of the strain and stress components in the ice floes that occur due to large-scale processes. This primarily refers to relaxation and quasi-harmonic self-oscillations occurring in the ice cover at ice pressures. Shears, ridging, displacement and cutting of ice floes by icebergs are accompanied by a complex of stress and strain parameters. Records of these parameters in the corresponding observation system allow approaching the problem of continuous tracing sea ice dynamics, operational forecasting of ice pressure and ridging and determination of the place and time of occurrence of risk situations. At present, a model of such a system has been created and it is planned to use it in the areas of the Arctic shelf and the central Arctic basin.

The method developed uses satellite transmission of ice pressure and ridging data. For a generalised assessment of the processes of ice pressure and deformation, it is necessary to record the following minimum list of parameters:

- two horizontal mutually orthogonal stress components in ice;
- amplitudes of two horizontal and one vertical component of ice cover oscillations;
- relative phases of oscillations at three points based on the quarter wavelength;
- ratio of the horizontal/vertical component amplitudes;
- accompanying meteorological parameters at the observation point: atmospheric pressure, wind direction and speed, air temperature;
- observation time.

Regular measurements and a set of statistics of the enumerated parameters at the main synoptic times (6 times a day) and their transmission via a satellite telemetric communication channel to the data collection points, for example, the AARI will allow efficient use of this information for the purpose of operational forecasting of ice conditions in the areas of deployed instruments (Fig. 2.22).

As a base satellite telemetric communication channel, the automated ice station (AIS) is used, which operates at the AARI since 1988 for measuring meteorological parameters and the drift in the central Arctic areas. The AIS is designed for a long-term self-contained operation and is equipped with a Doppler system for geographical coordinate averaging and data transfer via satellites of the “Okean-0” series.

For linking the primary sensors of stress and wave processes in the ice with the AIS, special instrumentation was developed. It includes 5 measurement sensors and a measurement-coding block (Fig. 2.23).

Three sensors present seismometers of the magnetic-electric system with a mutual-orthogonal orientation designed for measuring the amplitudes of longitudinal and cross ice oscillations.

For identifying the operating frequency range, band filters are used. The ice oscillation amplitude is assessed at the logarithmic scale overlapping the dynamic range of 60dB.

Stresses in the ice are measured by the sensors with in-built converters of elastic ice deformation to the output signal frequency. The measurement-coding block converts the output signal to a digital binary 10-digit code. A complete data volume transmitted by AIS in one communication session comprises 256 bits including service parameters: AIS number, number of the synoptic observation time, Doppler displacement parameter of the transmitter frequency for determining geographical coordinates. It is planned in the next AIS modification to increase the transmitted information volume in one communication session up to 2048 bits).

Observations are made in continuous mode, but recording in the buffer memory is performed only at synoptic times with a 10-minute parameter averaging similar to averaging requirements for meteorological data.

Data transmission to satellite is made on programming request twice a day on average at the time of satellite passing above the observation area. Satellite is polar-orbited with the 90-minute revolution period. Stable receiving of sub-satellite pass comprises 4000 km. Data are received from satellite at the receiving points. The receiving instrumentation is linked with the IBM PC type that makes complete data processing and listing of the results in the form of a standard table. Data are regularly transmitted to synoptic bureau to be used for ice condition, ice drift and weather forecasting.

The methodology for forecasting ice conditions from the observations of the ice stress state is based on the sufficiently reliable correlation relations established due to multiyear full-scale studies.

Fig.2.20. Diagram of satellite sea ice pressure and ridging data transmission

Fig.2.23 Instrument array on sea ice. 1 – automated ice station; 2 – electronic block; 3 – release; 4 – seismometer; 5 – ice strength sensor.

2.5. Interannual changes in the average sea ice thickness in the Arctic during 1972-1992 period

In 1972-1992, the Arctic and Antarctic Research Institute carried out regular observations of sea ice cover oscillations in the Arctic Basin at the North Pole drifting stations (with most intense polygon observations in 1983-1989). Polygon measurements were made using 6 tiltmeter sensors in a T-shaped array. The spacing between the sensors was 100 m. Using a large number of sensors and the known spectral methods (Konyaev, 1981) it is possible not only to determine the frequency and the length of the oscillation wave, but also the direction of its origin with sufficient accuracy. Since wave oscillation characteristics result from the elastic-gravity wave travelling along different routes in the ice-upper ocean layer system, the calculated effective ice thickness (h) is due to natural averaging in the process of this wave motion in different ice by horizontal including ice ridges, fractures and polynyas. That is why h is convenient to use for studying the climatic variability of sea ice thickness. The elastic-gravity waves in the ice and the upper ocean layer are generated by the swell waves propagating from the ice-free ocean, strong wind zones and ridging processes. The generated free elastic-gravity waves can travel over large distances (hundreds of kilometers) with weak damping. In respect of the horizontal dimensions, fractures and polynyas are less or comparable with the length of the free elastic-gravity waves (200-500 m) propagating in ice and in the upper ocean layer not hindering propagation of the latter. By averaging h values for all directions in April-May of each year, we obtain a curve of multiyear average ice thickness change for the entire Arctic Basin that is especially important for climatic estimates.

Monthly area-averaged thickness as derived from surface-based measurements made from Russian *North Pole* drifting stations and interannual variability and trends for April and August are presented on fig. 2.24 (a) and (b) correspondingly

The 1972-1992 linear trend indicates an approximately 10 cm decrease of the average ice thickness in the entire Arctic Basin, which comprises 3-4% of the average ice thickness

(~3 m). The average ice thickness variations during the indicated period comprised 20 cm, i.e. 7% of average thickness or 40% of seasonal ice thickness variations comprising 50 cm (Nagurny,1997, Nagurny et al, 1994). The largest ice thickness decrease occurred in 1987-1990.

A

$$\text{April: } y = -0.0038x + 2.9713$$

$$\text{August: } y = -0.0045x + 2.6341$$

B

Fig 2.24 Monthly area-averaged thickness(a) and Interannual variability and trends for April and August

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3. Analysis of hemispheric sea ice trends and variability from satellite data

MonArc Task 3 analysed the dataset produced in Task 1 in order to quantify variability and trends in the arctic ice cover as a whole. The statistical analysis of the 20-year satellite-derived dataset (1978-1998) in the earlier reporting periods has been updated and analysed from 1998 to 2001 in ModArc Task 2.

3.1. Annual changes in the total ice cover

The trend in total ice area is shown on Fig.3.1. The decrease is about 3.13% per decade, generally consistent with previous analysis to 1995 (Bjorgo E, Johannessen O.M., Miles M.,1997) , 1997 (Cavelieri D. J., Gloersen, P., Parkinson C. E., Zwally H. J., Comiso J.,1997) and 1999 (Johannessen O.M., Miles M.W., Shalina E.V.,1999).

Fig.3.1. Annual sea ice area of the Arctic ice pack, 1978-2000, derived from SMMR and SSM/I data.

Fig.3.2. Annual sea ice extent of the Arctic ice pack, 1978-2000, derived from SMMR and SSM/I data.

The trend in the ice area is shown in Fig.3.2. The decrease is about 2.3% per decade, generally consistent with previous analysis to 1995 (Bjorgo E, Johannessen O.M., Miles M.,1997) , 1997 (Cavelieri D. J., Gloersen, P., Parkinson C. E., Zwally H. J., Comiso J.,1997) and 1999.

The latter analysis shows that the total ice cover has continued to decrease at a comparable rate (~3% per decade) as found earlier in the project.

3.2. Changes in the multi-year ice cover

In the analysis of multi-year ice transformations we used monthly averages instead of daily averages to minimize weather effects, which can significantly change the results from one day to another. The use of monthly averages also reduces high frequency noise, facilitating the analysis of the interannual variability and trends of multi-year ice during the continuous period of satellite observations. The study has been done only for winter months (November – March) when the signatures are relatively stable because melt ponding effects are at minimum.

Fig.3.3. Variability of microwave-derived multi-year ice area in winter 1978-2000. The results are obtained for five winter months (November-March); each winter is indicated by two years. The negative trend is about 16% for the whole period.

Our results showing (Fig.3.3) the 16% (comparing to 14% up to 1999) reduction in multi-year ice area in the past two decades are corroborated by other analyses. As was reported in (Smith, 1998) the analysis of SMMR and SSM/I data found an 8% increase (5.3 days) in the length of sea ice melt season in the Arctic from 1978 to 1996. Besides, independent data from oceanographic field observations have revealed changes in upper ocean water masses (McPhee M.G. et al, 1998) between 1975 and 1997 that are assumed to stem from a substantial melting of perennial multi-year ice.

However, the satellite dataset remains inadequate to resolve multi-decadal variability – it is conceivable that should atmospheric circulation anomalies seen in, e.g., North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) / Arctic Oscillation (AO) indices during the most recent decades return to “normal”, the ice cover could rebound accordingly. However, as noted in the MonArc Task 6 and ModArc Task 3 results, we suggest strongly that the recent decreases reflect anthropogenic forcing and therefore will most probably continue.

3.3. Spatial analysis

The detailed spatial patterns of the mean values and trends were identified via pixel-by-pixel analysis. Mean fields for the whole period of satellite observations (Fig.3.4) as well as linear trends (Fig.3.5) were calculated using total ice and multi-year ice concentrations for different seasons.

a) SEPTEMBER

b) MARCH

Mean ice concentration

linear trend

Fig.3.4 Spatial distribution of mean total ice concentrations and linear trends for September (a) and March (b)

***Multi-year ICE
NOVEMBER***

Fig.3.5 Spatial distribution of mean multi-year ice concentrations and linear trends for November

From analysis of the linear trends one could make a conclusion, that in September the main changes in ice cover occurred in Barents Sea and Canadian sector of the Arctic. Possibly, it was caused by a sharp increase since 1989 in the frequency of low pressure system over central Arctic (Maslanik J. et al,1996).

Statistical and visual analyses of the resulting database have been made, revealing among other things, the specific areas of largest negative linear trend in the total ice and of the perennial MY ice from 1978-2001. It was found that these areas – namely the Siberian marginal seas (e.g., Kara, Laptev and East Siberian) and the Barents Sea – were in close correspondence for both the total ice concentration in late summer and the MY ice in winter. The results corroborate the total ice distribution maps in Parkinson *et al.*, [1999] and the Siberian ice reductions in the 1990s noted by Maslanik *et al.* [1996].

3.4 Analysis of monthly variability

Analysis of satellite-derived sea ice concentration indicates that variability on time scales of days to weeks and longer is usually organised into geographical patterns that are associated with synoptic-scale pressure systems and large-scale structures of atmospheric circulation variability. In the context of climate change detection, this high-frequency variability is considered to be essentially background noise, such that climate change analyses based on sea ice data tend to be based on monthly averages. The predominant variability in the Arctic sea ice time series is seasonal, with typical late winter (March) maximum ice extent $\sim 15 \cdot 10^6 \text{ km}^2$, compared to a late summer (September) minimum $\sim 5 \cdot 10^6 \text{ km}^2$.

We considered monthly difference between ice extent and area (fig.3.6). This difference characterizes relation between ice and open water concentrations. The seasonal cycle was removed statistically, leaving a series of anomalies from which remaining irregular variability and trends were determined. Irregular component was found through the subtraction the trend-cyclical component from the series with seasonal correction. As it is seen from Fig.3.6., maximum difference occurred in July, 1984. This year in July (see Fig.3.7) relative maximum of ice extent and minimum of ice area were observed. That could be explained by two possible reasons: 1. Ice with very small concentration existed during that period; 2. Ice was covered with water and wet snow over large territories. Passive microwave methods do not allow to distinguish between such type of ice and water because of their close emissivity.

Fig.3.7. (a) and (b) demonstrate variability of microwave-derived total ice extent in 1979-2000 for different months. For each month linear trend was calculated. Results are presented in the Table 3.1.

Fig.3.6 Monthly difference between ice extent and area (km^2)

Trends of ice extent for 1979-2000

Table 3.1

Month	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	Year
Trend, (%)	-4,3	-3,4	-4,4	-4,1	-3,2	-4,7	-9,7	-6,7	-7,6	-1,9	-5,2	-4,3	-4,75

Fig.3.7. and Table 3.1. demonstrate, that total ice extent decreased during all the seasons. The minimum negative trend was found for October, maximum negative trend occurred in July.

The seasonality and forcing mechanisms behind the decreases in arctic ice extent in the 1990s were analysed using SMMR-SSM/I data together with meteorological data fields Maslanik *et al.* [1996]. The ice reductions were found to be the most pronounced in the summer, apparently linked to atmospheric circulation anomalies – in particular, an increase in low pressure systems and associated advection of warm air from the Eurasian landmass in the 1990s.

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4. Spatio-temporal variability of sea ice: regional analysis

4.1 Analysis of satellite data

As reported in previous reports, MonArc Task 4 was regional statistical analysis of the SMMR-SSM/I produced in Task 1.

We have analyzed the changes in the total ice area in Barents, Kara, Laptev and East Siberian Seas (see the location of the boundaries of the Arctic Ocean seas on Fig.4.1).

Fig.4.1 Schematic location of the boundaries of the Arctic Ocean seas. (North—European Basin – Greenland, Norwegian, Barents and White seas; Siberian Arctic Water – Kara, Laptev, E. – Siberian, Chukchi (west) seas)

Among the four mentioned seas the Barents Sea shows the largest decrease of the total ice area during the last 20 years. The area of the sea ice has reduced by 103,800 km², which makes 16% of the total ice decrease in the Arctic. The trend in the total ice area in the Kara Sea was measured to be -8% over 20 years. It is 56,700 km² reduction, which is 8% of the whole decrease of the Arctic ice area. The warmest periods observed in the Kara Sea were in 1984/85 and 1995 years. In the end of the period of observations we see a slight increase on the ice area. In the Laptev Sea the warmest year with the minimum ice area also was in 1995. The trend in total ice area in this sea was -4% over 20 years being 31,000 km² (5% of the total ice reduction in the Arctic). In the East Siberian Sea the observed trend was 61,700 km² over the whole period of observations (9% of the total Arctic ice reduction), but the warmest period was somewhere in the beginning of the second half of the period of observations – in the 1990-93, after that time the increase of the ice area in this sea has been recorded.

Everywhere the negative linear trend in the total ice area has been received for the whole period of satellite observations. However, it does not mean that the steady decrease of the total ice cover is observed in these seas (see Fig.4.2).

It should be noted that although each region has a negative overall trend, there are some regional variations in the interannual variability. It should also be mentioned that these substantial decreases are largely the result of reduced summer ice, whereas the wintertime reductions are considerably less. This underscores the need to investigate further the detailed spatial variability of the summer ice cover and the winter MY ice cover, as we have subsequently done in MonArc Task 5.

Fig.4.2. Linear trends in total ice area of Barents and Siberian Seas.
(Marks on the time axis correspond to the November of each year.)

4.2. Analysis of regional features in sea ice extent in the Arctic Ocean from Russian data

The variability of sea ice extent in the Arctic Ocean is characterized by an obvious regional peculiarity. In the central part of the ocean occupying the entire near-pole area up to the boundaries of the marginal seas, the seasonal and multiyear changes are not pronounced at all. This is the area of the so-called “perennial” ice whose core is comprised of multiyear and second-year ice. Beyond this area (in the marginal part of the ocean, which includes all seas), the seasonal and multiyear variability in sea ice extent is pronounced, but its character to the west and east of Novaya Zemlya is different. West of the archipelago, i.e. in the North-European Basin where the conditions for unhindered horizontal development of sea ice are preserved the year-round, the seasonal and interannual differences in ice area are most pronounced (Fig.4.4, fig.4.5). To the east of Novaya Zemlya, in the Kara, Laptev, East-Siberian and Chukchi Seas that are completely ice-covered from November to May, these differences are manifested only in the summertime (Fig.4.8, 4.7, 4.3, 4.6, correspondingly). The contribution of some seas to dispersion of sea ice area changes in the Arctic Ocean is presented in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1

Contribution of some seas to dispersion of sea ice area changes in the Arctic Ocean, %%

Regi	X	XI	XII	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX
EG	24	43	55	56	52	51	42	35	29	26	11	11
B	43	57	45	44	48	49	58	65	58	39	15	12
K	24	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	18	22	17
L	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	10	24	21
ES	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	11	26	34
Ch _w	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-3	-4	2	5

Note: EG – East-Greenland waters; B – Barents Sea;
 K – Kara Sea; L – Laptev Sea; ES – East-Siberian Sea;
 Ch_w – western Chukchi Sea.

The contribution of some seas to the total dispersion of mean annual ice area is as follows: EG – 36%, B – 44%, K – 8%, L – 5%, ES – 7% and Ch_w – 0%.

It follows from the Table that the contribution of the Siberian portion of the ice “pancake” to the total dispersion of the total Arctic ice area changes is comparatively small, while the contribution of East-Greenland and Barents Sea ice is overwhelming. In the mean annual expression, the share of the latter comprises 80% of dispersion. This means that the character and the depth of the climatic scale changes in the sea ice extent in the Arctic Ocean observed in the 20th century is mainly governed by the ice formation and melting processes in the North-European Basin.

The dominating significance of this basin in the variability of sea ice extent is clearly manifested in the values of linear trend parameters β . It is specifically noted that the horizontal development of sea ice in the Arctic Ocean was throughout the 20th century under the sign of the decrease of its area. The intensity of this decrease, on average, for a year

expressed by β comprised 56 thousand km²/decade. In the North European Basin, it was 48 thousand km²/decade and in the Siberian arctic waters, it equaled 8 thousand km²/decade.

It should be noted that the secular trends indicate a rather generalized picture of sea ice area changes. A more detailed understanding can be gained taking into account the natural intra-secular stages of their development consistent with the changes in the thermal state of the atmosphere. Four such stages were identified in the 20th century: two stages of the ice cover expansion in the Arctic Ocean (1900-1918 and 1939-1968) and two stages of its reduction (1918-1939 and 1968-1999). Each of these stages is characterized, on average, for a year by the following trend parameters: $\beta=+169$ in 1900-1918, 200 in 1918-1939, +25 in 1939-1968 and 121 thousand km²/decade in 1968-1996.

To investigate the features of trend manifestation within a year everywhere where it was possible, their parameters for each month were also derived in the framework of the development stages (Table 4.2).

Table 4.2

Parameters of linear trend β of sea ice area in the Arctic Ocean by the stages of the stages of development (thousand km²/decade)

Period	1900-1918	1918-1938	1946-1968	1968-1996
October				-77
November				-34
December				-76
January				-104
February				-118
March				-150
April	+121	-134	+6	-173
May	+187	-164	+44	-182
June	+182	-116	+124	-143
July	+195	-342	+198	-154
August	+239	-431	+188	-141
September				-107
Mean annual	+169	-200	+122	-122

As can be seen from the data contained in the Table, the ice extent trend does not change its sign during the year. However, its inclination expressing the intensity of ice cover decrease or expansion depending on the sign, experiences significant seasonal variations. The lowest values of parameter β are noted in autumn and the most significant in spring and summer. However, this conclusion requires further checking being so far of a preliminary character.

Fig.4.3. Deviations of the average for June-September from the mean sea ice area in the East-Siberian Sea

Fig.4.4. Deviations of the annual from the mean for XX Century East-Greenland sea ice areas

Fig.4.5. Change of the deviations from the mean of the annual ice area in the Barents Sea in XX century

Fig.4.6. Deviations of the average for June-October from the mean sea ice area in the western part of the Chukchi Sea

Fig.4.7. Deviations of the average for June-October from the mean sea ice area in the Laptev Sea

Fig.4.8 Deviations of the average for June-October from the mean sea ice area in the Kara Sea

5. Spatio-temporal variability of sea ice: pixel-by-pixel.

5.1 Introduction

Maps have long been used to represent the location of different objects on the earth surface and their superposition in space, but maps are static and qualitative. Geographic information systems (GIS) grew out of the need to have quantitative geographical information, particularly about the distribution of and interactions among earth's resources. GIS technology integrates geographic analysis benefits offered by maps and database operations such as query and statistical analysis and it is probably the best technology currently available for spatial and temporal analysis of data.

Geographic information systems are used to store information with a geographical component to investigate interactions among different parts of any system, which is described by collected data and information, and to manage complex and delicate environmental structures.

A GIS differs from a map in several ways. A map is an analog depiction of the earth's surface, while a GIS records spatially distributed features in digital form. A map simultaneously depicts a variety of features of landscape or waterbody (e.g., topography, land cover type and bathymetry), while a GIS usually stores each feature as a separate data layer, identifying relationships between different layers. A map is static and difficult to update, while a GIS data layer can be easily revised. Although maps can be a form of GIS input or output, a GIS greatly increases the versatility of mapped data because of its wealth of techniques for quantitative analysis of geodata. The end product of a GIS analysis may be a map or data.

A geographic information system is a computer-based system for the manipulation and analysis of spatial information in which there is an automated link between the data and their spatial location.

There are two basic types of GISs, which differ in the way they store data. Raster-based GISs (grid- or pixel-based systems) present the surface as a matrix of grid cells, each with an individual data value. Vector-based GISs portray surface as an aggregation of points, lines and polygons, which are encoded and stored as a collection of x, y coordinates. Each of these data structures has advantages and disadvantages, depending on the type of GIS application. Modern GISs are able to handle both data structures, but still they are more efficient in handling one type of data. Raster-based GISs are in widespread use for spatial analysis because of their computational simplicity and compatibility with remotely sensed data.

5.2 Geographic Information System for SSM/I data on the Arctic sea ice

Dedicated geographic information system was created. This GIS contains SSMI data on sea ice cover in the Arctic. Total ice concentration data were processed for the period from 1979 to 2000 (September's average). Basic map was got from Digital Chart of the World (DCW). It is standard ArcView vector map.

ArcView3.1 has been chosen for this GIS creation because of its well known advantages and worldwide use GIS. ArcView can be used to access data stored in it's own shapefile format, ARC/INFO format, and many others formats. You can add tabular data , such as dBase and .txt, onto your map so that you can display, query, summarize and organize data geographically.

5.3 Approach

SSM/I data sets were converted into ArcView3.1 by using Add Table. After this there are some files with useful information. They are the shape file, it is a standard format of GIS ArcView, .dbf file with latitude, longitude and parameter(s). Raw SSMI data is shown below.

0	38.984	143.884
150	39.351	140.017
37	39.367	139.774
0	39.411	139.042
0	39.424	138.798
22	39.193	128.041
59	39.169	127.800
150	39.145	127.558

Next step was adding this data to view and creating a palette. Result are shown in Fig.5.1 and Fig.5.2. After processing we had raster-based layers, based on passive microwave images. The results were colour-coded maps indicating statistical parameters associated with the ice concentration for each pixel. In addition, results of spatially-detailed analysis were added.

Each point has its own coordinates (latitude and longitude) and ice concentration parameter. For example, if you choose any point you can see ice concentration in this place. Fig.5.3 is an example of it.

ArcView3.1 enables find and mark interesting results. As an example (Fig. 5.4) we marked in yellow colour all points where Septembers trend are equal -30.

Fig. 5.1. Total ice, Septembers average.

Fig. 5.2. The fragment of previous image.

Fig. 5.3 Example of demonstration of points attribute

Fig. 5.4. Example of selection (trend = -30)

Geographic Information System consist of two parts. Second part contained selected data sets, results of analysis and technical reports. Metadata (papers, article etc.) are converted into HTML format with links to each over. Below you can find an example. You can choose year (Table 5.1) and then you'll see page where pictures with results are shown (fig.5.5). Data sets which were converted into GIS are presented by differing image and there are a hyperlink to ArcViews file with it.

Table 5.1

Time period and some statistical characteristics

Years.

1978	1979	1980
1981	1982	1983
1984	1985	1986
1987	1988	1989
1990	1991	1992
1993	1994	1995
1996	1997	1998
1999	2000	2001
Trend	Average ice	

Months

Fig. 5.5 The example of HTML file.

5.4 Results

Total ice concentration were converted into the shape format of GIS ArcView. We processed Septembers average data for the period from 1979 to 2000. After processing we had raster-based layers, based on passive microwave images. The results were colour-coded. Some statistical data were processed during realization this task. September and March trends and average ice means were converted into the shape format of GIS ArcView3.1. The results were colour-coded maps indicating statistical parameters associated with the ice concentration for each pixel.

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6. Comparison with other climate data

MonArc Task 6 has been a multivariate analysis that compares sea ice variability to other climate–ocean variability. Here, we have analysed our MonArc/ModArc SMMR-SSM/I dataset and two unique sets of century-long observational records of surface air temperature (SAT) from AARI, together with atmospheric circulation indices. Statistical methods such as PCA, canonical correlation analysis and wavelet analysis have been applied.

An analysis was made to detect and quantify North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) and other climate signals in the Arctic ice cover (Alekseev G. A. et al, 2001, Bjørgo E. et al, 1997). The spatio-temporal sea ice variations were compared to those from other climatic data sets, including: 1) long meteorological time series from the North Atlantic region and north-western Russia, 2) time series of NAO and other atmospheric circulation indices, 3) 2-D atmospheric-oceanic fields from other analysis.

6.1 NAO, AO and other circulation indices

The North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) and Arctic Oscillation (AO) are different ways of characterizing one of the leading modes of Northern Hemisphere variability (Hurrell J.W., 1995, Thompson D. W. J and Wallace J. M., 1998). The Arctic oscillation is pattern in which atmospheric pressure in northern latitudes switches, or oscillates randomly, between positive and negative phases. The negative phase brings high pressure over the polar region and low pressure at about 45° N latitude – a line that runs through the northern third of the United States and western Europe. The positive phase reverses the conditions, steering ocean storms further north and bringing wetter weather to Alaska, Scotland and Scandinavia and drier conditions to areas, such as California and Spain.

In its positive phase frigid winter air doesn't plunge as far into the heart of North America, keeping much of the United States east of the Rocky Mountains warmer than normal. Significant changes in the Arctic oscillation during the last 30 years have influenced temperature and precipitation patterns throughout the Northern Hemisphere. Those changes might well have been caused by ozone depletion over the northern polar region or a buildup of greenhouse gases.

The AO can be characterized as an exchange of atmospheric mass between the Arctic Ocean and surrounding zonal ring centered ~ 45° N. The observed trend in the AO toward its "high index" polarity (i.e. toward stronger westerlies at subpolar latitudes and lower sea level pressure over the Arctic) is a way of interpreting the observed decrease in SLP over the North Pole and the associated cyclonic tendency in the surface winds over the Arctic.

The North Atlantic Oscillation has been traditionally viewed as a teleconnection pattern with "centers of action" in the Atlantic sector. The perceived dynamical significance of the NAO derives from the strength of its pointwise correlations in the sea-level pressure field. It has recently been suggested that the NAO is a regional expression of the AO.

The NAO index is defined as the normalized pressure difference between a station on the Azores and one on Iceland. The difference between NAO indices is caused by the choice of the stations and period of normalization.

First of all, NAO indexes from different sources were analysed (Fig.6.1). The difference between these indices consists in the use of different periods for normalizing and the choice of the location of the atmosphere centers of action. All the indices presented on fig.6.1 are in a good agreement and correlation coefficient is more than 0.8.

An extended version of the index can be derived for the winter half of the year by using a station in the southwestern part of the Iberian Peninsula. Here we give data for SW Iceland (Reykjavik), Gibraltar and Ponta Delgada (Azores). (a) - SLP anomalies at each

station were normalized related to the 120-year period 1864-1994 ((Hurrell J.W., 1995) (e) – SLP anomalies at each station were normalized related to the 120-year period 1864-1983; (b) – PC timeseries SLP index; (c) – based on the difference of normalized SLP between Ponta Delgada (Azores) and Stykkisholmur. December-February; (d) – the same as c), but annual; f) The NAO calculated from Gibraltar and SW Iceland , (Jones P.D. et al, 1997).

In the present work we used the NAO index from (Hurrell J.W., 1995) (Fig.6.1 (a)).

Fig 6.1. NAO indexes

Autocorrelation function was calculated in order to determine temporal structure of the processes (fig6.2). It is seen from the figure, that autocorrelation function changes confusedly and abruptly, that point to the predominance of short-period oscillations in the spectrum. It does not decrease with time, hence we can speak about non-stationary of the process.

Fig.6.2 Autocorrelation function for NAO index

Typical periods of NAO and AO were determined with the use of the wavelet analysis (fig.6.3). It was found that since the beginning of 80s spectral characteristics have considerably changed indicating the enhanced intensity of these processes. Starting from 1900 oscillations with the period 16-23 years are very strong. Intensive 2-y oscillation appeared in the spectrum in 70s-80s. Analogous results were obtained with the use of spectral analysis (Fig.6.4)

Fig. 6.3. Wavelet power spectrum NAO

Fig.6.4. Periodogram for NAO index

Analysis of AO indexes demonstrates more complicated situation. Correlation between different existing AO indexes much more less and does not exceeds 0.2 Fig.6.5 represents time evolution AO indices (Thompson D. W. J and Wallace J. M., 1998):

- a) NCEP/NCAR reanalysis. Index values are found by projecting the structure of the EOF onto monthly SLP anomalies.
- b) Index based on SAT data. In this case the index values are the expansion coefficient time series of the pattern of SAT anomalies associated with the AO.
- c) Found by projecting the AO pattern onto SLP anomalies.

The AO index varies almost randomly from year to year, with one lag correlation of only 0.7.

Fig.6.5. Time evolution AO indices

The wavelet analysis also demonstrated a great difference between different AO indexes (Fig.6.6). For all the indices oscillations with the period of ~ 16 years were revealed. However, in the first case these oscillations remain constant for the whole period (a), whereas in b) and c) one can find shorter oscillations increasing during recent decades.

Fig.6.6. Wavelet power spectrum of the AO index

Fig.6.7. Autocorrelation function of the AO index

Autocorrelation functions (see for example fig.6.7) of all the considered AO indexes are similar and characterized by abrupt changes, that allow to speak about non-stationarity of the processes.

Correlation coefficient between winter NAO index and total sea ice extent time series from Walsh data is 0.35 from 1901 to 1999 with lag=1 and 0.14 with lag=0. Best correlation was received with the use of 5-y running mean for the period 1950-1975 ($r=0.38$). Correlation between NAO index and sea ice extent from Russian data is rather small for observations covering about 3/4 of the Arctic Ocean region (fig.6.8), however, for annual mean area, covered by the ice in the North-European basin and ice extent in Siberian Arctic basin in the second half of August it is larger and consists -0.35 and -0.19 correspondingly.

All above mentioned conclusions were made for the whole period of observations. Considering correlation between ice extent from Russian data for 3/4 of the Arctic Ocean region and NAO index without smoothing of initial time series we have got very small values ($r < 0.1$). Using polynomial approximation of degree by 10 we have got much more large correlation coefficients ($r = \text{up to } 0.9$). As it was demonstrated in MonArc Task 2, polynomial trends for "Walsh" and "Zakharov" datasets differ, especially for the period 1925-1970. Hence, correlation between NAO index and these datasets is also different and smaller for Walsh data (fig.6.9).

Correlation between Zakharov data and NAO index was calculated for 30-y periods overlapping with 5 years for different months and annual values (see table 6.1). For all seasons maximum correlation was found for the period 1965-1996.

It was also found that correlation between AO index and observations, covering about 3/4 of the Arctic Ocean region is 0.48. It is probably points to the stronger influence of AO to the processes in the Arctic comparing to NAO.

Correlation coefficients between Sea Ice Extent in the Arctic Ocean and NAO index

Table 6.1

Years	annual	April	May	June	July	August
1900-1929	-0.35	-0.24	-0.36	-0.36	-0.27	-0.4
1905-1934	-0.3	-0.25	-0.28	-0.37	-0.2	-0.27
1910-1939	-0.16	-0.26	-0.15	-0.27	-0.07	-0.12
1915-1944	-0.31	-0.42	-0.28	-0.45	-0.2	-0.2
1920-1949	0.06	-0.09	0.29	0.08	0.25	0.21
1925-1954	-0.04	-0.19	0.16	0.09	0.16	0.16
1930-1959	0.07	0.09	0.33	0.18	0.12	0.21
1935-1964	-0.18	0.01	0.22	-0.03	-0.26	-0.27
1940-1969	-0.33	-0.29	-0.17	-0.33	-0.37	-0.32
1945-1974	-0.33	-0.38	-0.22	-0.38	-0.4	-0.29
1950-1979	-0.42	-0.48	-0.39	-0.52	-0.5	-0.34
1955-1984	-0.35	-0.63	-0.4	-0.5	-0.35	-0.21
1960-1989	-0.4	-0.67	-0.54	-0.55	-0.32	-0.23
1965-1996	-0.62	-0.81	-0.75	-0.69	-0.52	-0.45
1900-1996	-0.18	-0.28	-0.24	-0.24	-0.15	-0.14

Fig.6.8. Annual ice extent (Walsh data) and the NAO index

6.2. Comparison with long-term meteorological time series

Long-term temperature records were taken from AARI polar meteorological data base. It includes 2 m temperature data on 38 stations north of 60N. The earliest observations began in 1813 with all observations encompassing the period through 1999. The structure of database and its description are presented in Aleksandrov et al., 1996.

The connection of air temperature and sea ice variability was considered using estimates of the correlation linear relation between their changes. Fig.6.9 and Fig.6.10 indicate station temperature variability and trends, along with the ice extent for North-European sector (Fig.6.9) and Siberian Arctic (Fig.6.10). The smoothed time series of sea ice extent and SAT have been approximated by algebraic polynomials of degree 10. The 1920s-40s warm period is evident in these station data, as is the warming in recent decades. The warming trends are greater further north and over land areas, whereas one area (e.g., coastal western Greenland) has actually cooled since the 1970s in response to the NAO. Increased variability in SAT in recent decades is also evident. The above zero air temperature trend over the study period in the Arctic is consistent with the general tendency of the known air temperature increase on a global scale. It has a corresponding negative ice extent trend in the Arctic

Fig.6.9. SAT and annual mean area, covered by the ice in the North-European basin

Fig.6.10. SAT and ice extent in Siberian Arctic

Correlations between temperature on Arctic meteorological stations (SAT) and ice extent in Siberian Arctic as well for SAT and annual mean area, covered by the ice in the North-European basin are presented on Fig.6.11. It is clearly seen from the figure, that for coastal regions correlation is larger and achieves 0.3, whereas for continental stations it is almost absent

Fig.6.11. Correlation between SAT and ice extent

Correlation between temperature on Arctic meteorological stations (SAT) and AO index is represented on fig.6.12. Correlation coefficients are larger for North-European coastal zone (62 % for Haparanda). Zero correlation locates near Akureyri and Jan Mayen. In Greenland correlation coefficient is also high but has opposite sign.

Fig.6.12. Correlation between SAT and AO index

Summer ice anomaly patterns from Walsh data were calculated and compared with temperature trends. Fig 6.13 represents ice anomalies and temperature trends for the periods 1920-1939, 1945-1964, 1980-1999 for temperature and 1970-1989 for ice. The association between the sea ice and the enhanced warming of the past two decades is pronounced with a substantial reduction pattern around all the Arctic. The patterns are different in the 1920s-1930s warm period and the subsequent cooler period, particularly in the Greenland and Barents Seas. However, the substantial reduction in Northern Hemisphere ice extent seen in the recent warm decades is absent in the earlier warm period.

Fig 6.13. Summer (JAS) ice anomalies and temperature trends for the periods 1920-1939, 1945-1964, 1980-1999 for temperature and 1970-1989 for ice.

Annual sea-ice extent from Russian data since 1900, compared with the annual mean SAT between 70-90°N, indicate the linkage between an extensively reduced ice cover and the 1920s-1930s warming, not seen in Walsh dataset (Fig.6.14). The linkage between the 1940-1965 cooling, is not seen clearly until the late 1950s. However, there is indeed a linkage between the 1920-40 warm event and reduced sea ice, at least for the 3/4 of ice cover where the data are adequate. The correlation coefficient is maximal ($r \sim 0.5$) at 0 lag, implying that the temperature variability alone explains a quarter of the variability in the ice cover.

Fig. 6.14. Annual mean ice area over much of the Arctic Ocean (77% of its area) and annual temperature averaged for 70-90N (A) and Annual mean ice area over much of the Arctic Ocean (77% of its area) and annual temperature anomalies averaged for 70-90N (b)

An analysis of the relation between surface temperature in polar atmosphere and sea ice extent in the AO indicates a strong instability of this relation throughout the 20th century. Table 6.2 presents the correlation coefficients characterizing the closeness of this relation for the series with duration of 30 years.

The causes for a strong temporal instability of the relation between the temperature of polar atmosphere and the arctic ice extent are not yet completely clear. One can suggest that at least one of them might be a low quality of ice data referring to the period of World War II when no observations in the NEB were carried out at all, and to the first years after the war. Ice observations have become systematic only in the late 1950s.

Table 6.2

Correlation coefficients characterizing the closeness of relation between the mean annual sea ice area in the Arctic Ocean and surface air temperature in the latitudinal belt of 85-70° N and its four sectors (0-90°, 90-180°, 180-270, 270-360° E)

Years	Belt 85-70° N	Sector 1 0-90° E	Sector 2 90-180°E	Sector 3 180-270°E	Sector 4 270-360°E
1900-1929	-0,60	-0,74	-0,34	-0,13	-0,33
1905-1934	-0,72	-0,79	-0,43	-0,22	-0,57
1910-1939	-0,78	-0,82	-0,61	-0,36	-0,63
1915-1944	-0,76	-0,78	-0,59	-0,47	-0,55
1920-1949	-0,37	-0,44	-0,36	-0,11	-0,13
1925-1954	-0,29	-0,55	-0,27	-0,02	+0,16
1930-1959	+0,15	-0,13	+0,15	+0,27	+0,19
1935-1964	-0,11	-0,34	-0,01	+0,18	-0,12
1940-1969	-0,35	-0,55	-0,15	+0,12	-0,44
1945-1974	-0,47	-0,57	-0,22	+0,07	-0,57
1950-1979	-0,48	-0,58	-0,24	+0,15	-0,58
1955-1984	-0,38	-0,60	-0,17	+0,27	-0,26
1960-1989	-0,42	-0,63	-0,26	+0,22	-0,09
1965-1994	-0,57	-0,68	-0,38	-0,09	-0,09

The relation between the sea ice extent in the Arctic and the thermal conditions in the atmosphere in the Northern Hemisphere in 1936-1976 were considered in (Zakharov et al., 1978). The area of this ice spreading in summer (in July, August and September) was correlated with mean annual air temperature in the extra-tropical part of the Northern Hemisphere (87.5-17.5° N) and in its latitudinal belts. The coefficient of correlation with the temperature of the extra-tropical part of the Hemisphere was maximum in July (−0.59) and minimum (−0.37) in September. The arctic ice in July had the closest relation to the temperature of the polar latitudinal belt (85-75° N) with the correlation coefficient comprising −0.62. A more detailed quantitative assessment of sea ice relation to the air temperature of the Northern Hemisphere was made in (Abramov et al, 1985; Zakharov, 1996). The dependence between the mean annual ice area in the North-European Basin and the air temperature in the latitudinal belts and at the meteorological stations in polar and temperate latitudes was investigated. The results of this assessment will be commented on a little later.

Availability of new data on the arctic sea ice extent over the entire 20th century and of more accurate data on the surface temperature of the atmosphere allow us to consider the problem of their relationship on a more reliable basis. For a quantitative assessment of this relationship, we have used the series of surface mean annual air temperature in the Northern Hemisphere (Vinnikov et al., 1994; Jones et al., 1994; Wilson et al., 1994), in its latitudinal belts (85-70°, 65-40°, 35-20° N) and (87.5-72.5°, 72.5-57.5°, 57.5-37.5°, 37.5-17.5° N) (Vinnikov et al, 1980) and in the polar belt sectors 85-70° N (0-90°, 90-180°, 180-270°, 270-360° longitude), and the series of mean annual ice areas in the Northern Hemisphere (NH) and in the Arctic Ocean (AO) (Zakharov, 1996). It should be said that mean annual data on sea ice in the NH and in the AO in the pre-satellite era were obtained with some exception by reconstruction. That is why, it was reasonable to perform an assessment of the relation

between the atmospheric temperature and sea ice development using both ice data series (Fig. 6.15). This was also necessitated by the fact that as can be seen from Table 10, the cross-correlation of these series was quite unstable throughout the century.

Fig.6.15. Year-to year change of sea ice extent of Arctic Ocean (a), North European Basin (b) and Siberian Arctic Water

Table 6.3

Correlation coefficients between mean annual ice areas in the Arctic Ocean and in the Northern Hemisphere

Period	Correlation coefficient
1901-1930	0.71
1906-1935	0.66
1911-1940	0.60
1916-1945	0.44
1921-1950	-0.18
1926-1955	-0.07
1931-1960	0.19
1936-1965	0.10
1941-1970	0.13
1946-1975	0.38
1951-1980	0.38
1956-1985	0.48
1961-1990	0.65
1966-1995	0.74

The correlation coefficient between the ice extent series in the Hemisphere and in the Arctic Ocean during the 1901-1999 interval comprises 0.57. The closeness of relation between the 30-year series changes significantly including the change of its sign (from 0.74 to -0.18). The highest correlation coefficients (from 0.60 to 0.74) are typical of the first and the last third of the century while the lowest ones (from -0.18 to +0.13) characterize the time interval between these 30-year periods. The cause of instability of the correlation relation is probably in the quality of ice observation data. Only using a comparative analysis, one can establish what of the series reflects more adequately the real picture of changed ice conditions in the Hemisphere.

First results of such a comparison were obtained from the study of the dependence between the air temperature and the ice area in the AO and in the NH (Table 6.4).

These coefficients definitely indicate instability of the correlation relation between the sea ice development in the AO and in the NH and the temperature in the Northern Hemisphere. The instability is expressed not only in a weaker relation itself in the second third of the 20th century, but also in the change of its sign in some cases. This fact contradicts the physical understanding and its only plausible explanation is an insufficiently high quality of ice data pertaining to this period. In the 1940s and in the early 1950s, ice data for the North-European Basin are either absent at all (1940-1945), or insufficiently reliable.

The comparison of correlation coefficients in columns of Table 6.4 for the AO and the NH suggests that ice of the Arctic Ocean had a greater relation to temperature in the first third of the century whereas ice in the Northern Hemisphere – in the last third of the century. This is probably connected with the spatial differences of climate warming in the 1920s-1930s and the 1980s-1990s (Alekseev, et al., 2001). The warming event in the end of the 20th century was stronger in the sector 180-270° E than in 0-90° E. In the 1920s-1930s, the picture was opposite.

Table 6.4

Correlation coefficients between the air temperature in the Northern Hemisphere and the sea ice area

Years	Mean annual air temperature in the hemisphere					
	Vinnikov et. al.		Jones et. al.		Wilson et. al.	
	S _{AO}	S _{NH}	S _{AO}	S _{NH}	S _{AO}	S _{NH}
1901-1930	-0.55	-0.31	-0.49	-0.38	-0.57	-0.33
1906-1935	-0.62	-0.29	-0.61	-0.34	-0.67	-0.34
1911-1940	-0.70	-0.47	-0.68	-0.49	-0.72	-0.52
1916-1945	-0.59	-0.46	-0.58	-0.61	-0.62	-0.50
1921-1950	0.00	-0.14	-0.15	-0.16	-0.01	-0.13
1926-1955	0.18	-0.14	-0.18	-0.16	0.06	-0.16
1931-1960	0.40	-0.08	0.06	-0.25	0.26	-0.15
1936-1965	0.28	-0.04	0.14	-0.23	0.22	-0.10
1941-1970	0.07	-0.05	0.06	-0.24	0.01	-0.11
1946-1975	-0.07	0.11	0.08	-0.02	-0.07	0.01
1951-1980	0.03	-0.22	0.15	-0.09	0.02	-0.24
1956-1985	-0.07	-0.61	0.09	-0.40	-0.06	-0.61
1961-1990	-0.26	-0.73	-0.07	-0.57	-0.24	-0.72
1966-1993	-0.33	-0.75	-0.20	-0.65	-0.32	-0.74

Note: S_{AO} and S_{NH} are the ice areas in the Arctic Ocean and in the Northern Hemisphere, respectively.

It can be supposed with greater certainty that the relation between the thermal conditions in the atmosphere and sea ice extent should increase with latitude. Therefore, the next step in its study was the use of data on surface air temperature by latitudinal belts of the Northern Hemisphere. Data in Table 12 allow us to state that the closest relation of sea ice to temperature of the polar belt (85-70° N) is really observed becoming less manifested with decreasing latitude. In addition, the changes of correlation coefficients from the beginning to the end of the century confirm the conclusion about instability of relation between the temperature and the sea ice extent.

Of significant interest appear to be the results of correlation between the ice state and the surface air temperature in different sectors of the polar latitudinal belt 85-70° N (Table 6.6). The choice of this belt was not random. The correlation dependence in it between the selected characteristics is more pronounced and hence, the probability of errors in estimating the values of each sector is minimum. Thus, one can more clearly define the area of strong correlation dependence between the temperature and the sea ice extent within the latitudinal belt itself.

As follows from the Table, the highest correlation coefficients are typical of the sector 0-90° longitude where open water adjoins ice the year round and horizontal thermal contrasts are stronger than anywhere else (Fig. 6.16). In the sectors 90-180° and 270-360° longitude, the relation weakens and in the sector 180-270° longitude, it is practically not pronounced. The only exception for this sector (180-270° longitude) is the last third of the 20th century. The correlation coefficient between the temperature and the ice state in the Hemisphere comprises -0.70.

Table 6.5
Correlation coefficients between mean annual air temperatures in the latitudinal circles
and the ice state in the AO and in the NH

Period	T _{85-70 N}		T _{65-40 N}		T _{35-20 N}	
	S _{AO}	S _{NH}	S _{AO}	S _{NH}	S _{AO}	S _{NH}
1900-1929	-0.60	-0.34	-0.39	-0.14	-0.20	0.03
1905-1934	-0.72	-0.34	-0.52	-0.13	-0.30	-0.07
1910-1939	-0.78	-0.41	-0.71	-0.33	-0.39	-0.34
1915-1944	-0.76	-0.41	-0.68	-0.26	-0.29	-0.53
1920-1949	-0.37	-0.19	-0.34	0.03	-0.04	-0.05
1925-1954	-0.29	-0.30	-0.19	-0.07	0.05	-0.07
1930-1959	0.15	0.03	0.16	-0.01	0.08	0.00
1935-1964	-0.11	0.10	0.13	-0.06	0.09	0.07
1940-1969	-0.35	0.04	-0.12	-0.16	-0.12	0.09
1945-1974	-0.47	0.18	-0.13	-0.05	-0.30	0.21
1950-1979	-0.48	0.20	-0.12	-0.20	-0.14	-0.13
1955-1984	-0.38	-0.32	-0.05	-0.40	0.06	-0.28
1960-1989	-0.42	-0.50	0.05	-0.35	0.20	0.04
1965-1996	-0.59	-0.61	-0.28	-0.59	0.04	-0.16
1900-1996	-0.55	-0.22	-0.39	-0.33	-0.28	-0.16

Note: T_{85-70 N}, etc. – mean annual temperature in the latitudinal belt 85-70° N;
S_{AO}, S_{NH} – the sea ice areas in the Arctic Ocean and in the Northern Hemisphere,
respectively.

Table 6.6
Correlation coefficients characterizing closeness of relation between the mean annual
sea ice extent in the AO and in the NH and the surface air temperature in the latitudinal belt
85-70° N and in its sectors

Years	T _{85-70° N}		T _{0-90° longitude}		T _{90-180° longitude}		T _{180-270° longitude}		T _{270-360° longitude}	
	S _{AO}	S _{NH}	S _{AO}	S _{NH}	S _{AO}	S _{NH}	S _{AO}	S _{NH}	S _{AO}	S _{NH}
1901-1930	-0.70	-0.40	-0.75	-0.53	-0.40	-0.02	-0.28	-0.15	-0.50	-0.32
1906-1935	-0.74	-0.36	-0.76	-0.40	-0.47	-0.05	-0.24	-0.38	-0.65	-0.47
1911-1940	-0.72	-0.45	-0.78	-0.36	-0.50	-0.21	-0.26	-0.38	-0.65	-0.47
1916-1945	-0.67	-0.41	-0.75	-0.28	-0.41	-0.35	-0.31	-0.46	-0.56	-0.28
1921-1950	-0.14	-0.21	-0.44	0.00	0.00	-0.29	0.15	-0.28	-0.08	-0.03
1926-1955	-0.08	-0.30	-0.41	-0.12	0.01	-0.36	0.23	-0.27	0.04	-0.11
1931-1960	0.22	-0.06	0.19	0.06	0.33	-0.07	0.33	-0.15	0.02	-0.04
1936-1965	0.06	0.04	-0.19	0.09	0.17	0.00	0.28	-0.03	-0.07	0.08
1941-1970	-0.22	0.05	-0.40	0.06	0.04	0.00	0.13	0.02	-0.44	0.08
1946-1975	-0.34	0.23	-0.47	0.12	-0.06	0.16	0.12	0.31	-0.53	0.13
1951-1980	-0.36	0.15	-0.49	0.12	-0.09	0.29	0.21	0.14	-0.54	-0.20
1956-1985	-0.47	-0.41	-0.60	-0.11	-0.17	-0.15	0.15	-0.31	-0.29	-0.16
1961-1990	-0.53	-0.57	-0.71	-0.30	-0.36	-0.40	0.13	-0.38	-0.06	-0.07
1966-1995	-0.64	-0.67	-0.72	-0.44	-0.42	-0.49	-0.22	-0.60	-0.22	-0.23
1971-1998	-0.33	-0.75	-0.65	-0.37	-0.42	-0.54	0.01	-0.70	0.17	-0.23
1901-1998	-0.50	-0.29	-0.55	-0.12	-0.29	-0.17	-0.19	-0.40	-0.37	-0.14

Fig. 6.16. Mean annual sea ice area in the Arctic Ocean (a) and the temperature in the sector $0-90^{\circ}$ E of the latitudinal belt $85-60^{\circ}$ N in the 20th century. (b)

In order to more accurately define the area with a high correlation relation between the sea ice extent and the surface air temperature, the correlation coefficients in (Abramov et al, 1985) were calculated for each of more than 200 stations of air temperature observations. The length of the series for cross-correlation was equal to 30 years (1946-1975). The map of iso-correlates characterizing the closeness of relation between the mean annual sea ice area in the North-European Basin and the surface temperature is presented in Fig. 6.17. It is noted that the first half of the series used as mentioned above is distinguished by a low quality of ice data. That is why, one can expect that the obtained coefficients will be slightly lower than their actual values.

As can be seen from the Figure, the area with a negative correlation relation covers the North Atlantic, part of West Europe and the entire sub-Atlantic Arctic. The core of the correlation relation of this sign with the coefficient values of 0.6-0.7 is located within the North-European Basin. The geographical localization of the core suggests that the most significant features of the surface temperature regime in this basin are connected with the changes in sea ice extent and with the oscillations of its boundary. The ice influence on the thermal conditions in the atmosphere is manifested far from this basin, which becomes possible due to the atmospheric circulation transporting perturbations over large distances from the area of their origin.

The last result of the analysis made concerns the time shift between the changes in the sea ice state and the surface air temperature in different latitudinal belts of the Northern Hemisphere. The shift was determined on the basis of mean annual values, hence a lag or a

Fig.6.17. Iso-correlates of mean annual surface air temperature and sea ice area in the North-European Basin

lead period less than a year could not be naturally obtained. Due to instability of the correlation relation in time, we have used samplings where the relation of ice and temperature is more obvious to determine the time shift. Samplings in the 1900-1939 and 1960-1996 intervals met this condition (Table 6.7).

Table 6.7

Correlation coefficients between the mean annual ice area in the Arctic Ocean and the surface air temperature in the latitudinal belts of the Northern Hemisphere synchronously and with a shift

Latitudinal belt	Temperature shift, years					Time series
	-2	-1	0	+1	+2	
85-70° N	-0.42	-0.50	-0.55	-0.43	-0.29	1900-1996
65-40° N	-0.30	-0.28	-0.28	-0.35	-0.34	
35-20° N	-0.28	-0.25	-0.25	-0.28	-0.31	
85-70° N	-0.55	-0.70	-0.76	-0.71	-0.53	1900-1939
65-40° N	-0.37	-0.50	-0.60	-0.64	-0.54	
35-20° N	-0.28	-0.32	-0.34	-0.38	-0.31	
85-70° N	-0.46	-0.45	-0.54	-0.37	-0.16	1960-1996
65-40° N	-0.23	-0.15	-0.33	-0.26	-0.28	
35-20° N	-0.08	0.00	-0.14	-0.08	-0.16	

Note: sign “+” means the air temperature lag of a year or two years relative to the changes in sea ice area.

As can be seen from the Table, the maximum correlation coefficients are observed either at a zero shift (synchronous relation), or at a temperature lag of one year from the ice extent changes. In the latitudinal belt (85-70° N), where the relations are the closest, the time shift is absent. In the belts 65-40° N and 35-20° N, the maximum coefficients are observed in some cases at a temperature shift of +1 year. This lag of the air temperature changes in the southern latitudinal belts from the Arctic ice development obviously contradicts the leading role of atmospheric factors in the ice extent changes. However, some small differences in the correlation coefficients do not so far give grounds for a clearer conclusion in this respect.

Thus, an analysis of the correlation dependence between the thermal conditions in the atmosphere and the sea ice state based on 100-year data series gives grounds for the following conclusions:

- The dependence between the surface temperature of the atmosphere and the sea ice extent has an unstable character. It is quite well pronounced at the beginning of the century, is absent in the middle and is reconstructed at the end of the century. The cause for the observed weakening of the relation is rather caused by deterioration of quality of the ice data for the war period and during the first years after the war.

- Between the surface air temperature in the Northern Hemisphere, on the one hand, and the sea ice state in the Arctic, on the other hand, there is a physically clear correlation dependence characterized by the coefficients exceeding the significance level. For the series of 1900-1993 and the case where the temperature increases, this coefficient comprises -0.51 according to Vinnikov et. al, -0.60 according to Jones et. al and -0.57 according to Wilson et. al.

- The relation between the sea ice state and the air temperature is spatially non-uniform increasing with latitude. Thus, the correlation coefficients with temperature in the latitudinal belts 35-20°, 65-40° and 85-70° N are equal, respectively, to -0.60 and -0.76 for 1900-1939 -0.34 , and to -0.28 , -0.39 and -0.55 for 1900-1996.

- Within the polar latitudinal belt itself (87.5 – 72.5° N), the relation between the ice extent and the surface temperature is also subjected to strong changes. It is most strongly expressed in the sector 0 - 90° N, i.e, where the most significant interannual and multiyear oscillations in the ice extent occur. The correlation coefficients characterizing the closeness of this relation in the polar latitudinal belt sectors 0-90°, 90-180°, 180-270° and 270-360° longitude in the 1900-1939 interval were equal to -0.80 , -0.57 , -0.39 and -0.62 , and in 1900-1998 -0.55 , -0.29 , -0.19 and -0.37 , respectively. These results indicate a key role of the sub-Atlantic Arctic and especially the North-European Basin in the variability of natural processes in the Northern Hemisphere.

- The results of the analysis of a time shift between the temperature and the development of Arctic sea ice indicate a possibility of the lag of thermal condition changes in the atmosphere from the development of sea ice in the latitudinal belts south of 60 parallel.

6.3. Comparison with oceanography and hydrology data

The Arctic Ocean's freshwater can affect the global ocean through increasing stratification in the Greenland and Labrador seas, thereby reducing deep convection and weakening the North Atlantic's thermohaline circulation. Therefore, the importance of hydrological variability is great, as the Arctic Ocean receives ~10% of the world's river runoff, yet contains only 1% of the world's ocean water.

We examine an ensemble of pertinent long time series of oceanographic and hydrological parameters from the Arctic since 1950, together with baseline time series of sea ice and atmospheric parameters (Fig. 6.18).

The variability of annual SAT anomalies averaged from 70-90°N is shown in Fig 6.18B, together with the winter NAO index (Fig. 6.18A). Figure 6.18D is a composite index of major Siberian river runoff, showing no clear trends, in contrast to the atmospheric and sea ice (Fig. 6.18C) fluctuations on multi-decadal time scales.

Regional-scale ocean variability is evident in an analysis of an exceptionally extensive dataset from the Greenland Sea and adjacent areas since 1950. Figure 6.18E shows composite time series of Greenland Sea Deep Water (GSDW) temperature at 2000m depth (G. Alexeev et al, 2001). These data permit identification of changes in convective process intensity and water mass structure in the region. Two periods of increased convective activity (early 1950s and late 1960s–early 1970s) and two with reduced convection (late 1950s and early 1980s–present) are evident. The latter period of increased convection is linked to atmospheric conditions in the late 1960s, with extremely cold winters, extensive sea ice in the Greenland Sea, accompanied by intensive spreading of the saline AW within the area of the Nordic Seas. Together, these factors contributed to the intensification of the vertical exchange in the Norwegian and Greenland Seas. The cold and relatively fresh GSDW production was extremely high in the central Greenland Sea, while in the southern Norwegian Sea, warm and saline water was redistributed downward, leading to increased gradients between the basins. However, since that “Great Salinity Anomaly” period, the GSDW temperature has risen 0.25°C (mostly in the 1990s), linked to reduced deepwater formation that may portend ocean change (Dickson R.R. et al, 1998).

Correlation was calculated between the parameters, presented on Fig 6.19 together with the temperature on Jan-Mayen station for the period 1950-1999. Fig.6.19(a) shows correlation between annual ice extent from Walsh data (WALSH), NAO index, temperature at Jan Mayen (TJANMAY), anomalies in surface air temperature (TA7090) averaged from 70-90°N, runoff into the Arctic Ocean from the major Siberian rivers, Greenland Sea deep-water (GSDWT) temperature at 2000m depth. Fig. 6.19(b) represents the same values, but for 5-y running means. The significance level calculated for each correlation is a primary source of information about the reliability of the correlation. In order to facilitate identifying those coefficients that are significant we mark significant correlation with a red color. The significance of a correlation coefficient of a particular magnitude changes depending on the size of the sample from which it was computed. The test of significance is based on the assumption that the distribution of the residual values (i.e., the deviations from the regression line) for the dependent variable follows the normal distribution, and that the variability of the residual values is the same for all values of the independent variable.

Fig.6.19 demonstrates, that the correlation is larger for smoothed time series. Largest negative correlation was found between ice extent and NAO index ($r = -0.87$), between ice extent and river runoff ($r = -0.73$). Remarkable correlation was also found between runoff into the Arctic Ocean from the major Siberian rivers and NAO index ($r = 0.63$).

Fig 6.18 Composite of observed variability in the Arctic ocean-climate system since 1950. **(A)** NAO index, **(B)** Anomalies in surface air temperature (SAT) averaged from 70-90°N, **(D)** Runoff ($\text{km}^3 \text{ yr}^{-1}$) into the Arctic Ocean from the major Siberian rivers, **(C)** Arctic sea ice extent from Walsh data, **(E)** Greenland Sea deep-water (GSDW) temperature at 2000m depth

Fig.6.19 Correlation between annual ice extent from Walsh data (WALSH), NAO index, temperature at Jan Mayen (TJANMAY), anomalies in surface air temperature (TA7090) averaged from 70-90°N, runoff into the Arctic Ocean from the major Siberian rivers, Greenland Sea deep-water (GSDWT) temperature at 2000m depth. Marked correlation (red values) are significant

Besides, correlation of sea ice extent from both data sources was calculated for indexes of hurricane activity in the Atlantic region and Globally Integrated Angular Momentum index. It was found, that correlation coefficients are less than 0.1.

6.4. Comparison with fluxes of heat and momentum

The Arctic ocean is the area of extreme differences in the temperature between the ocean and the atmosphere, but the heat exchange is frequently restricted by sea ice cover. The Arctic ocean transfers heat to the atmosphere primary along the periphery, where leads, polynyas, and seasonally open seas allow large fluxes (the heat flux from the sea to the air may reach several hundreds of watts per square meter (Cavaliere D.J. and Martin S., 1985, Schumacher J.D. et al, 1983). On the other hand, the heat and moisture exchange affects the amount of sea ice

Changes in sea ice concentration can affect the atmospheric circulation through changes in surface albedo and surface fluxes of heat, moisture, and momentum. In the framework of this subtask atmosphere-ocean-sea ice fluxes of heat and momentum were analyzed using the NCEP/NCAR reanalysis for the period 1948 to present. Anomalies of these fluxes were related to observed sea-ice anomalies.

Anomalies of heat and momentum fluxes were calculated for the period of satellite observations and compared with ice concentrations anomalies from passive microwave data. Fig. 6.20 represents anomalies of mean zonal sensible + latent flux, zonal and meridional components of momentum flux as well as ice concentration anomalies from satellite derived data. Fig. 6.20 shows that at the beginning of the period under investigation, positive anomalies were observed for all the parameters, for latent + sensible heat flux the maximum anomalies for the whole period were observed at the latitude region near 70N, whereas ice concentration anomalies were located between 70-80N in 1979-1982, penetrating to the 60N in 1984. At the beginning of 90s negative anomalies of all above mentioned parameters were observed to the north from 70N. However, starting from the end of 90s ice concentration anomalies occupied all the considered latitude regions (50-90N), at the same time flux anomalies became positive.

Fig.6.21 (a) presents ice area from satellite data with linear trend subtracted. Using this figure we have chosen the years of ice area maxima (1982, 1988) and minima (1990, 1995). For chosen years spatial distribution of anomalies of ice concentration and heat and momentum fluxes were considered. Fig.6.22 - Fig.6.24. represent anomalies of annual mean heat and momentum fluxes; averaged over 60-90N region and for the years of maximum and minimum ice area. During the years of ice minimum negative anomalies of ice concentration located in Russian Arctic and to the west from Greenland. At the same time small areas of positive anomalies occurred to the east from Greenland and Bering Sea. During the years of relative ice maximum, largest positive anomalies occupied eastern part of Barents, Eastern Siberian and Chukchi Seas, smaller areas of positive anomalies located in Hudson Bay and Boffort Sea. Negative anomalies are almost absent. During the years of ice minimum the area, occupied by negative anomalies is larger, then positive anomalies area during the ice maximum periods. Comparing absolute anomaly values it could be concluded, that they have similar range. Positive upward heat flux anomalies are associated with reduced ice cover, negative upward heat flux anomalies are connected with ice growth and increasing of ice concentration anomalies.

Time evolution of spatially averaged heat and momentum fluxes have small correlation with time evolution of ice area. However, spatial distribution of anomalies have some similar features. Negative ice concentration anomalies coincide with positive anomalies of sensible + latent heat flux. Strong positive anomaly in meridional component of momentum flux in 1995 is in a good correlation with negative ice anomalies, that can be connected with ice export from Fram Strait.

Fig.6.25 shows correlation coefficients between winter (JFM) ice concentrations and heat and momentum fluxes. The largest correlation between heat flux and ice concentration

Fig. 6.20 Anomalies of mean zonal sensible + latent flux (a), zonal (b) and meridional (c) components of momentum flux, ice concentration anomalies from passive microwave data (d).

Fig.6.21. Anomalies of annual zonal mean ice concentrations (passive microwave data) Ice area with linear trend substructured (a) and ice concentration anomalies (b) for the years of maximum and minimum ice area.

Fig.6.22. Anomalies of annual mean sensible + latent heat flux; averaged over 60-90N region (a) and for the years of maximum and minimum ice area (b).

Fig.6.23. Anomalies of annual mean zonal component of momentum flux; averaged over 60-90N region (a) and for the years of maximum and minimum ice area (b).

Fig.6.24. Anomalies of annual mean meridional component of momentum flux, averaged over 60-90N region (a) and for the years of maximum and minimum ice area (b).

Fig.6.25 Correlation coefficients between winter (JFM) ice concentrations and heat and momentum fluxes. A) – sensible + latent heat flux; B) – zonal component of momentum flux; C) – meridional component of momentum flux

changes occur near the ice edge. The maximum correlation coefficient exceed 0.8. Correlation with zonal component of momentum flux is smaller (about -0.4). Correlation between ice concentrations and meridional component of momentum is pretty large, especially for the areas, where meridional momentum fluxes affect ice export. It should be noted, that the surface flux anomalies are reanalysis derived and hence are dependant on model parameterisations. Surface heat flux anomalies associated with changes in ice cover may be overestimated in the NCEP/NCAR reanalysis because of the crude binary representation of the ice cover (Deser C., Walsh J., Timlin M. 2000).

Except in the marginal ice zone, the results (T.S.Ledley, 1988) suggest that the sensible heat flux above the sea is most frequently directed downwards in winter. The simple model results of Makshtas (1991) for Arctic sea ice in winter suggest that over sea ice less than 1 m thick the sensible heat flux is directed upwards, and over thicker ice downwards. This is because radiation balance tends to be negative and it can not be balanced by the heat flux through the ice alone. The turbulent heat flux over leads and polynyas are large, even larger than the heat losses via longwave radiation. In summer, the lower atmosphere is almost in thermal equilibrium with the sea surface (except close to the continent) resulting in reduced fluxes.

At present, a large number of theoretical and experimental studies have dealt with the heat budget of multiyear ice in the Arctic Basin, however, a large number of questions remain unresolved. These pertain primarily to the description of heat transfer processes between the ocean and the atmosphere via leads, polynyas, and thin ice, which have a great effect on the total heat loss from the ocean and even a few per cent of open water or thin young ice make a dominant contribution to the regional heat budget in winter (A.Makshtas, 1991).

The reduction of ice could be related to changes in air temperature, precipitation and snow cover or to advective processes such as increased ice export that accompanies the elevated NAO index in the late 1980s and early 1990s (Kwok and Rothrock, 1999).

Rothrock et al, 1999 demonstrated, that observed decrease in ice thickness could arise from any of the following flux increases:

- a 4 W m^{-2} increase in ocean heat flux from a nominal value of 2 to 4 W m^{-2}
- a 13 W m^{-2} increase in poleward atmospheric heat transport from a nominal value about 100 W m^{-2}
- a 23 W m^{-2} increase in downwelling shortwave radiation from a nominal value about 200 W m^{-2} for about half the year.

6.5. Ice Thickness

The linear trend and the most short-period changes of h are in good agreement with the changes in average air temperature at high latitudes ($75\text{-}85^\circ\text{N}$), presented in Fig. 6.26 (a) as a deviation from the secular norm at running 3-year averaging. The higher the air temperature, the smaller the ice thickness is with the time of ice thickness adaptation to temperature change being quite short. Fig. 6.26 (b) presents a curve of the ice volume exported from Fram Strait taken from Alekseyev et al. (Alekseyev G.V et al, 1997). The exported ice volume is proportional to the atmospheric pressure gradient between two points near the strait (81°N , 15°W and 73°N , 5°E) characterizing actually the atmosphere dynamics in the zone of intense ice export from the Arctic Basin. By diagnosing the development of atmospheric processes, the quasi-uniform temporal periods can be identified (according to Girs-Vangengeim classification, the stages are 3-8 years long) (Girs A.A., 1971). The boundaries of their change mark a sharp modification of large-scale atmospheric process pattern, i.e. the change in the pressure field sign and in the direction of general air mass circulation in the Arctic.

Fig.6.26 Multiyear changes of sea ice thickness in April-May and mean annual temperature (3-y running mean) (a) and mean annual ice export through Fram Strait (approximation by a 7-degree polynomial) (b) in the Arctic basin

The following stages in the interannual atmospheric circulation variability were identified in the study period: 1972-1976, 1977-1980, 1981-1984, 1985-1987, 1989-1996. Within each stage, the frequency of a specific type of atmospheric processes first increases and then decreases, which governs to a great extent the temporal variability of meteorological and hydrological indicators in different areas of the Hemisphere. Each stage is characterized by a specific temperature background which is in agreement (with the inverse sign) with the temporal ice thickness variations in the central polar basin.

The aforementioned features in the temporal variability of meteorological and hydrological values influence the ice export variability in the Arctic. One observes a time lag in the extreme volume of exported ice against the extreme ice thickness. The maximum ice thickness growth or the minimum decrease is manifested in approximately 6 years in the minimum or maximum ice export from the Arctic through Fram Strait. A typical time of the main ice exchange in the Arctic Basin comprises around 6-7 years given that a complete turnover in the known stationary ice gyre in the eastern Arctic comprised 7 years according to the drift of the NP-22 drifting station.

The periods of the decreased ice export from the Arctic basin (1972-1976 and 1981-1984) correspond to the periods of the above zero air temperature anomalies and the decreased ice thickness (Fig. 6.26). The below zero air temperature anomalies and the ice thickness growth correspond to the periods of increased ice export (1977-1980 and 1985-1987). Such regularities contribute to average ice thickness oscillations around some equilibrium value with a period of ice thickness adaptation to the air temperature less than a year and to atmospheric circulation of up to six years given inertia of ice exchange through Fram Strait. This indicates the existence of some self-oscillating process in the ice-atmosphere system at the scale of the Arctic Ocean. The range of ice thickness variations in general for the Arctic Basin in April-May reaches 40% of the seasonal changes.

A long-term climatic signal (a linear approximation) comprised 10 cm in 1972-1992 or 3% of the average ice thickness.

6.6. Causes of sea ice extent changes

The materials presented above disclose the dynamics of marine glaciation in the Arctic throughout the 20th century and its relation to the thermal conditions in the atmosphere. They do not, however, answer the question of their cause-effect relations. A widespread opinion about the controlling role of atmospheric factors is not indisputable. The thermal role of the ocean changes throughout the year. In summer, the ocean is a solar energy accumulator and in winter, it is a thermal energy source. That is why, it is not quite evident that the changes in the state of polar ice observed during the year, from year-to-year, etc. are determined exclusively by the factors regulating the heat fluxes in the atmosphere (concentration of greenhouse gases and volcanic dustiness). In winter when the ocean heats the atmosphere, these changes can be governed by the causes that regulate the vertical heat fluxes in the ocean itself. We shall consider some arguments in favor of the important role of this oceanic factor in the horizontal development of sea ice cover.

Table 6.8 includes monthly averages of sea ice extent in the Northern Hemisphere and in some of its regions during the full annual cycle of development.

Table 6.8

Monthly averages of sea ice area in the Northern Hemisphere and in some of its regions, thousand km²

	X	XI	XII	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX
NH	9728	1192 8	1323 0	1442 6	1520 7	1541 6	1504 5	1385 1	1234 1	1037 6	8749	8020
AO	7496	8386	8696	8921	9053	9083	9082	8966	8520	7876	6960	6444
NEB	618	942	1252	1477	1609	1639	1638	1522	1267	918	586	451
EG	375	507	644	737	788	800	787	742	681	582	423	326

Note: NH – Northern Hemisphere, AO – Arctic Ocean, NEB – North-European Basin, EG – East-Greenland waters.

Regardless of whether the tabular data refer to the entire ice cover or only to some of its parts, of interest is one remarkable peculiarity of its intra-annual development. It is expressed in the fact that the seasonal cycle of the ice cover development is asymmetric relative to its mean multiyear level. The summer minimum is clearly pronounced occurring in all cases in September. The maximum is on the contrary unpronounced extending over three winter months: February, March and April. It is surprising that a sharp slowing or to be more exact the end of the ice cover expansion occurs at the height of winter when the surface air temperature corresponds or is close to the annual minimum. A fragment of the annual cycle referring to the Greenland Sea presented in Fig. 6.27 can serve as a specific example of such ice cover development. The Figure is based on weekly satellite data (Arctic and Antarctic Sea Ice, 1992). The annual sea ice area maximum during the 1980/1981 winter was achieved by early January. The subsequent decrease of this area cannot be convincingly explained in any way in terms of the leading role of thermal conditions in the atmosphere. One can even assume that the horizontal development of the ice cover from this moment has come under the control of a new unknown factor.

Fig. 6.27 Sea ice area change in the Greenland Sea during the 1980/1981 winter according to data of satellite observation

Additional evidence on the character of dependence between the sea ice extent and the thermal conditions in the atmosphere expressed by a sum of degrees-days of frost is given in Fig.13 referring to the North-European Basin. In the time interval between early October to early January, i.e. during the first half of winter, this dependence can be approximated by a direct line expressed by equation $Y=1.128X+609$, where Y – sea ice area in the North-European Basin in thousand km^2 , and X – the increasing sum of degree-days of frost from October 1 (calculated as an average for 12 stations of the region).

However, with the beginning of the second half of winter and until the end of May, this dependence transforms and attains a different character. The ice cover stops in fact to respond to the changing thermal conditions in the atmosphere and enters the state of stagnation. If there were no significant open water space in the North-European Basin, this phenomenon could be attributed to ice spreading to the shores. But this is not the case. Therefore, it is extremely important to understand the causes restraining the ice cover expansion under the external conditions seemingly quite favorable for this. Without these causes, i.e., with preservation of a linear dependence between the thermal conditions and the ice extent the entire cold period of the year, the ice cover would have comprised 2591 thousand km^2 by the end of May (not taking into account an inverse ice influence on surface temperature). In fact, its area at this time is equal to 1394 thousand km^2 .

Fig. 6.28. Diagram of relation between the sum of degree days of frost and sea ice area in the North-European Basin

To clear up the causes restraining the ice horizontal development, it is necessary to take into account that ice formation starts when the heat flux to the atmosphere from the surface begins to exceed the flux from sea depths. The occurring heat deficit at this is compensated by crystallization heat at water passing to the solid state. It follows from this that everywhere where the heat losses by the ocean during the year are greater than the amount of incoming solar energy (areas with a negative annual radiation balance), real prerequisites for sea ice formation are created. The realization of these prerequisites depends on some conditions that we shall consider below.

In the energy respect, it is known that the Northern Hemisphere can be divided into two parts approximately along a 38° parallel. South of it to the equator, the annual solar energy flux to the Earth-atmosphere system is greater than its losses due to radiation to the world space. This is the area of energy accumulation or its excess. North of it to the pole, the annual flux of short-wave solar radiation is smaller than the total heat loss in the process of long-wave radiation beyond the Earth's atmosphere. This is the area of the energy sink or the energy deficit. Given that the heat deficit at the ocean surface is a necessary ice formation condition, we can say that north of 38° N the potential possibilities for ice formation in the

wintertime exist everywhere. In some areas of this region (in the Arctic Ocean, offshore the east coast of the North American and Asian continents and also in some seas of the temperate zone), these possibilities are actually realized. However, ice is not formed over much of the oceanic space north of this parallel. As is known, this is due to the meridional heat transfer in the atmosphere and the ocean, which compensates the existing heat deficit creating the conditions preventing ice formation.

The role of the oceanic heat maintaining the ice-free regime in the energy sink areas makes us consider the mechanisms that regulate the vertical heat transfer to the ocean surface. The vertical heat loss in the ocean occurs by mixing. Its intensity depends on stability of the water layers, which is determined in the polar oceans (at low water temperatures) predominantly by the vertical salinity gradients and beyond – by the vertical temperature gradient. Due to this, the vertical heat exchange conditions are quite favorable in the warm currents where waters moving to high latitudes cool, become denser and provide a free heat flux to the ocean surface. In the cold currents – the picture is quite opposite. Heating of water in these currents is accompanied with increased hydrostatic stability and decreased oceanic heat flux to the ocean surface. The decreased water salinity in cold surface currents also contributes to this. Thus, the differences in the water density distribution by vertical in warm and cold currents are expressed in the first case in the unhindered oceanic heat export and in the second, in creating the conditions preventing its export to the surface.

The key role of the upper ocean layer structure in regulating the vertical heat fluxes is most well pronounced in the Arctic Basin. Here, below the Arctic water layer with a salinity of about 32‰ and a temperature near the freezing point, Atlantic water is located (with a salinity of more than 34‰ and a temperature higher than 0° C). In 50-100 m depths, these waters are separated by a transient layer with large vertical salinity gradients (halocline), which similar to a chimney damper, screens the Atlantic Ocean flux to the ocean surface (Fig. 29). The total heat flux through the halocline in the central part of the ocean is assessed by first tens of kJ/cm^2 a year (Nazintsev, 1961; Panov et al 1963; Nikolayeva et al., 1970; Treshnikov et al., 1972). Note for comparison that the total heat losses to the atmosphere from the open water surface in the eastern Barents Sea comprise 275-300 kJ/cm^2 a year (Atlas of the Arctic, 1985). The distribution of this flux in the Arctic Basin is presented in Fig. 6.30 from the monograph (Treshnikov et al., 1972). As can be seen, the vertical heat flux in this basin is so restricted that one can speak about the extremely weak thermal permeability of the halocline. This practically complete «disconnection» of Atlantic waters from the energy exchange with the atmosphere makes it inevitable that sea ice is formed in the entire area of its spreading.

The halocline in the Arctic Ocean is genetically connected with surface Arctic waters. These waters extend over the greatest portion of the Arctic Ocean. They move southward farther of all in the Labrador and East-Greenland Current being everywhere accompanied with sea ice. This ice extends over the entire area occupied by surface arctic waters already by the middle of winter. From this time, its development in the horizontal direction stops.

Thus, the main cause restraining the ice cover winter expansion at the present time is the horizontal dimensions of the Arctic halocline, rather than the thermal conditions in the atmosphere. Moreover, the peculiarity of the geographical distribution of sea ice in the Northern Hemisphere depends on the configuration of its external boundary, expressed in the formation of ice tongues of large meridional length (East-Canadian, East-Greenland and Pacific Ocean). Such known phenomena as the ice cape (Odden feature) formation in the area of Jan-Mayen and obstruction of the northern and eastern coast of Iceland owe their origin to the water inflow of decreased salinity in the surface layer and to the locking layer forming at its lower boundary. In summer, when the ocean transforms from the thermal energy source to its accumulator, the halocline stops influencing the state of sea ice. At this time of the year,

Fig. 6.29 Depth of the halocline boundary in March-May (meters) and vertical stability E^8 in the Atlantic (a) and Pacific (b) sectors of the Arctic Basin (1 – $f(S)$; 2 – $f(t)$; 3 – $f(t,S)$)

Fig. 6.30 Heat flux from water to the bottom ice cover surface, kcal/cm^2 over winter (Treshnikov et al., 1972)

the radiation factors governing zonality on Earth play the main role. And in fact, the typical picture of arctic sea ice spreading in winter changes by the end of summer. The ice tongues strongly shorten and their spreading becomes close to zonal. This allows us to suggest that the conditions causing and maintaining the existence of these tongues are manifested predominantly during the colder part of the year.

It is known that the ice extent at this time of the year is in good agreement with the character of surface oceanic circulation. It penetrates farther of all southward to the cold Labrador, East-Greenland and Oyashio currents. In the ocean areas subjected to the influence of warm currents, the situation is different. However, one cannot fully agree with ice advection as the main cause of the development of ice tongues. The fact is that ice comprising these tongues, form predominantly on the spot. The role of advection of polar ice offshore the east coast of Greenland is more noticeable. However, here as noted by F. Nansen, L. Kokh and other investigators, local ice occupies more than half of the ice belt area in the end of winter. All its external portion facing the open sea is comprised of young thin ice formed on the spot. The features of the structure of the upper ocean layer that are governed by advection of polar waters of decreased salinity also play the main role in its formation.

The formation of the surface Arctic water mass started at the time when the atmospheric precipitation and the continental runoff began to prevail over evaporation from the Arctic Ocean surface. The transition from the ice-free to the ice regime has become inevitable as the new water mass spreading over the surface dammed the export of Atlantic heat. From that time the picture of moistening in the Arctic characterized by its excess did not change in principle and no other causes are anticipated except for man made that could change it in the near future. This means that the arctic sea ice whose existence is connected with surface arctic water is not threatened with full disappearance. The increase of the atmospheric temperature under the influence of anthropogenic factors will obviously lead to the decrease of its area in the summertime. However, without changing in principle the existing freshwater balance of the Northern Polar region and the entire modern vertical water structure in the Arctic Ocean with it, it will be impossible to prevent its freezing during the colder part of the year.

The stable state of arctic sea ice whose causes are investigated in (Zakharov, 1978), is an important stabilizing factor of climatic conditions in the Northern Hemisphere. The strong changes of these conditions due to natural causes during short time intervals appear to be impossible due to inertia of the surface arctic water mass. This, however, does not exclude the possibility of their changes restricted by scale. We shall consider now their causes by the example of the 20th century.

Since the main factor providing the open water regime in the areas of the energy sink is heat advection by sea currents, the end of this advection or its significant decrease should lead to freezing without any additional cooling of the atmosphere. The nature has found the way, how to do this a long time ago. This method consists in spreading the locking layer to the areas of constant open water. An opposite result is obtained at the decrease of the locking layer horizontal size. In this case, there is a direct energy exchange between deep Atlantic water and the atmosphere compensating the heat flux from the surface.

The idea that the ice area increase can be achieved at present due to changed haline structure of the upper ocean layer caused by expansion or the decrease of the arctic water mass is confirmed both by calculations and the actual data. It is known that the area of Iceland is usually ice-free the year round. However, from the mid-1960s, the situation has unexpectedly changed here. Sea ice began to advance to the island shore for several years obstructing its north coast and making navigation and fishery difficult in coastal waters. The year 1968 was especially severe. Such conditions near the island coast did not occur here from 1888. Ice blocked the north and east coasts for 180 days. Investigating the causes of this

phenomenon, it was possible to establish that the indications of the forthcoming changes have been already recorded in summer of 1964. They were expressed in the decreased surface layer salinity in the region between Iceland and Jan-Mayen and in the East Icelandic Current. Surface water salinity for the first time over the period of systematic observations decreased below 34.7‰. Next year, waters of decreased salinity and temperature advanced south- and eastward nearing the shores of Iceland. In June 1968, they occupied the area surpassing the observed one at this time in 1965 and 1967 (Malmberg, 1969; Steffansson, 1969).

The deterioration of ice conditions in waters of Iceland in 1964-1968 occurred thus simultaneously with the decrease of temperature and salinity in the upper layer to a depth of approximately 200 m. Discussing these results, Malmberg paid attention to the role of salinity decrease in ice formation. The calculations have shown, in particular, that when the surface layer salinity decreased to 34.7‰ and lower as it was during the unfavorable in ice respect 1965, 1967 and 1968, the cooling of the layer to the freezing temperature was insufficient for convection to spread below this layer. The conditions under which the thermal convection could extend to the lower lying layers and provide the heat flux to the ocean surface, occur only at salinity greater than 34.8‰. Referring to the character of relation between the ice and oceanographic conditions, the author definitely points that the conditions in the ocean act as a cause here.

The role of the polar halocline in the formation, spreading and stability of arctic sea ice impels us to consider a number of natural factors that determine its own horizontal development. This development as shown above is restricted by the surface arctic water spreading area whose size at climatic time scales depends predominantly on the freshwater volume coming to the Arctic Ocean from all sources and runoffs, i.e. in the end, on the freshwater balance of this ocean. The main components of this balance are atmospheric precipitation ($P = 5428 \text{ km}^3/\text{year}$), the continental runoff ($Q_M = 5135 \text{ km}^3/\text{year}$), a decreased salinity water inflow from the Pacific Ocean via the Bering Strait expressed through the freshwater equivalent ($Q_T = 1800 \text{ km}^3/\text{year}$), evaporation ($E = 3337 \text{ km}^3/\text{year}$) and the export of ice and freshened water from the Arctic Ocean to the Atlantic.

The unambiguous disturbance of the freshwater balance for more or less long time should lead to the changes not only in the volume and area of surface arctic waters but also in the integral vertical heat flux in the ocean itself with consequences following from this. Since the decreased heat flux from the ocean under other equal conditions results in the ice mass increase, there are weighty grounds to consider structural transformations in the upper ocean layer as the immediate cause of multiyear oscillations in the arctic sea ice state during the colder period. It is quite another matter in summer. With the onset of warm time, the direction of the heat fluxes between the ocean and the atmosphere changes and the functions of control for the ice cover state are transferred to the latter. This continues for not more than 3-4 months, hence, the winter time processes determine the average picture for the year.

The disturbances of freshwater balance of the Arctic Ocean of some sign or other can considerably affect the ice cover state after a long time, i.e. at scales of climatic intervals. Shorter oscillations, including interannual are most likely caused by other factors. In particular, among others, there is a Beaufort Gyre located to the north of the coast of Alaska and Canada. The role of this gyre in surface water spreading was considered in (Alekseev et al., 2001). Water and ice entrained into the gyre move clockwise and have a component directed to its center. As a result of the influence of this component there is a surge of water deep into the gyre and its sinking along its axis. At decreased circulation, these light surface waters will tend to spread and increase the area of their distribution while at increased circulation, an opposite picture should be observed.

Recognition of the fact that the climatic signal propagates in the direction at which the changes in the ocean precede changes in the sea ice area and the latter – changes of thermal

conditions in the atmosphere, rises many questions. To give an exhaustive answer based only on actual data is so far impossible to-date. To trace the propagation of this signal along the entire chain of cause-effect relations, we shall have to use hypothetical considerations along with the available facts. We have already passed part of the way along this chain (oceanic) and the only thing left is to trace the signal propagation in the atmosphere not forgetting about the problem of disturbance of freshwater balance in the Arctic Ocean.

It is well known that during the period of arctic warming in the 1920s-1930s, the atmospheric pressure in high latitudes noticeably decreased. The negative pressure anomaly covered at this time the polar and sub-polar areas and a zone of temperate latitudes in some places. The pressure drop over much of the Arctic Basin, Alaska and the Canadian Arctic Archipelago from 1900-1919 to 1920-1939 comprised 4 mb and more. This process was accompanied with the increased velocity of the western zonal flow at sea level in high latitudes: between 60 and 80° N by 0.98 in winter and by 0.6 m/s in summer (Villett, 1966). V.Yu. Viese in some of his studies (Viese, 1932, 1939, 1941, 1944) showed that the Atlantic cyclones in the 1920s-1930s spread in the Arctic more northward than in the preceding cold period over hundreds and even thousands of kilometers. This result was further confirmed by the studies of L.A. Vittels (Vittels, 1946, 1957). Comparing the pressure-circulation regime characteristics in 1900-1919 and 1920-1939, he has come to a conclusion that the most significant changes of intensity of anti-cyclonic circulation occurred in temperate and of cyclonic – in high latitudes. The number of cyclones passing across Europe has decreased approximately by 10%, while the number of cyclones crossing the Arctic Seas has increased. Interesting data on the change of dominating pathways of cyclones in the historic period and in the Holocene are presented by G.G. Lamb (Lamb, 1964, 1980). In the opinion of these authors, the increased atmospheric circulation during the second 20-year period of the 20th century has caused not only the Arctic warming but also the northward retreat of the external boundary of sea ice and its area decrease. This viewpoint was not fully recognized due to preserved vagueness in respect of the causes of changes in the atmospheric circulation itself.

The existence of the mechanism for a horizontal ice cover development that does not depend on changing conditions in the atmosphere allows us to consider the occurring changes in air temperature as the consequences of changed underlying surface albedo in the Arctic and in the atmospheric circulation as a result of ice boundary displacement. Since there are some controversial moments in the issue of relations between the ice boundary location and the atmospheric circulation, it makes sense to consider it in greater detail.

It is known that the most important feature of changes in the thermal state of the atmosphere in space is a noticeable decrease of the amplitudes of these changes from high latitudes towards the equator. Due to this, the thermal contrasts between the high and low latitudes at the stages of climatic warming decrease whereas the atmospheric circulation becomes weaker. At the stages of cooling these contrasts between the high and low latitudes increase and the circulation intensifies. The dependence of this kind is confirmed by variations of the meridional temperature gradient in the latitudinal belt of 25-75° N throughout the 20th century (Budyko, Vinnikov, 1973).

However, there is a different conclusion based on actual data in which we could be convinced discussing the studies of Viese, Vittels and Lamb. It is concluded that the development of warming events coincides in time with increases of atmospheric circulation intensity in the Arctic and of cooling events, on the contrary, with its decreases. This “contradiction” is due to the fact that the regional changes in the atmospheric circulation intensity in the Arctic occur in the opposite phase with its changes in general over the hemisphere. During the periods of global climatic warming events accompanied with the atmospheric circulation weakening in the Hemisphere, a displacement of the trajectories of Atlantic cyclones takes place in the northern direction following the retreating sea ice edge.

As a result, an increase of intensity of air transports at a regional scale occurs in the Arctic proper. Given that the regime of atmospheric precipitation is related to the atmospheric circulation intensity, one can speak about its increase in the Arctic during the periods of climatic warming and decrease during the periods of cooling (Bryazgin, Voskresensky, 2000). The consequences of these changes should be logically manifested in the state of the surface Arctic water mass so that during the periods of warming, the tendencies for the growth of its horizontal size will increase and during the periods of cooling – the tendencies for its reduction.

Thus, the succession of events in the climatic system, at which the changes in the ocean are ahead of those in sea ice spreading with the latter being ahead of the changes in the atmosphere, makes it inevitable to recognize self-oscillations as the most probable cause for the development of the natural process. The water turnover in the Northern Hemisphere or to be more exact in its polar branch is the force maintaining this development. The hydrological cycle in the polar branch prescribes the direction of climatic signal and determines the order of its transfer from one component of this system to the other.

Fig. 6.31 presents a conceptual scheme of the development of self-oscillations in the climatic system relative to the modern period. It is based on the understanding presented above, that is why any additional explanations relative to the character of relations between the system components are unnecessary. We have included here only the components that play the most important role in the development of self-oscillations. This is only a skeleton of the main interactions during one full cycle of the development of the natural process. The interaction of some components of the system has not yet been sufficiently studied, that is why the scheme can be considered as a program of some kind for future studies. It is also noted that the relation itself between some components of the system has been studied so far at the qualitative level and needs further study. This concerns specifically the dependence of the freshwater balance of the Arctic Ocean on the character of moisture turnover in the atmosphere.

Fig. 6.31 A conceptual diagram of self-oscillations in the system atmosphere-ocean-polar ice relative to the present-day period

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7. Comparison with climate model results

Some of the supplementary funding for 2001 has been used to compare observed climate variability with numerical models in ModArc Task 3. Results from several experiments of ECHAM4 coupled ocean-land-atmosphere climate model, developed at the Max Plank Institute for Meteorology (MPI), Germany were used to investigate natural and anthropogenically-forced climate and sea ice variability in the Arctic.

7.1. Description of the coupled Global General Circulation Model (GCM)

Coupled Global Circulation Models (CGCMs) represent powerful tools for understanding interactions between components of the climate system and for making quantitative projections of future climate change resulting from natural variability and from anthropogenic effects.

The climate model used in the Project is the coupled global ocean-atmosphere model. Its atmospheric component is the fourth-generation general circulation model ECHAM4 developed at the Max-Planck-Institute for Meteorology (MPI). It is a spectral transform model at triangular truncation, used for the range of resolutions, although the bulk of experiments has been carried out at wavenumber 42 (T42) (Roeckner E. et al, 1996). It belongs to the more realistic of current models and has been extensively used by several climate modelling groups. It use spectral transform technique for the “dynamical variables” but a Lagrangian scheme for water vapor, cloud water and tracer constituents. The prognostic variables are vorticity, divergence, the logarithm of surface pressure, temperature, specific humidity, mixing ratio of total cloud water. The non-linear terms and most of the parameterised physics are calculated on the Gaussian transform grid which for T42 resolution has a meshwidth of $2.8^{\circ} \times 2.8^{\circ}$ in latitude and longitude. The vertical domains extend up to 10 hPa, corresponding to a height of approximately 30 km. A hybrid sigma-pressure coordinate system is used. There are 19 irregularly spaced levels with the highest resolution in the atmosphere boundary layer. The lowest level is placed at a height of about 30 m above surface layer. The planetary boundary layer, up to 1,5 km above the surface is resolved by four additional levels. A semi-implicit time scheme is used. The time step for T42, 19 level model is 24 min for dynamics and physics, except for radiation which is calculated at 2 hours interval. Water vapour, cloud water and trace constituents are calculated by a Lagrangian scheme using a shape preserving interpolation to eliminate spurious minima and maxima. Subgrid scale processes such as radiation., cloud formation, precipitation, convection, turbulent mixing, land-surface processes and gravity wave drag are parameterised. Experiments with individual model components provide insight into the role of various processes and an opportunity to optimise parameterisations; however, the broader range of feedback can only be studied using coupled models. Of particular interest are the processes by which the ice and ocean interact to control water-mass structure in the Arctic Ocean.

The ocean general circulation model used is the OPYC model (The OPYC Ocean General Circulation, 1993), which is based on the primitive equations, isopycnals are used as a Lagrangian vertical coordinates. The basic equations are formulated in flux form as conservation equations for the vertical mean of the mass flux, mass content, the heat content, the salt content and the tracer content. Surface mixed layer is coupled to the interior ocean in order to represent near-surface vertical mixing and to improve the response time scales to atmospheric forcing, which is controlled by the mixed layer thickness. Sea ice model with rheology is included and serves the purpose of decoupling the ocean from extreme high-latitude winter conditions and promotes a realistic treatment of the salinity forcing due to melting or freezing sea ice. Arakava B-grid $130^{\circ} \times 63^{\circ}$ was used in the horizontal discretization

scheme. A predictor-corrector method in connection with semi-implicit technique is applied for the discretization in time. The ocean model has a vertical resolution of nine layers and explicit mixed layer; its horizontal resolution is twice that of the atmosphere model, increasing toward the equator. The ocean and atmosphere components are coupled by air-sea fluxes of momentum, heat and fresh water.

The ECHAM4-OPYC coupled model has been used successfully in a number of climate change experiments (L. Bengtsson., 1999).

Simulation of the patterns of global warming . The prediction of future climate change is critically dependent on scenarios of future anthropogenic emissions of greenhouse gases and other climate forcing agents such as aerosols. Scenarios of net greenhouse gas and aerosol precursor emissions for the next 100 years or more are necessary to support study of potential anthropogenic impact on the climate system. The scenarios provide inputs to climate models and assist in the examination of the relative importance of relevant trace gases and aerosol precursors in changing atmospheric composition and climate.

The report of Working Group 1 of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) (J.T.Houghton, G.J. Jenkins and J.J. Ephraums, 1995) presented four scenarios of future changes in greenhouse gas concentrations. These scenarios had been used to force the coupled model in several experiments. The radiative forcing of the greenhouse gases CO₂, CH₄, N₂O has been calculated for the change of concentration between 1860-1990. The forcing from anthropogenic sulfate aerosols has been considered in a very comprehensive way by basing the calculation on the actual emissions of SO₂ from sources at the ground. The effect of sulphate aerosols have been included directly through increased single scattering albedo in cloud free atmosphere. For reference, a 300-year control run was performed with fixed equivalent greenhouse gases concentration. Three ECHAM4 experiments were used in our study:

Control run (1860-2160),

Greenhouse warming experiment (1860-2100),

Greenhouse gases + aerosol (direct effect) experiment (1860-2050)

Thus, climate models have been used to make projections of future climate based upon greenhouse gas and aerosol scenarios from IPCC Special Report on Emission scenarios (SRES).

7.2. Sea ice extent, area and concentration

Data on ice concentrations from three ECHAM-4 runs (control run, runs, forced by greenhouse gases and greenhouse gases and aerosols) were used for the calculation of ice extent and ice area through the numerical integration. Sea ice extent was defined as the area with ice concentration of $\geq 15\%$. It was assumed, that the area to the north of 87.86°N is permanently covered with sea ice during whole year.

Annual and seasonal distribution of ice extent and area were calculated for the period 1860-2050 and compared with observational data.

Fig.7.1 presents observed and modeled variations of annual mean NH sea ice extent. Satellite derived data for 1979-2000 has been received in the framework of the project (Johannessen et al.,2000). Observed data for 1901-1999 are from Chapman and Walsh, 1999.

Fig.7.2 demonstrates observed and modeled variations of annual averages of NH sea ice area for the observations and three ECHAM4 runs. The smoothed time series of sea ice extent and area have been approximated by algebraic polynomials of degree 10 to estimate the trends. These trends are very small for the first half of the century, but become much more larger during the second half of the century. A 20 to 50% decrease in sea ice area is calculated to occur by the end of 20th century.

Fig.7.1. Observed and modeled variations of annual averages of NH sea ice extent. Satellite derived data for 1979-2000 are from Johannessen et al., 1999. Observed data for 1901-1998 are from Chapman and Walsh, 1999. The modeled sea ice extents are from three ECHAM4 model runs (control (CRL), runs forced by greenhouse gases (GHG), greenhouse gases and aerosols (GSD)).

Fig.7.2. Observed and modeled variations of annual averages of NH sea ice area. Observed data for 1979-2000 are microwave-derived ice area. The modeled sea ice areas are from ECHAM4 l runs: (control (CRL), forced by greenhouse gases (GHG), greenhouse gases and aerosols (GSD)).

Observed and modeled decrease of NH ice extent and ice area for the period 1979-2000 are presented on fig.7.3 and 7.4 correspondingly

Fig.7.3. Observed and modeled NH sea ice area for the years 1979-2000. Observed data are microwave-derived ice area. The modeled sea ice areas are from ECHAM4 I runs: (control (CRL), forced by greenhouse gases (GHG), greenhouse gases and aerosols (GSD)).

Fig. 7.4. Observed and modeled NH sea ice extent for the years 1979-2000. Satellite derived data for are from Johannessen et al., 1999. Observed data for 1901-1998 are from Chapman and Walsh, 1999. The modeled sea ice extents are from three ECHAM4 model runs (control (CRL), runs forced by greenhouse gases (GHG), GHG and aerosols (GSD)).

Observed and modeled decrease of NH ice extent for the different seasons is represented on fig.7.5.

Fig 7.5. Observed and modeled variations NH sea ice extent for March (A) and September (B) Satellite derived data for 1979-2000 are from Johannessen et al., 2000. Observed data for 1901-1998 are from Chapman and Walsh, 1999. The modeled sea ice extents are from three ECHAM4 model runs (control (CRL), runs forced by greenhouse gases (GHG), greenhouse gases and aerosols (GSD)).

The comparison between satellite-derived ice extent and ice area data and ECHAM-4 simulations in the cases of control run, greenhouse gases forcing (GHG) and combined forcing of greenhouse gases and aerosols (GSD) demonstrated that the model realistically reproduces observed annual trends in NH sea ice area and extent, predict continuing substantial extent and area decreases in the next century. All observed data show reduction of NH sea ice area and extent during last few decades. For the ice area the decrease is 3.13% per decade according to data by Johannessen et al., 2000; 1.2% per decade in the case of GSD experiment and 3.9% per decade for GHG experiment. For the ice extent observed decrease is 2.3% for Chapman and Walsh data, 2.3% for Johannessen et al. data. Modeled decrease is 1.7% for GSD and 2.9% for GHG experiments. Thus, for the period of satellite observations the observed trends in ice extent and area are in a very good agreement with the results of ECHAM4 greenhouse gases forced run. However, the model underestimates the ice area and overestimate ice extent, that possibly means, that model data on ice concentrations spread over vaster area whereas absolute model values are less, then observed.

According to previous analysis, the rate of decrease both of ice area and extent become greater comparing trends up to 1999.

A recent comparison of GCM-simulated sea ice extent and observed sea ice trends concludes that there is less than a 2% chance that the 1978-98 sea ice trends arise from natural variability (Vinnikov et al., 1999). On the other hand, 20 years of microwave satellite data may be inadequate to establish that this is a long-term trend rather than reflecting decadal-scale atmosphere-ocean variability such as ENSO and the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO). Interannual variability in the NAO is known to be strongly coupled to fluctuations in arctic sea ice motion and ice export through the Fram Strait, as well as regional sea ice extent. The NAO winter index has also been found to be lag-correlated with the arctic minimum ice area following summer, and hence the following winter MY ice area ($r = -0.54$), such that the NAO index explains ~25% (r^2) of the MY ice variability (Johannessen et al., 1999). However, if the recent trends continue, the arctic sea ice cover could disappear next century, at least in summer, with important consequences for the regional and global ocean-climate system.

7.3. Ice thickness

Spatially averaged ice thickness, as derived from surface observations for 1970-1990 (Nagurnyi *et al.*, 1999), submarine measurements (Rothrock *et al.*, 1999) and three ECHAM4 experiments: control run (CRL), GHG run (forced by greenhouse gases) and GSD run (forced by greenhouse gases and aerosols) were compared and analysed (see fig.7.6).

Nagurnyj's data for 1972-1992 indicates an approximately 10 cm decrease which comprises 3-4% of the average ice thickness. According to Rothrock's data from early submarine cruises of 1968 to 1976 and during the cruises in the 1990s, mean thickness has decreased 1.4m, or some 40% from earlier period. In the last case decrease is more dramatic, then in the case of GHG experiment, where decrease for the same period consists approximately half a meter. Nevertheless, spatially averaged values of modeled ice thickness are in a good agreement with observations and vary between 2.5-3m up to the 80s.

Fig.7.7 presents the same as Fig.7.6, but for March and September. The reduction of ice could be related to changes in air temperature, precipitation and snow cover or to advective processes such as increased ice export that accompanies the elevated NAO index in the late 1980s and early 1990s (Kwok and Rothrock, 1999).

Rothrock et al, 1999 demonstrated, that observed decrease in ice thickness could arise from any of the following flux increases:

- a 4 W m^{-2} increase in ocean heat flux from a nominal value of $2 \text{ to } 4 \text{ W m}^{-2}$
- a 13 W m^{-2} increase in poleward atmospheric heat transport from a nominal value about 100 W m^{-2}
- a 23 W m^{-2} increase in downwelling shortwave radiation from a nominal value about 200 W m^{-2} for about half the year.

In spite of similarities in the values of observed and modelled averaged ice thickness, there are a lot of differences in spatial ice thickness distribution. Fig.4.8 represents spatial distribution of averaged ice thickness (m), for the years 1972-1988, April

Fig.7.6. Spatially averaged ice thickness (m), as derived from surface observations for 1970-1990 (Nagurnyi et al., 1999), submarine measurements (Rothrock et al., 1999) and three ECHAM4 experiments: control run – CRL, GHG – run, forced by greenhouse gases, GSD – run, forced by greenhouse gases and aerosol

Fig.7.7. The same as fig4.6 but for March and April.

for the cases of a)- control run, b) - GHG experiment, c) - GSD experiment. Multi-year averaged ice thickness was compared with Romanov's atlas data. Model realistically reproduces the main features of spatial distribution such as Kara spur of the ocean ridge, maxima in the coastal zones of East-Siberian Sea, minima in Canadian Arctic and so on. But absolute values differ significantly, model presented larger maxima and smaller minima and illegitimately broadened vaster area.

Fig.7.8. Spatial distribution of averaged ice thickness (m), for the years 1972-1988, April for the cases of a)- control run, b) - GHG experiment, c) - GSD experiment. Multi-year averaged ice thickness was compared with Romanov's atlas data

7.4. Ice volume

The total sea ice volume was defined as the sum over ice thickness at each grid point multiplied by their grid cell area.

Fig.7.9 and fig 7.10 present ice volume (m^3), as derived from three ECHAM-4 experiments: control run, run forced by greenhouse gases, run forced by greenhouse gases and aerosol.

The decrease is apparent throughout the annual cycle. The annual means (fig7.9) show large variability about mean state ($\sim 30 \text{ mln km}^3$) before beginning of 80s. The reduction of the modeled total sea ice volume of % over last decades represents an undoubtedly strong climate signal. The decrease in ice volume within last decades was three to six times larger than within early 20 century.

Fig 7.9. Northern Hemisphere annual Ice Volume as derived from three ECHAM4 experiments: control run – CRL, GHG – run, forced by greenhouse gases, GSD – run, forced by greenhouse gases and aerosol

Fig 7.10. Northern Hemisphere Ice Volume for March and September as derived from three ECHAM4 experiments: control run – CRL, GHG – run, forced by greenhouse gases, GSD – run, forced by greenhouse gases and aerosol

Further satellite monitoring and analysis of the sea ice cover are needed to better estimate patterns and processes behind these changes. For improved assessment and prediction of global warming in the polar regions it is necessary further comparison observational data with output from global coupled climate models.

In order to provide a credible prediction concerning the stability of polar pack ice over the next few decades, both theoretical and observational knowledge of the processes via which the ice, the ocean and the atmosphere interact must be improved. In particular, a position must be attained where predictions of change in the ice regime over short time scales (seasons, years, decades) can be tested against observations.

It will be most informative to observe over the next few decades the changing characteristics of polar pack ice as it seeks a new equilibrium with an atmosphere whose composition is changing progressively in time. The possibility that a transition to an iseseasonable ice-free Arctic Ocean might be irreversible, adds further interest to this study.

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8. Satellite data assimilation into sea ice model forecasts

The main objective of this task was to forecast seasonal sea ice variability using numerical models into which satellite-derived sea ice parameters are assimilated. Sea ice concentrations derived from SSMI data (Task 1) have been assimilated into an implementation of the HYbrid Coordinate Ocean Model (HYCOM) coupled with a dynamic-thermodynamic sea ice model. The model domain covers the entire Arctic, with highest resolution (~25km) in the Fram Strait/Greenland Sea sector, a key area for ocean-climate interaction. The coupled model has now been run at NERSC with realistic atmospheric forcing. Preliminary conclusions were that the overall performance of the model is realistic, and that the ocean-ice model is suitable for inclusion in a fully coupled global climate model (Lisaeter et al., 2000). Sea ice concentrations satellite data have been assimilated to validate the ice variability forecast by the models on a seasonal basis. The assimilation procedure was the Ensemble Kalman Filter (EnKF). The result from this Task will also be evaluated as regards the forecasting component in Task 5.

8.1 Model description

The model used consists of the HYbrid Coordinate Ocean Model (HYCOM) coupled with a dynamic-thermodynamic sea ice model. The dynamic sea-ice model used is based on the elastic-viscous-plastic, EVP, rheology formulation by Hunke and Dukowicz (1997), while the thermodynamic formulation is similar to that in Drange and Simonsen (1996).

The HYbrid Coordinate Ocean Model is a successor of the Miami Isopycnic Ocean Model (MICOM) (but the HYCOM has the different vertical discretization in the top of the ocean and the different representation of vertical mixing processes). HYCOM is isopycnal in the open, stratified ocean and it uses z-level coordinates in the mixed layer (Bleck and Brounra, 1981, Bleck and Benjamin, 1993). The layer density in HYCOM is allowed to deviate from reference density of a layer, and each layer can be set to a minimum thickness. This is a major improvement and can be used to achieve a high vertical resolution near the surface boundary layer, where the coordinate layers become z-layers, while reverting to isopycnal layers in the interior. The higher resolution near the surface layer makes it possible to use sophisticated vertical turbulent mixing parameterizations instead of the bulk mixed layer approach used in MICOM.

The dynamical part of the sea ice model is based upon the viscous-plastic, VP, rheology of Hilber (1979), where sea ice is considered as a two-dimensional continuum. The rheology formulation of this model seems to be the best alternative when it comes to modeling large scale sea-ice dynamics (Kreyscher et al., 2000), but the traditional numerical formulation suffers from strong numerical constraints, forcing the use of implicit numerical methods. The EVP formulation solves this problem by introducing an elastic term in the ice stress tensor. This makes it practically possible to use explicit numerical methods, while still (approximately) achieving the same result as the VP rheology.

The ocean model solves the primitive equations using a split-explicit numerical scheme (Bleck and Smith, 1990) and has C-grid horizontal discretization. The model domain consists of 140×130 grid cells that include the Atlantic and Arctic oceans (figure 8.1). The model grid is generated according to mapping package of Bentsen et al. (1999). The surface boundary conditions are provided from ECMWF reanalysis fields. The present implementation of the model has 22 vertical layers.

8.2. Assimilation procedure

The object of the data assimilation procedure is to combine the model state with observations in order to generate improved estimates of the model fields. The actual analysis

based on the minimizing of a cost function for the model error. This cost function is based on the errors in model prediction and measurements.

For a discrete model the actual model state ψ^f can be related to the true state ψ^t as

$$\psi^f = \psi^t + p^f, \quad (8.1)$$

Figure 8.1. The bathymetry of the Arctic on the model grid.

where p^f is the model error. Later we will refer to ψ as the state vector and the state vector ψ^f as the forecast. Note that the state vector can contain other variables than those we wish to assimilate into our model, and we will get back to the specification of ψ later. We may also relate the measurements (d) to the true values ($H\psi^t$) as

$$d = H\psi^t + \varepsilon. \quad (8.2)$$

Here the ε is the measurement error, and the matrix H is called the measurement matrix. The measurement matrix relates the state vector values to the observed values, and for our application the matrix $H\psi^t$ give us the ice concentration at the measurement locations. The analysis is based on the following assumptions on the error in the model and measurements:

$$\overline{p^f} = 0, \quad (8.3)$$

$$\overline{\varepsilon^f} = 0, \quad (8.4)$$

$$\overline{p^f (\varepsilon)^T} = 0. \quad (8.5)$$

In other words we assume that the measurement error and the model error are uncorrelated, and that the model and observations are unbiased. In addition we define

$$\overline{p^f (p^f)^T} = P^f, \quad (8.6)$$

$$\overline{\varepsilon(\varepsilon)^T} = \varpi^{-1}. \quad (8.7)$$

An improved estimate of the state vector, which takes into consideration the error in the model and observations, can be found through the analysis (ψ^a) that minimizes the discrete cost function \sum :

$$\sum [\psi^a] = (\psi^f - \psi^a)^T (P^f)^{-1} (\psi^f - \psi^a) + (d - H\psi^a) \varpi (d - H\psi^a). \quad (8.8)$$

The result of the minimization procedure can be shown to be

$$\psi^a = \psi^f + (HP^f)^T (HP^f H^T + \varpi^{-1})^{-1} (d - H\psi^f). \quad (8.9)$$

From this expression we can see that the analysis update is dependent upon the difference between observations and simulated values (last parenthesis in (8.9)) at the measurement locations. The dependence upon measurement and model error statistics is also evident through the matrices P^f and ϖ^{-1} . If the observations have larger (smaller) errors we get a smaller (larger) update $\psi^a - \psi^f$. For instance, if we assume that the measurement error is negligible (in the limit $\varpi^{-1} \rightarrow 0$), and take the observation of the analyses then:

$$\begin{aligned} H\psi^a &= H\psi^f + H(HP^f)^T (HP^f H^T + \varpi^{-1})^{-1} (d - H\psi^f) \\ &= H\psi^f + (H(P^f)^T H^T) (HP^f H^T)^{-1} (d - H\psi^f) \\ &= H\psi^f + (d - H\psi^f) = d. \end{aligned} \quad (8.10)$$

The last step was achieved because P^f is symmetric, and in effect, the observed analysed field get the value of the measurements at the measurement locations. The use of the model covariance for the error matrix P^f ensures that we get a spatially smooth update. The analysis given by (8.9) is a basis of many data assimilation schemes, what separates them is how we choose the error matrix P^f .

Since we do not know the precise form of the matrix P^f , we have to make some assumptions about the form of the error. One way of achieving knowledge of model statistic and later on model error statistics is through an ensemble of model states. Such an ensemble for a numerical model can be written in matrix form in the following manner

$$A = [\psi_1, \psi_2, \dots, \psi_{N-1}, \psi_N] \in \mathfrak{R}^{n \times N}. \quad (8.11)$$

Here the ψ_i , $i = 1, \dots, N$ are the members of the ensemble. The number of rows in the matrix,

n , is the dimension of the ensemble members. The matrix \bar{A} is defined as

$$\bar{A} = [\bar{\psi}, \bar{\psi}, \dots, \bar{\psi}, \bar{\psi}] \in \mathfrak{R}^{n \times N}. \quad (8.12)$$

In other words, \bar{A} contains the ensemble mean in each column. We will also need the ensemble perturbations, defined as

$$A' = A - \bar{A} \in \mathfrak{R}^{n \times N}. \quad (8.13)$$

It follows that the sample error covariance matrix for the model can be written as

$$P^f = \overline{(\psi - \psi^t)(\psi - \psi^t)^T}. \quad (8.14)$$

This equation is of little use since we still do not know the true model state, ψ^t . However, our best estimate of the true model state is the mean value of the ensemble, so it becomes natural to use the spread of the ensemble around the mean value as an estimate of the error. This gives us the following estimate of the error covariance matrix:

$$P^f = \overline{(\psi - \psi^t)(\psi - \psi^t)^T} \approx \frac{A'(A')^T}{N-1} \in \mathfrak{R}^{n \times n}, \quad (8.15)$$

where the ensemble covariance matrix is expressed in terms of the ensemble perturbations (8.13). The equation (8.9) can now be expressed in terms of the ensemble perturbations as

$$\psi^a = \psi^f + \frac{A'(A')^T H}{N-1} \left(\frac{HA'(A')^T H^T}{N-1} + \varpi^{-1} \right)^{-1} (d - H\psi^f). \quad (8.16)$$

As can be seen from equation (8.16), the analysis update can be considered as a linear combination of the ensemble perturbations A' .

As we have a way of getting model error statistics from an ensemble of model states, we only have to define how to choose these members. A method such as the Ensemble Kalman Filter (EnKF; Evensen, 1994) integrates several model states and estimates statistics from these states. This method is very good for estimating the true error statistics as it captures the temporal development of the error covariance matrix.

8.3. Observations data set

Basic observation data were derived from the satellite-borne Special Sensor Microwave Imager (SSM/I). Sea ice concentrations assimilated into the model were obtained from passive microwave data (brightness temperatures) using the NORSEX algorithm developed by Svendson et al., 1983. For detailed explanation how to use this algorithm see Hamre et al., 2001. The data have a temporal resolution of approximately one day and are distributed on a 304×448 pixel grid with a spatial resolution $25\text{km} \times 25\text{km}$. The grid is in a polar stereographic projection which is true at 70°N .

This sea ice data set has been analysed statistically to obtain estimates of the annual, seasonal, and monthly variability and trends for the entire Arctic, updating and expanding the results from Johannassen et al. (1995), Bjorgo et al. (1997) and particularly Johannassen et al. (1999).

The SSM/I data was average over seven days and over 25 observation's grid cells before being assimilated into the model. The observation error variance is set to 0,0025.

8.4. Experiment design

To estimate the impact of ice concentration assimilation, two assimilation experiments were run. In the first experiment [1] an ensemble of 100 model states was integrated forward in time. The pseudo random forcing was generated according to the algorithm described by Evensen (1994). Each ensemble member was integrated from October 1998 till July 1999 with assimilation of ice concentration data every 7 days. In the second experiment [2] the ensemble mean was computed and used to initialise a single model, which was integrated forward in time without assimilation over the same time period. Approximately one year time period of model running let us to estimate the impact of assimilation during a season.

The state vector. The state vector ψ was chosen to include both ocean variables and ice variables as these are closely related, and was chosen as follows for each model grid cell:

For each layer (3d) of the ocean model:

- Salinity
- Temperature
- Hybrid layer thickness
- Horizontal velocity components (2)

And from ocean and ice model these 2D variables were included:

- Barotropic velocity components (2)
- Barotropic pressure
- Ice concentration
- Ice thickness

This gives a total of 115 variables for each grid cell. The analysis (8.16) can be calculated for the full model state vector ψ , i.e. all grid points. For this application the dimension for the state vector ψ would be approximately

$$\dim \psi = 140 \times 130 \times (22 \times 5 + 5) \approx 2 \times 10^6. \quad (8.17)$$

This will clearly result in problems if we only have a 100 ensemble members forming a basis for this vector space (the analysis update is a linear combination of the ensemble perturbations). A common practice in data assimilation is therefore to look at the problem locally; i.e. each grid cell value is updated by using observation values in the radius of influence around the grid point. The radius of influence in this study was set to 100km. This way the 100 ensemble members will span the vector space (with dimension 115) if it can be combined to form a basis. Thus the local analysis makes the problem much better behaved and was chosen for this study. Note that the inclusion of variables other than the ice concentration will also force an update of these variables because they can be negatively or positively correlated with ice concentration through the ensemble covariance matrix (equation (8.16)).

8.5. Impact of data assimilation

8.5.1. RMS and STD

To obtain a simple measure on the quality of the update, the root mean square (RMS) of the distance between model ice concentrations and observations and the standard deviation computed from the ensemble (STD) for each assimilation step (k) before and after the analysis were considered.

$$\text{RMS}_k = \sqrt{\frac{1}{m} (d_k - H\bar{\psi}_k)^T (d_k - H\bar{\psi}_k)} \quad (8.18)$$

$$\text{STD}_k = \sqrt{\frac{1}{m} \text{trace}(H_k P_k^f H_k^T)}, \quad (8.19)$$

where d_k is the vector of measurement at assimilation step k , $\bar{\psi}_k$ is the ensemble mean in the same time. Note that (8.18) and (8.19) are calculated in the locations of the observations.

Figure 8.2. RMS, STD for assimilation experiment [1] and for free-run experiment (RMS(WA)) [2].

The RMS and STD for experiments [1] and [2] are plotted in figure 8.2. We can see that the distance between model ice concentrations and observations decreases in each time step after assimilation and generally decreases with the integration forward in time as a result of the assimilation process (RMS). In case of STD we can see the decrease of the deviation with the assimilations as well. If the errors for ice concentrations are well represented, the standard deviation computed from the ensemble should be close to the RMS (and equal to the RMS in case when the measurement error is negligible (in the limit $\varpi^{-1} \rightarrow 0$), because STD gives a measure of the error in ice concentrations for the model integration, i.e. determines model error covariance. In our result (figure 8.2) the tendencies of RMS and STD curves to approach each other are observed. This is both accumulative effect of multiple analyses and of “seasonal variation” in ensemble spread. The curve (RMS(WA)) for the model running without assimilation shows us an increase of the error in the end of the simulating time period.

The conclusion can be made that the analysis draws the model values of ice concentration towards the observations, i.e. the assimilation process improves the model result compared to the free-run model.

8.5.2. Ensemble statistics

The EnKF predicts estimates of multivariate covariance, which are used at each analysis step. The multivariate correlation functions and their spatial and/or temporal variability are of interest, since they determine the impact from the observations when computing the analysis.

Figure 8.3 shows spatial ensemble correlation in the same horizontal grid points between ice concentration and the upper model layer temperature (a), salinity (b) and ice thickness (c) for day 001 (January 1999). The strongest correlation is observed only in the seasonal ice-covered areas of the model close to the ice edge for all these variables. The correlation in areas far from the ice edge is weak or close to zero. In figure 8.3-c) we see strong positive correlation between ice concentration and thickness. The ice concentrations-salinity correlation (figure 8.3-b)) has different behavior along the ice edge towards open water. It changes from weakly positive to strongly negative. The correlation between ice concentration and temperature (figure 8.3-a)) is mostly weakly negative.

Figure 8.3. Spatial ensemble correlation in the same horizontal grid points: a) - between ice concentration and upper layer temperature, b) - between ice concentration and upper layer salinity, c) - between ice concentration and ice thickness.

To further study the properties of multivariate assimilation scheme, we analyzed vertical section with correlation between ice concentration and lower model layers temperature and salinity in the same horizontal grid points. As expected, these values are the strongest close to surface and reduced with a depth (figure 8.4).

Figure 8.4. Ensemble correlation in the same horizontal model grid points for day 001 (January 1999) : a) - between ice concentration and ocean layer temperature, b) - between ice concentration and ocean layer salinity.

The time evolution of the covariance between ice concentration and other variables was obtained for a number of single model points in the Greenland Sea, Baffin Bay, Barents Sea and central part of the Arctic. In figure 8.5 time evolution of covariances between ice concentration and other variables is presented for one of the points in the Barents Sea. The non-zero covariances are observed only during the ice formation/melting period and decrease after assimilation steps. How this covariance provides the model variables update will be described in the next chapter.

8.5.3. Model fields update

Since the state variable ψ contains other variables than ice concentration, an update in the ice concentrations will also lead to an update in these variables. The Ensemble Kalman Filter provides for this update through covariances between ice concentration and other variables. In figure 5.5 we can see the update in ice concentration (a), upper ocean temperature (b), salinity (c) and ice thickness (d) for day 001 (January 1999). We can see that the updates in all variables are small as we expected from the correlation (figure 8.3) and the largest updates are in the ice edge area.

To examine the updates in the vertical levels, we extracted the temperature time-depth sections for a number of single points in different parts of model grid. One of these sections for a point in the Greenland Sea is shown in figure 8.7-b). The updates are observed in depth

down to 500m, especially during the period of ice formation and ice melting when the most significant upper layer temperature updates are occurred (figure 8.7-a).

Figure 8.5. Ensemble covariance before – a) and after – b) assimilation between ice concentration and temperature (red), salinity (green) and ice thickness (black) in single model grid point (37,40) in Barents Sea. The blue curve is a variance of ice concentration.

Figure 8.6. The update of the model for day 001 (January 1999): a) - in ice concentration, b) - upper ocean temperature, c) - salinity and d) - ice thickness

We also examined the time evolution of ice concentration, upper ocean temperature, salinity and ice thickness in different model points (figure 8.8). The figures show that the updates correspond well to the covariances between ice concentration and these variable (figure 8.5).

Figure 8.7. a) - the temperature time evolution for the single model grid point (41,64) in Greenland Sea before (blue) and after (red) assimilation steps;
 b) - time-depth sections simulated mean temperature in the same point.

We can see that the updates take place only for non-zero covariances, i.e. during ice formation and ice melting period.

In case of ice concentration the updated values can be compared with assimilated observations and with free-run model values. The time evolutions of these values are shown in figure 8.9. This comparison shows the impact of assimilation procedure upon updated ice concentrations, drawing them towards the observations every step of analysis. The model

values with assimilation is much closer to the observations than those from the model running without assimilation during ice formation (days 310-352) and ice melting (days 520-562) time periods.

Figure 8.8. The time evolution of a) - ice concentration, b) - upper ocean temperature, c) - salinity and d) - ice thickness in the single model point (37,40) in the Barents Sea before (blue) and after (red) assimilation steps.

8.6. Conclusion

The experiments performed in this study have shown that the sequential assimilation method such as Ensemble Kalman Filter provides the integration of satellite data together with state-of-art models. It is necessary to mention that this type of multivariate data assimilation scheme has not been used for ice concentration before and the results are encouraging. The assimilation of the real data demonstrates that the sequential updating scheme can correct the model evolution and improves the modeled ice concentration field with respect to the real observations. As a result of analysis of RMS, STD and ice concentration time evolution in single points, the main conclusion was made that the assimilation of ice concentration observations improves the estimate of sea ice concentrations compared to a free-run model. This study demonstrates that the ice concentration assimilation is more important for generation of seasonal sea ice variability model forecast, i.e. in the marginal ice zones during ice formation and melting period, because of the specific character of the ice concentration field.

The Ensemble Kalman Filter does not only affect ice concentration as we perform the analysis. Through covariances between ice concentration and other variables these are also updated. Analysis of spatial and temporal changes of model fields and their covariance and correlation with ice concentration before and after assimilation steps shows update of the

Figure 8.9. Ice concentration time evolution for observation's grid point in the Baffin Bay (-60°W, 70°N): black curve - observed values, red curve - values from the model experiment with assimilation [1], blue curve - values from the model experiment without assimilation [2].

model state vector according to ensemble covariance. We have obtained reasonable updated fields of ice thickness, temperature and salinity in ice edge areas, and further work can be done to validate the results of the assimilation against independent data sets for these model fields.

Further, an important step can be to develop a system for real time operation such as the Diadem/Topaz project for the North Atlantic, using the model and assimilation methods implemented.

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Conclusions

The scientific results of the research project on “Monitoring, evaluating and forecasting sea ice and climate changes in the Arctic (MonArc)” have been reached in accordance with the project’s overall objective and the specific objectives. The overall objective has been to analyse data from satellites and other sources in order to determine and evaluate arctic sea ice and climate change. The specific objectives have been to: ■ integrate data from diverse satellite microwave sensors and other sources to produce long sea ice datasets, ■ analyse these and other observational and model data, in order to: ■ determine the spatio-temporal variability, ■ evaluate the variability with respect to observations and modelled variability in the ice–ocean–atmosphere system, ■ forecast sea ice variability using models, and ■ recommend a sea ice–climate monitoring scheme. The lattermost objectives are part of supplementary funds received from the *Området for Internasjonalt samarbeid – Sentral- og Øst-Europa* in 2001. These objectives have been achieved through the six tasks specified in the primary MonArc workplan, as well as tasks in the supplementary funding for the “Monitoring and modelling sea ice and climate in the Arctic (ModArc)” project workplan. The overall objective of the ModArc component has been to integrate and analyse satellite data together with state-of-art models, in order to determine, assess and forecast sea ice and climate variability in the Arctic.

Scientific Highlights

- **Dataset:** The project has produced a unique new dataset of arctic sea-ice concentrations in Task 1. The dataset of *NORSEX Sea Ice Concentration in the Arctic, 1978-1999, Including MY Ice Concentrations in During Winter Months* [Johannessen *et al.*, 2000] has been issued on CD-ROM. This NERSC-NIERSC data product has since been analysed within the project and has attracted interest from the international sea-ice research community.
- **Scientific Research Articles:** The results achieved in the project have been published in international refereed journals, highlighted by the article “Satellite evidence for an arctic sea ice cover in transformation” in the prestigious *Science* [Johannessen *et al.*, 1999]. The article earned the University of Bergen award in 2000 for “Outstanding Research in Marine Sciences”. The second major research article “Interannual variability of water masses in the Greenland Sea and adjacent areas. has been recently published in *Polar Research Polar Research – The Journal of Norwegian Polar Research* [Alekseev *et al.*, 2001]. The third major research article “Arctic Climate Change – Will the Ice Disappear This Century?” is in final preparation for submission to *Science* [Johannessen *et al.*, 2002] shortly after the project’s conclusion.
- **Scientific Assessments:** The results achieved in the first year of MonArc contributed towards two of the project participants (O. M. Johannessen and M. W. Miles) invitation to take part in the latest Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) assessment. This resulted in our contribution to the sea ice assessment in Chapter 2 on “Observed climate variability and change” in *Climate Change 2001: IPCC Third Assessment Report – The Scientific Basis*.
- **Scientific Reviews and Reportings:** The MonArc project’s results have led to invited contributions to national and international scientific review journals, including the

British scientific journal *Science Progress* [Johannessen and Miles, 2000] and the Norwegian popular science journal *Ottar* [Johannessen and Miles, 2001]. There have also been extensive reportings in the mass media in Norway and internationally, particularly following the Johannessen *et al.* [1999] publication in *Science*.

Scientific Results from the Research Activities

The research activities were partitioned into six (6) research Tasks in MonArc and (5) research Tasks in ModArc, of which ModArc Tasks 1 and 2 served to update the results from MonArc Tasks 1 and 3. The Tasks involved different amounts of resources and therefore the amount of results from each Task are different, with MonArc Task 1 and 6 and ModArc Task 3 being the most substantial.

1. Processing and integration of data from satellite sensors

1.1. Processing and integration of satellite data.

Satellite passive-microwave brightness temperature (T_{BS}) data from the Scanning Multichannel Microwave Radiometer (SMMR) (1978-87) and Special Sensor Microwave Imager (SSM/I) (1987-2001) sensors were used to produce and update spatio-temporal series of several arctic sea-ice parameters. The MonArc efforts resulted in a unique new dataset of arctic sea-ice concentrations: *NORSEX Sea Ice Concentration in the Arctic, 1978-1999, Including MY Ice Concentrations in During Winter Months* [Johannessen *et al.*, 2000]. This dataset was issued on CD-ROM and, since the previous reporting period, it has been updated through March 2001 in ModArc Task 1. The approach to obtain the merged SMMR-SSM/I time series for the entire period was described by Bjorgo *et al.* [1997] and Johannessen *et al.* [1999]. Monthly ice concentration (total, first-year (FY) and multi-year (MY) ice) were retrieved – see Figure 1 – and the following parameters were calculated for whole Arctic: ice extent, ice area, mean ice concentration, open water area, and MY ice area.

The verification of the passive microwave-derived estimates of MY sea-ice concentration and boundary has been conducted using different methods. The spatial distributions of the SMMR-SSM/I-retrieved MY ice in each winter 1978-2000 were compared to the preceding summer minimum total ice cover. In addition, monthly SSM/I-derived patterns of MY ice concentration for the winter of 1995/1996, from November through March were analysed in a case study. Visual analysis of SSM/I-derived MY ice concentrations revealed their qualitative correspondence with the other data: namely, MY ice clustering in the central Arctic Basin. Nevertheless, SSM/I patterns show presence of MY ice in areas where it could not be, e.g., the Sea of Okhotsk, the Bering Sea, central and southern parts of the Barents and the Kara seas, and in the Pechora Sea. Therefore we believe that the algorithm for calculation of the MY sea-ice concentration should include a filter which uses *a priori* geographical knowledge on the sea-ice distribution.

1.2 Validation of the multi-year ice estimates using independent satellite data

A comparative analysis has been made between the MY-ice concentrations and boundaries derived from synchronous SSM/I and Russian Okean satellite images. This case analysis was done for the winter of 1994/1995 in the Laptev and East Siberian seas. Several comparisons were conducted for the winter of 1996 and for the April of 1998 in the Barents and Kara seas. The boundary between MY and FY ice could be delineated using satellite high-resolution

radar images. The transition from FY to MY ice was generally quite sharp – from compact FY ice with several inclusions of MY to compact MY ice with concentration near to 100%. It was found that SSM/I reproduced this boundary realistically and in almost all cases the deviations between two estimates were not substantial. MY ice concentrations from radar images have been determined visually, and therefore we compared areas with “pure” FY or MY ice. As compared with radar, SSM/I underestimated MY-ice concentrations, and an average difference between two estimates was about 30% for November-December. Nevertheless, we should take into account, that radar images covered the Eurasian Arctic shelf seas, and further to the north, the SSM/I estimates also reach 100%. For the period January-March SSM/I-derived MY-ice concentrations were above 90% in three cases and 76% in one case. In April, the differences between the two sensors again increased. The SSM/I-derived MY-ice concentrations for the areas with “pure” FY ice generally were $\pm 10\%$. MY-ice concentrations were also calculated for each month of the winter of 1993/94 for the points, corresponding to the locations of two drifting ARGOS buoys, deployed inside the MY massif in the Laptev Sea. The MY-ice concentrations for the locations of these buoys did not significantly deviate from 100%. MY-ice concentrations retrieved from SSM/I-data and ERS Scatterometer radar data, were compared for the winter of 1995/1996. It was found that SSM/I reveals significantly lower MY-ice concentrations in the Canadian Arctic and in the Fram Strait than does the Scatterometer data, although without higher-resolution validation data, it is inconclusive which of these sensors gives more accurate MY-ice retrievals there. In summary, the MonArc/Modar project dataset is regarded as a valuable new baseline dataset for monitoring and analysing the arctic ice cover and its FY-ice and MY-ice components.

2. Processing and integration of other sea ice data

Non-satellite sea ice observational data including the Arctic and Southern Ocean Sea Ice Concentration grids (the so-called “Walsh dataset”) and Russian historical data (the so-called “Zakharov dataset”) from Arctic and Antarctic Research Institute (AARI) in St. Petersburg were acquired and analysed statistically. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) of the Walsh dataset for 1901-1995 revealed the general features of the ice cover’s spatial and temporary variability. A statistical projection of ice concentration anomalies fields onto Empirical Orthogonal Functions (EOFs) 1-3 shows three different locations in “EOF space”, with shifts from one state to another in the early 1950s and late 1970s. The reason of this can be connected with different input-data sources, e.g. start of satellite observations in 1978/79. The data from winter in particular contain heterogeneities due to observational deficiencies, especially before the 1950s; however, the summer data are relatively homogenous around the Arctic. It became evident that the Walsh data may not be adequate to draw reliable conclusions about the earlier periods, especially in winter.

The newly-available Zakharov dataset based on Russian observations covering about 3/4 of the Arctic Ocean region (missing only the Canadian Arctic Archipelago and the Beaufort and Chukchi marginal seas of the western Arctic) was analysed, as well as time series of 1) annual mean area covered by the ice in the North-European basin and 2) late summer ice extent in the Siberian Arctic basin. Spectral and autocorrelation analyses were conducted for both above-mentioned data sets in order to determine patterns of oscillatory behaviour in the ice cover and to estimate the response time of the ice cover to anomalous conditions. The spectral analysis found 18-year and 64-year cycles in both ice extent time series, with a spectral density maximum at 18 years. Wavelet analysis reveal multi-decadal oscillations of ~30 years in Russian data and ~30 years in the Walsh data. However, a wavelet analysis of annual Walsh data does not reveal any oscillations before early 1950s, which further supports

the conclusion about that dataset's deficiencies before 1953. Therefore, in the MonArc Task 6 climate–sea ice analysis, we focused on the Zakharov dataset rather than the Walsh data.

3 . Analysis of hemispheric sea ice trends and variability from satellite data

MonArc Task 3 analysed the dataset produced in Task 1 in order to quantify variability and trends in the arctic ice cover as a whole. The statistical analysis of the 20-year satellite-derived dataset (1978-1998) in the earlier reporting periods has been updated and analysed from 1998 to 2001 in ModArc Task 2. The latter analysis shows that the total ice cover has continued to decrease at a comparable rate (~3% per decade) as found earlier in the project. During the course of the project period, the substantial (14%) decrease found in the MY ice area in winter (1979-1998) has passed through peer-review process and the results have been published in *Science* [Johannessen *et al.*, 1999]. Subsequently, these results led to invited contributions to the journal *Science Progress* [Johannessen and Miles, 2000] and the latest Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) assessment [Folland *et al.*, 2001], and the University of Bergen award for “Outstanding Research in Marine Sciences” in 2000.

The perennial MY-ice area in winter also continued to generally decrease the last three years, as determined in ModArc Task 2. The 1999/2000 total and MY-ice areas were the lowest since the minimum ice year of 1995/96 (Figure 2). However, the satellite dataset remains inadequate to resolve multi-decadal variability –it is conceivable that should atmospheric circulation anomalies seen in, e.g., North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) / Arctic Oscillation (AO) indices during the most recent decades return to “normal”, the ice cover could rebound accordingly. However, as noted in the MonArc Task 6 and ModArc Task 3 results, we suggest strongly that the recent decreases reflect anthropogenic forcing and therefore will most probably continue.

4. Spatio-temporal variability of sea ice: regional analysis

As reported in previous reports, MonArc Task 4 was regional statistical analysis of the SMMR-SSM/I produced in Task 1. It was found that the Barents Sea shows the largest decrease in total ice area from 1978-98. The area of sea ice has decreased 103,800 km², representing 16% of the total ice decrease in the Arctic. The downward trend in the Kara Sea was 56,700 km² (8% of the total ice decrease in the Arctic). The trends in the Laptev and East Siberian seas are also negative, 31,000 and 61,700 km², respectively. It should be noted that although each region has a negative overall trend, there are some regional variations in the interannual variability. It should also be mentioned that these substantial decreases are largely the result of reduced summer ice, whereas the wintertime reductions are considerably less. This underscores the need to investigate further the detailed spatial variability of the summer ice cover and the winter MY ice cover, as we have subsequently done in MonArc Task 5.

5. Spatio-temporal variability of sea ice: pixel-by-pixel

Sea-ice concentration arrays from the SMMR-SSM/I passive microwave dataset produced in MonArc/Modarc Task 1 were converted into the shape format of the ArcView Geographic Information System (GIS). Total ice concentrations retrieved from the satellite data for the period from 1979 to 2000 (September averages) were processed to produce raster-based layers, which were then density-slice colour-coded. MY-ice concentrations from the winter were then processing similarly, providing the basis for analysing the spatial variability of the perennial MY ice cover with respect the summer ice minimum. In addition, the results from a

spatially detailed analysis were added, including statistical parameters such as means and linear trends. The base map was from the Digital Chart of the World (DCW) and is a standard ArcView vector map. The GIS consists of two parts, with the second part containing selected datasets, results of the analysis and technical reports. Metadata are converted into HTML format with links to each other. Statistical and visual analyses of the resulting database have been made, revealing among other things, the specific areas of largest negative linear trend in the total ice and of the perennial MY ice from 1978-2001. It was found that these areas – namely the Siberian marginal seas (e.g., Kara, Laptev and East Siberian) and the Barents Sea – were in close correspondence for both the total ice concentration in late summer and the MY ice in winter. The results corroborate the total ice distribution maps in Parkinson *et al.*, [1999] and the Siberian ice reductions in the 1990s noted by Maslanik *et al.* [1996]. Moreover, the spatial patterns found here provide further support for the reliability of our MY ice retrievals as a baseline dataset for studies of sea ice–climate variability.

6. Comparison with other climate data

MonArc Task 6 has been a multivariate analysis that compares sea ice variability to other climate–ocean variability. Here, we have analysed our MonArc/ModArc SMMR-SSM/I dataset and two unique sets of century-long observational records of surface air temperature (SAT) from AARI, together with atmospheric circulation indices. Statistical methods such as Singular Spectrum Analysis (SSA), PCA and canonical correlation analysis have been applied. An analysis was made to detect and quantify NAO/AO and other climate signals linked to arctic sea-ice variability and trends. Different indices of atmosphere circulation were inter-compared and analysed. Autocorrelation functions were calculated in order to determine the temporal structure of the processes. A wavelet analysis detected periodicities typical of the NAO and AO.

It was found that since the beginning of the 1980s, the spectral characteristics have considerably changed indicating the enhanced intensity of these processes. Winter and summer ice anomaly patterns from the Walsh dataset were calculated and compared with temperature trends calculated for the same periods. The association between the sea ice and the enhanced warming of the past two decades is pronounced with a substantial reduction pattern around all the Arctic. However, the substantial reduction in arctic ice extent seen in the recent warm decades is less pronounced in the 1920-1940 warm period.

To ascertain whether this has a physical explanation or is simply due to data deficiencies identified in MonArc Task 2, we also analysed the Zakharov dataset. Comparison of the annual sea-ice extent since 1900 and the zonal annual mean SAT between 70-90°N indicates the linkage between an extensively reduced ice cover and the 1920s-1930s warming, not evident in the Walsh dataset. The linkage between the 1940-1965 cooling, when one would expect an increasing ice cover, is seen clearly from the mid 1950s – the data from 1940 through the early post WWII years are insufficient to show this. We conclude that there is indeed a linkage between the 1920-40 warm event and reduced sea ice, at least for the 3/4 of the arctic ice cover represented by these data. The correlation coefficient (r) is maximal ($r \sim 0.5$) at 0 lag, implying that the SAT variability alone explains a quarter of the variability in the ice cover.

- The correlation between the winter NAO index and total sea ice extent time series from the Walsh data is 0.4 from 1901 to 1999. The correlation between the NAO index and sea ice extent for the observations covering about 3/4 of the Arctic Ocean region is rather small. However, for annual mean area, covered by the ice in the North European basin and ice extent in the Siberian Arctic basin in August, it is larger and consists of r values of 0.35 and -0.19 correspondingly. It was also found that the correlation between AO index and Zakharov data

is 0.48. In addition, the correlation of sea-ice extent from both historical data sources was calculated for indices of hurricane activity in the Atlantic region and Globally Integrated Angular Momentum index. Anomalies of zonal and meridional fluxes of momentum were calculated for the period of satellite observations and compared with ice concentrations trends from the passive microwave data.

The observed multi-decadal variability in sea ice, atmospheric circulation and SAT has also been associated with large-scale variations in oceanography in the Arctic and northern North Atlantic. In the MonArc project, we have taken advantage of an extensive oceanographic dataset covering the period 1950-1998 in the Greenland Sea and adjacent Nordic Seas areas. It was seen that a simultaneous rise in the NAO index and Greenland Sea Deep Water (GSDW) temperature points to a link between the atmosphere and thermohaline circulation. Weakening in water exchange with the North Atlantic could be the reason for an observed Polar Water recirculation increase within the Nordic Seas. These results have been published in *Polar Record* since the last reporting period [Alekseev *et al.*, 2001]. It was obtained, that largest negative correlation was found between ice extent and NAO index ($r = -0.87$), between ice extent and river runoff ($r = -0.73$). Remarkable correlation was also found between runoff into the Arctic Ocean from the major Siberian rivers and NAO index ($r = 0.63$).

The atmosphere-ocean-sea ice fluxes of heat and momentum were analyzed using the NCEP/NCAR reanalysis for the period 1948 to present. Anomalies of heat and momentum fluxes were calculated for the period of satellite observations and compared with ice concentrations anomalies from passive microwave data. At the beginning of the period under investigation, positive anomalies were observed for all the parameters, for latent + sensible heat flux the maximum anomalies for the whole period were observed at the latitude region near 70N, whereas ice concentration anomalies were located between 70-80N in 1979-1982, penetrating to the 60N in 1984. At the beginning of 90s negative anomalies of all above mentioned parameters were observed to the north from 70N. However, starting from the end of 90s ice concentration anomalies occupied all the considered latitude regions (50-90N), at the same time flux anomalies became positive. During the years of ice minimum negative anomalies of ice concentration were located in Russian Arctic and to the west from Greenland. At the same time small areas of positive anomalies occurred to the east from Greenland and Bering Sea. During the years of relative ice maximum, largest positive anomalies occupied eastern part of Barents, Eastern Siberian and Chukchi Seas, smaller areas of positive anomalies located in Hudson Bay and Boffort Sea. Negative anomalies are almost absent. During the years of ice minimum the area, occupied by negative anomalies is larger, then positive anomalies area during the ice maximum periods. Comparing absolute anomaly values it could be concluded, that they have similar range. Positive upward heat flux anomalies are associated with reduced ice cover, negative upward heat flux anomalies are connected with ice growth and increasing of ice concentration anomalies.

Correlation coefficients were calculated between winter (JFM) ice concentrations and heat and momentum fluxes. The largest correlation between heat flux and ice concentration changes occur near the ice edge. The maximum correlation coefficient exceed 0.8. Correlation with zonal component of momentum flux is smaller (about -0.4). Correlation between ice concentrations and meridional component of momentum is pretty large, especially for the areas, where meridional momentum fluxes affect ice export. It should be noted, that the surface flux anomalies are reanalysis derived and hence are dependant on model parameterisations. Surface heat flux anomalies associated with changes in ice cover may be overestimated in the NCEP/NCAR reanalysis because of the crude binary representation of the ice cover.

7. Comparison with climate model results

Some of the supplementary funding for 2001 has been used to compare observed climate variability with numerical models in ModArc Task 3. Results from several experiments of ECHAM4 coupled ocean-land-atmosphere climate model, developed at the Max Plank Institute for Meteorology (MPI), Germany were used to investigate natural and anthropogenically-forced climate and sea ice variability in the Arctic. Its atmospheric component is the ECHAM4 fourth-generation general circulation model (GCM) developed at MPI. It has 19 vertical levels and a horizontal resolution of 2.8° latitude/longitude. The ocean general circulation model used is the OPYC model, which is based on the primitive equations, isopycnals are used as a Lagrangian vertical coordinates with 11 layers. The horizontal resolution is the same as for the atmospheric part, except it increases to 0.5° at the equator.

Data on ice concentrations from three ECHAM4 runs were used for the calculation of ice extent and ice area through the numerical integration. Sea ice extent was defined as the area with ice concentration $< 15\%$. It was assumed that the area to the north of 87.86°N is permanently covered with sea ice during whole year. Annual and seasonal distribution of ice extent and area were calculated for the period 1860-2050 and compared with observational data. Trends are very small for the first half of the century, but become much larger during the second half of the century. Decreases of between 20 to 50% in sea ice area were calculated for the end of 20th century, with a more substantial reduction ($\sim 70\%$) in the summer ice cover.

Observed and modelled arctic sea ice extent and area for the period of satellite observations (1979-2000) were analysed. The comparison between satellite-derived ice extent and ice area data and ECHAM4 simulations demonstrated that the model realistically reproduces observed trends, predict continuing substantial extent and area decreases in the next century. All observed data show reduction of NH sea ice area and extent during last few decades. For the ice area, the decrease is 3.1% per decade according to passive microwave data, 2% per decade in the case of GSD experiment and 3.8% per decade for GHG experiment. For the ice extent observed decrease is 2.3% for Chapman and Walsh data, 2.3% for passive microwave data. Modelled decrease is 1.7% for GSD and 2.9% for GHG experiments. Thus, for the period of satellite observations the observed trends in ice extent and area are in a very good agreement with the results of ECHAM4 greenhouse gases forced run. However, the model underestimates the ice area and overestimate ice extent that possibly means, that model data on ice concentrations spread over vaster area whereas absolute model values are less then observed. According to previous analysis, the rate of decrease both of ice area and extent become greater in comparison with trends up to 1999.

Spatially averaged ice thickness, as derived from surface observations for 1970-1990 [Nagurnyi *et al.*, 1999], submarine measurements [Rothrock *et al.*, 1999] and three ECHAM4 experiments: control run (CRL), GHG run (forced by greenhouse gases) and GSD run (forced by greenhouse gases and aerosols) were compared and analysed. Nagurnyi's data for 1972-1992 indicate an approximately 10-cm decrease, which comprises 3-4% of the average ice thickness. According to Rothrock *et al.*'s [1999] data from early submarine cruises of 1968 to 1976 and during the cruises in the 1990s, mean thickness has decreased 1.4m, or some 40% from earlier period. In the latter case, the decrease is more dramatic, then in the case of GHG experiment, where decrease for the same period consists approximately half a meter. Nevertheless, spatially averaged values of modelled ice thickness are in a good agreement with observations and vary between 2.5-3m up to the 1980s. Ice thickness averages from ECHAM4/OPYC model were comparable to AARI atlas data for the years 1972-1988 in April.

The reduction of ice is believed to be related primarily to changes in SAT and advective processes such as increased ice export that accompanied the elevated NAO index in the late

1980s and early 1990s [Kwok and Rothrock, 1999]. It will be most informative to observe over the next few decades the changing characteristics of the arctic ice cover as it seeks a new equilibrium with an atmosphere whose composition is changing progressively in time. A recent comparison of GCM-simulated sea ice extent and observed sea ice trends concludes that there is less than a 2% chance that the sea ice trends arise from natural variability [Vinnikov *et al.*, 1999]. However, if the recent melting continues and our model forecasts are accurate, the arctic sea ice cover may disappear by about 70% next century in summer, with important consequences for the regional and global ocean-climate system.

The main results from this study are in preparation for submission to *Science* [Johannessen *et al.*, 2002] shortly after the project's conclusion. A more comprehensive, detailed publication is also in preparation for publication [Kuzmina *et al.*, 2002] – *Monitoring, Evaluating and Modelling Sea Ice and Climate Changes in the Arctic (MonArc/ModArc)*, NIERSC Technical Report No. 19, Nansen International Environmental and Remote Sensing Center, St. Petersburg, Russia.

8. Satellite data assimilation into sea ice model forecasts

In ModArc Task 4, experiments with assimilation of sea ice concentration data derived from SSM/I into implementation of HYbrid Coordinate Ocean Model (HYCOM) coupled with a dynamic-thermodynamic sea ice model have been performed. The assimilation procedure used is the so-called Ensemble Kalman Filter, a method that estimates model error statistics from many parallel model integrations, in our case the ensemble is comprised of 100 members. The ensemble integration was started on day 289 of 1998 and is presently well into the year 1999. To assess the assimilation impact, spatial and temporal distributions of a number of statistic characteristics of model fields (ice concentration, ice thickness, temperature and salinity) were obtained and analysed. As a result of the ice-concentration assimilation through covariance between ice concentration and other variables, these have been updated mostly in the areas close to the ice edge. The main conclusion of this analysis was that the assimilation of ice concentration observations improves the estimate of sea ice concentrations compared to a free-run model.

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There is general agreement among global climate change forecasts using computer models that there will be enhanced warming in the Arctic. This theory also suggests that changes in the arctic sea ice cover may provide early observational indications of global warming. Some evidence of substantial changes in the ice cover has indeed been found using data from satellites and other sources. For example, our satellite image analyses have established a decrease in the coverage of arctic sea ice of about 3% per decade in the past 20 years. Moreover, we have found a 7% per decade decrease in the thicker, multi-year (perennial) ice pack in winter. These results, published in the journal *Science*, are in general correspondence with observed reductions in ice thickness in the Arctic. However, some uncertainties remain regarding ice thickness and how to interpret the melt-back of the ice cover. For example, there have been warm periods prior to the present warming period. However, the present one is larger than previous warming from about 1920-1940. We believe that the previous one was simply a natural fluctuation, whereas the present one is most likely caused to a large extent by human emissions of greenhouse gases. If the recent warming trends continue, the arctic sea ice cover could largely disappear in summer by the end of this century, with important consequences for the regional and global ocean-climate system.

These results are certainly of popular scientific interest. Indeed, the international scientific community, news services and other journalists have written numerous reports in various media around the world, based on our research article in *Science* in 1999. Furthermore, the British scientific review journal *Science Progress* and the Norwegian popular science review journal *Ottar* have published our contributions in 2000 and 2001, respectively.